

Funded by the European Union

D6.2 – Learning material and pilots plan

Document properties

Deliverable number: D6.2

Deliverable title: InCITIES Deliverable D6.2 - Learning material and pilots plan-30.05.2024-version-1.0-Final

Deliverable type: R - Report

Contractual date of delivery: M18 – March 2024

Actual date of delivery: first full version ready 28.03.2024; updated version with LbD experiences, upon request to the European Commission project officer: 31.05.2024

Deliverable authors: Yannick Cornet, Christina Georgouli, Tibor Petrov, Albert Kulla, Jozef Bruk (UNIZA); Isabel Alexandre, Maria do Carmo Botelho, Nuno Nunes, Catarina Ferreira da Silva (ISCTE) Sanna Ketonen-Oksi (LAUREA)

Leading partner responsible for the deliverable: UNIZA

Deliverable reviewer(s): LAUREA, TH Koln

Deliverable related Work Package: WP6

Deliverable dissemination level: Public

Final deliverable version: 1.0

Deliverable total number of pages: 60 + 141 pages in annexes

Project grant number: 101071330

Project acronym: InCITIES

Project name: Trailblazing Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities

Funding scheme: Horizon Europe

Project duration: 36 months

Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05 European Excellence Initiative

Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05-01

Type of action: HORIZON-CSA

Start date of the project: 1 October 2022

Project coordinator: ISCTE

Production properties

Reviewers	LAUREA, TH Köln
------------------	-----------------

Executive summary

The Deliverable D6.2 provides the Learning material and Learning by Developing (LbD) pedagogical model plan which are developed and adopted in UNIZA and ISCTE pilots. This material can serve as an inspiration for future educators who plan similar pilots, using the project's results in different educational settings. The document describes a LbD pilot's plan and methodology for the organisation of training events and short-term, e.g., Summer and Winter, schools. The plan integrates the InCITIES project's LbD pedagogical model which aims at making cities inclusive, sustainable, and resilient. The pilot planning involves securing partners, addressing constraints, creating balanced student groups, and fostering interactive learning environments. It also details the workflow for international, multidisciplinary and multi-learning level LbD implementations and specifics of the pilots, including challenges and strategies for success.

History of changes

Title of the document	Version number	Changes	Who	Date
D6.2 InCITIES Learning material and pilots plan	0.1	Initial version	Yannick Cornet (UNIZA)	17-31.10.2023
Deliverable D6.2 - InCITIES-draft_v0.2	0.2	Marketing-ready version, with course description and benefits	Yannick Cornet (UNIZA)	14.11.2023
Deliverable D6.2 - InCITIES-draft_v0.3	0.3	Updated full draft	Christina Georgouli, Tibor Petrov, Yannick Cornet (UNIZA)	12.03.2024
Deliverable D6.2 - InCITIES-draft_v0.4	0.4	ISCTE pilot plan and content	Isabel Alexandre, Maria do Carmo Botelho, Nuno Nunes, Catarina Ferreira da Silva (ISCTE)	13.03.2024
Deliverable D6.2 - InCITIES-draft_v0.5	0.5	First full version of UNIZA pilot plans ready for review	UNIZA	22.03.2024
Deliverable D6.2 - InCITIES-draft_v0.6	0.6	Reorganisation of deliverables content; all pilot implementation material moved to D6.3; refocused on LbD; picture updates, section 4 updates	ISCTE, UNIZA, Sanna Ketonen-Oksi (LAUREA)	10.05.2024
Deliverable D6.2 - InCITIES-draft_v0.7	0.7	Refinement of deliverable – first full version for review	UNIZA, ISCTE	21.05.2024
InCITIES Deliverable D6.2 - Learning material and pilots plan-31.05.2024-version-1.0-Final	1.0	Final version - Revision of comments received by TH Koln, LAUREA	UNIZA, ISCTE	31.05.2024

Table of contents

Executive summary	2
History of changes.....	3
Table of contents	4
Table of tables.....	5
Table of figures	5
1. KNOWLEDGE-BASED CHALLENGES OF ISR CITIES	8
2. IDENTIFIED CONSTRAINTS	10
3.1 Attracting participants & instructors	10
3.2 Retaining students	11
3.3 Micro-credentials	11
3.4 Plan the pilot ahead of time	12
3.5 Institutional constraints	13
3. IMPLEMENTING LEARNING BY DEVELOPING IN A MULTIDISCIPLINARY INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT	15
4.1 LbD Guidance material.....	16
4.2 Planning and Implementation of LbD pedagogical model principles	17
4. PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING LbD CHALLENGES.....	22
5. PROCESS OF CREATION OF THE LEARNING MATERIAL.....	23
6. PILOT PLAN WORKFLOW.....	25
7. PILOT PLANS.....	27
7.1 UNIZA PILOT PLAN	27
7.2 ISCTE PILOT PLAN	49
8. KEY TAKE-AWAYS	57
ANNEXES	60

Table of tables

Table 1 - ISR themes (WP2) as key challenges to address in ISR cities, and their corresponding disciplines (WP6).....	8
Table 2 - Identified constraints, likelihood and mitigation actions.	13
Table 3 - UNIZA pilot marketing text.	32
Table 4 - Online course overview, 9 modules.....	44
Table 5 - Typical module breakdown.....	45
Table 6 - On-site week schedule.	47
Table 7 - ISCTE pilot marketing text.....	53
Table 8 - Online course overview of the ISCTE school pilot, 9 online session modules.....	54
Table 9 - On-site week schedule.....	56

Table of figures

Figure 1 - Stages of planning and implementation of ISCTE and UNIZA pilots.....	7
Figure 2 - Team role META test statements and evaluation methodology.....	18
Figure 3 - Illustrative screenshot of the Team role META test implementation.	19
Figure 4 - Screenshot for Module 1 evaluation form.	21
Figure 5 - Steps for creation of learning material and feedback loops.	23
Figure 6 - Pilot plan workflow.	25
Figure 7 - Common design of the course marketing materials (course flyer, poster and digital board slide).	35
Figure 8 - An example of course poster placement at UNIZA premises.....	36
Figure 9 - MS Teams background designed for use throughout the course online modules. 36	
Figure 10 - Course PowerPoint presentation template.....	37
Figure 11 - Screenshot of the course registration form on the InCITIES website.	40
Figure 12 - Screenshot of the course description web page.	41
Figure 13 - Screenshot of the course Questions & Answers webpage.....	42

1. INTRODUCTION

The current deliverable 6.2 is framed within WP6 task 6.2 objectives, meant to provide insights regarding a methodology for the organisation of training events and summer schools based on Learning by Developing (LbD) pedagogical model.

The **purpose** of this document is to implement the principles established in deliverable D6.1 Pedagogical Model Strategic Plan regarding the organisation of two pilot schools, one in Slovakia (UNIZA) and one in Portugal (ISCTE). This serves as a source of experiential information for other partners/organisations on how LbD can be implemented, especially to those adapting the approach for the first time. Further details on the actual implementation of the pilot will be described in the next deliverable D6.3 which will include reporting of the two pilots, student achievements and feedback in the 2 roll-out pilots in the widening countries.

The pilot schools aim to implement a ‘proof-of-concept’ that jointly achieve the following key goals within WP6:

1. to develop capacity and experiences on teaching topics relevant for a **transition towards Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient (ISR) cities**, as delineated by the 7 themes of WP2 (the ‘what’);
2. to achieve a shared understanding and practical experience in implementing the **Learning-by-Developing (LbD) pedagogical model**, which requires pilots to be based on a “authentic real-life assignment” (the ‘how’);
3. to attract both **instructors and students from InCITIES partners** by making use of existing EU mechanisms for researcher and student mobility (the ‘who’), and
4. doing so while monitoring and **collecting lessons learned** to include later in the deliverable D6.4 for ensuring continuous learning throughout pilot implementation, including particularly LbD learnings, ISR learnings for WP2 feedback, and administrative learnings for WP5 feedback.

This deliverable concerns itself with the first two goals. Goal #3 will be detailed as part of the pilot implementation report (D6.3 in M33) and goal #4 as part of the final lessons learned and outlook (D6.4 in M36).

This deliverable was due on M15 (March 2024) and was moved to M17 (May 2024) to better accommodate the pilot schedules. Due to the school year requirements, the UNIZA pilot school was planned to take place during M14-16 (February 19th until April 26th 2024). Therefore, the secondary purpose of this document is to collect all completed planning activities from the first ongoing pilot into a single place, so that best practices can be

documented and reused, particularly for the second pilot school to take place at ISCTE during autumn 2024.

Figure 1 below shows the stages and sequence of actions related to planning and organisation of UNIZA and ISCTE pilots. This schematic overview of tasks, provides an understanding of their sequence and interrelations. The overall timeline of pilots is also depicted.

Figure 1 - Stages of planning and implementation of ISCTE and UNIZA pilots.

Section 2 outlines the knowledge-based challenges of ISR cities. The following section 3 presents the constraints together with their mitigation actions, that are identified during pilot planning. The challenges and risks of implementing LbD in a multidisciplinary and international context, and within a pilot based on the Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) are detailed in section 4. How the authentic real-life assignments were selected and defined is explained in section 5. The process of developing the learning material is explained in section 6 and a detailed pilot implementation plan is provided in section 7. Finally, the key takeaways are discussed in section 8.

1. KNOWLEDGE-BASED CHALLENGES OF ISR CITIES

In the deliverable D6.1 Pedagogical Model Strategic Plan, under section 2.3 were introduced the 7 core themes that form the scientific basis for a systemic and integrated approach to making cities more Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient (ISR). How these themes were designed and developed into sub-themes is further explained in deliverable D2.1 “Production of a position paper including contents for each of the 7 HUBS”. To ensure clarity and synergy across the scientific parts of the InCITIES project, it was decided early on to align the description of challenges originally listed in WP6 task 6.2 to those themes and hubs defined by WP2. Table 1 below lists the ISR themes and establishes the correspondence with the underlying disciplines relevant to addressing the challenges of ISR cities in a holistic way.

Table 1 - ISR themes (WP2) as key challenges to address in ISR cities, and their corresponding disciplines (WP6).

#	ISR Theme	Sub-themes	Disciplines listed in WP6 T6.2 descriptions
1	Questioning urban transition	Welfare futures, democracy enhancement, justice and inclusion by spatial design, circular economy, citizen’s behaviour, needs and expectations, enablers of change	systems theory in general, circular economy, planning, backcasting, governance and processes of societal transitions
2	Nature in the city	Sustainable production from nature, adaptation (mitigation) connected to climate changes risks, cross cutting: governance, citizen engagements	environmental science
3	Energy in the city	Energy management, decentralised production, sustainability assessment of energy systems; energy communities, energy modelling and prediction	energy systems
4	Vulnerability, inclusion, and health in the city	Multidimensional inequalities and vulnerabilities, pollution and health impacts, accessibility and disability situations, vulnerable groups and healthcare solutions, well-being economy, vulnerability, and crisis management	health sciences
5	Mobility	Travellers’ needs toward inclusive mobility, first and last mile urban logistics, cycling systems design, transport operations modelling,	mobility systems

		intelligent transport systems and transformation of mobility, monitoring travel behaviour, interventions in public spaces	
6	Digital transition	Cybersecurity and security, sensors in smart cities, business models for smart cities, metrics, and analytics, urban planning and management, digital twins, inclusive digitalisation, RFID and radio-wave propagation in smart cities, Artificial Intelligence impacts on humans	human-centred design thinking
7	Sustainable and resilient cities	Environmental well-being impacts analysis, role of cities in circular economy implementation, infrastructure and territorial resilience, transformative policies analysis, understanding risks.	ecological systems and sustainability principles, life-cycle assessments

The goal of task 6.2 is to support the creation of a common knowledge base on ISR cities in a holistic way that produces learning material addressing the above 7 themes. At the same time, to ensure active and efficient learning, the Pilots to take place at UNIZA (Slovakia) and ISCTE (Portugal) and the teaching material need to be developed based on genuine real-life assignments, what we refer to as “authentic real-life assignments”: the challenge must be real and it must be considered relevant to an external partner, who provides the challenge - it can be a city or the planning office of a governmental institution dealing with urban development or a company. In our case challenges are provided by the project InCITIES Associated Partners. To succeed in these aims, we use the Learning by Developing (LbD) approach (see D6.1 section 3 for details), which is well adapted to real challenges provided by regional associated partners.

The Pilot planning process therefore needs to achieve and reconcile four key conditions:

1. to find and select a willing regional associated partner with a relevant and authentic real-life assignment;
2. to cover and integrate as many of the ISR themes as possible;
3. to find adequate capacities among the InCITIES partners to create learning material, and
4. to ensure the Pilot is designed and the learning material is created along LbD principles and best practices.

Additional constraints to achieve the above are developed in the next section 3.

2. IDENTIFIED CONSTRAINTS

This chapter outlines several constraints that were identified during the process of planning and organising the pilots. This task was implemented under the overarching goal of delivering the expected results while keeping the authentic challenge owners from the ecosystem members engaged at an adequate level and satisfied with the outcome. Constraints are discussed in this chapter, including mitigation actions, relate to attracting instructors and students, retaining students, issues related to micro-credentials, challenges concerning planning the pilot and other institutional constraints.

How these constraints were addressed in the case of UNIZA pilot is discussed in chapter 7.1 and in section 7.2 in the case of ISCTE pilot.

3.1 Attracting participants & instructors

To ensure **participants** enrolment in the WP6 pilots there is a need to identify supporting mechanisms that motivate the participation of attendees. Thus, the InCITIES consortium decided to organise the WP6 pilots as Erasmus+ Blended Intensive Programmes (BIP). Erasmus+ BIPs are higher education mobility actions funded by the European Commission (EC) that support physical and blended mobility of higher education students in any study field and cycle (short cycle, bachelor, master and doctoral levels) as well as of Professors/facilitators/instructors. The Erasmus+ BIP action supports the travel and daily allowance of the attendees coming from a partner High Education Institution (HEI) and enables to provide European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) for the course programme.

According to the EC, the objectives of the Erasmus+ BIP¹ mobility action are to:

- expose students to different views, knowledge, teaching and research methods as well as work practices in a study field in the European and international context;
- develop their transversal skills such as communication skills, language skills, critical thinking, problem solving, inter-cultural skills and research skills;
- develop their forward-looking skills, such as digital and green skills, that will enable them to tackle the challenges of today and tomorrow;
- facilitate personal development such as the ability to adapt to new situations and self-confidence.

¹ EC Mobility projects for higher education students and staff, <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/programme-guide/part-b/key-action-1/mobility-projects-for-higher-education-students-and-staff>

The LbD pilot course organised at UNIZA from February 19th until April 26th 2024 was implemented as a BIP and this is one of the reasons it got attention from students coming from different countries and advanced education in HEI. At UNIZA pilot, 68 applications were received by participants coming from 21 different countries and HEI. Overall evidence of student attendance will be provided in deliverable D6.3 - 2 roll-out pilots in the widening countries (June 2025).

To attract more students, additional efforts were made through various means of dissemination including the project's website and social media, as well as via different networks of all partners.

The BIP action objective is also to enable **instructors** to teach or train abroad as part of their professional development in order to:

- share their expertise;
- experience new teaching environments;
- acquire new innovative pedagogical and curriculum design skills as well as digital skills;
- connect with their peers abroad to develop common activities to achieve the programme's objectives;
- exchange good practices and enhance cooperation between higher education institutions;
- better prepare students for the world of work.

3.2 Retaining students

To retain students for the UNIZA pilot, a collective effort among instructors of all partner universities was made to create a compelling BIP course content. All course material was connected to 2 real-life assignments real-life assignments and course structure was organised such as to involve students in the learning process and provoke interaction. Organisation of the course was handled by different team members, to ensure smooth implementation.

Furthermore, communication with students was constant and efficient, making sure all questions and requests were handled in a prompt manner. A Q&A was created which was enhanced with more items along the way. More details are provided in chapter 7.

3.3 Micro-credentials

Aligned with the InCITIES Grant Agreement, WP6 pilot course should provide micro-credentials. This is well aligned with the LbD method and the BIP action as it enables to learn by developing in a small unbundled unit course awarding ECTS. Micro-credentials correspond

to short focused credential courses, designed to acquire specific skills or knowledge in a particular area and are gaining popularity as they provide a quicker, more affordable way to gain competencies compared to traditional degree programs (Wheelahan & Moodie 2021)². These micro-credentials are offered as stand-alone course programs that can range from a few hours to a few months. These credentials typically aim to enhance professional skills and are particularly valuable for continuing learning, professional development, up-skilling for adapting to job market demands or involving stakeholder partners from the surrounding society, such as the Associated Partners (APs) in the InCITIES project who provide the subjects of authentic real-life assignments as real-life assignments for participant learners to address during the LbD pilot implementations.

The HEI involved in defining the BIPs have jointly established the necessary ECTS, following EC guidelines, for assigning educational micro-credentials to certify the proposed training.

3.4 Plan the pilot ahead of time

The InCITIES consortium identified the need to plan the pilots well-ahead so that the dissemination and communication tasks can be done within enough time enabling participants enrolment and also the partner HEI to allocate BIPs funds for the students and Professors/facilitators travel and accommodation for on-site intensive week. Planning the content of the BIP pilot course and ensuring its smooth implementation need to be well thought out in advance. The pilot BIP online training sessions are accompanied with various tools and equipment, therefore technical issues are expected.

The marketing campaign for UNIZA pilot started the 27th of November 2023, that is 2 months before the course start, and creation of course content and coordination with instructors started 4 months in advance. It can be recommended that dissemination activities and teamwork with instructors begin 6 months before the start of the study.

Learning on UNIZA experience, the marketing campaign for ISCTE pilot is planned to start in June 2024, also in advance regarding the beginning of the ISCTE pilot for end of October 2024. Course content and coordination with instructors is being aligned since the beginning of 2024, when the APs provided their challenges.

² Wheelahan, L., & Moodie, G. (2021). Analysing micro-credentials in higher education: a Bernsteinian analysis. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 53(2), 212–228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2021.1887358>

3.5 Institutional constraints

Anyone who intends to plan a similar pilot, namely one which provides ECTS credits, should also analyse the particular institutional constraints the organising HEI may face. For instance, to provide a new course that awards ECTS, ISCTE must have the unit course description approved by its scientific council. An alternative is to issue ECTS from an existing course. This is the option that UNIZA chose, i.e., issuing 3 ECTS from an existing course.

Since BIP course is funded by ERASMUS+, coordination was necessary among different departments within UNIZA and ISCTE; the research/organisation team and the department dealing with ERASMUS+ exchanges and funding issues.

Table 2 below provides a summary of the identified risks and constraints together with the likelihood and mitigation actions for each one of them.

Table 2 - Identified constraints, likelihood and mitigation actions.

#	Risk/Constraint	Likelihood	Mitigation
1	Attracting students to sign up to the course	High if limited period between the announcement of the course and its start	Strong, professional and wide marketing campaign (see section 7)
2	Ensure instructors come to the on-site week	Low - close collaboration with partners is already established	Ensure foreign partners commit to engaging and sending enough instructors to support the activities
3	Ensure non-academic staff to support the execution of the on-site BIP LbD pilot week	Low – partners engage their own resources (ISCTE case) and subcontract (UNIZA case) professionals to support the implementation of the on-site BIP LbD pilot week	UNIZA hires non-academic staff part time to address this constraint by subcontracting the organisation of the on-site event to a professional. ISCTE engages its own resources and acquires catering for the on-site week.
4	Retaining students to join all online modules and to actively participate in group assignments	Medium - drop-outs or ‘free-riders’ are unavoidable	Ensure high quality course delivery as per the 10 LbD principles (see Annex I). Ensure continuous communication with students to address any problems they might face. Reach out directly to those who miss too many modules or groups

			who fail to produce outputs. Provide timely attention and support.
5	Technical issues with online tools and equipment	Very high - common obstacle in online trainings	IT support personnel present throughout the course, group IT training and individual trials with instructors before the course, prepare breakout rooms and student groups in advance in Teams, provide info in the Q&A for students, remind students to install and use the desktop Teams app and reboot their device prior to joining the online module.
6	Ensuring ERASMUS+ funding is available at each sending institution	Medium – some institutions keep a buffer of funding available almost on demand, others require long lead times	Contact ERASMUS+ coordinators early with key partners to clarify and set aside budgets. Share experiences on enablers and barriers with WP5.
7	ERASMUS+ funding is insufficient to cover travel costs	Medium – the typical funding for students is 450 Euro, which is not enough when travelling from Lisbon to Slovakia for example	Clarify quickly with students the need to make and confirm their travel arrangements early at the start of the course. Explore alternative solutions to reduce or to cover some of the local costs indirectly e.g. using low-cost university housing, offering canteen lunches, free local transportation, etc.
8	Ensure students come for the on-site week - it is critical that a minimum of 15 foreign students is reached to apply for ERASMUS+ BIP funding	Medium – partner HEI can support this mobility	Ensure early, continuous and timely support to students when organising their travel plans (see section 7.1.4).

3. IMPLEMENTING LEARNING BY DEVELOPING IN A MULTIDISCIPLINARY INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT

With a few exceptions, the LbD type of pedagogical approach was perceived as a new concept and had not been applied at UNIZA before introducing the pilot plan. At ISCTE, similar type of pedagogies have been applied in some courses before and the novelty/benefit of the pilot was mostly related to the experiment of working in a multidisciplinary context. For LAUREA UNIZA and ISCTE, the interest lied also in seeing how LbD can be applied in different universities, different institutional and cultural contexts, and what could be learned from the local adaptations.

To begin with, several efforts were made to facilitate the process, i.e., to share knowledge about LbD as a pedagogical model and to get instructors and educational staff familiar with its principles. This included discussing the different pedagogical approaches, methods and practices already in use at UNIZA and ISCTE and how they differ from LbD. Also, the training materials provided in spring 2023 reported in the deliverable D6.1 (e.g., webinars and also other LbD guidance material presented in this chapter) were put in use. Additionally, check-ups were organised in the form of a continuous mentorship formed between the pilot teams and LAUREA, providing guidance for the pedagogical discussions as well as the actual LbD related pilot planning and implementation. The feedback, experiences and development/elaborations received therein are beneficial and will be used for developing the LbD training course – the objective of which is to enhance the InCITIES collaboration toward the end of the project and beyond the project lifespan.

Implementing Learning by Developing (LbD) in a multidisciplinary international context involves several steps to ensure that students from various disciplines and cultural backgrounds can effectively collaborate on real-life projects. A comprehensive approach to implementing LbD starts by forming diverse teams to work on real challenge projects with clear objectives and outcomes. Also, continuous assessment, regular feedback, and opportunities for reflection are essential throughout the process. The key to success lies in fostering a supportive learning environment and in encouraging community building that brings together students, staff and stakeholders to work on the real challenge assignments. Moreover, to be able to work in multidisciplinary international teams requires technological solutions, structured mentorship and many other forms of support to enable efficient collaboration. In this project, the experimentations started with the UNIZA pilot where the core activities bringing LbD to life can be summarised as follows (and described in detail in the following sections):

- Creation of LbD guidance material;
- Personality tests for an effective mix in groups;
- Process for group creation among diverse participants;
- Group interaction tools and activities;
- Feedback and assessment.

4.1 LbD Guidance material

LbD was introduced to UNIZA when the Institute of Life Long Learning at UNIZA, in close collaboration with LAUREA, produced two documents to help steer the implementation of LbD within the scope of the first pilot:

1. **LbD - ISR Six Pillars Framework Job Labs methodology** 13-12 final, in Annex II: this document complements more extensively the first introduction produced in deliverable D6.1 on the LbD Pedagogical model. It covers:
 - a. Background Philosophy of LbD and SECI Model
 - b. The Essential Features of LbD
 - c. LbD as a Problem-Solving and Dialogue-Based Model
 - d. Learning Environments and Dialogue in the Coaching of Teams
 - e. Guidance Challenge: Student's Competence vs. Guidance Resources
 - f. An Example of the General Overview of LbD Course
 - g. Seven Pillars of Futures Thinking
 - h. The ISR Themes
 - i. An example of LbD Using Future Foresight Strategy (Worskhop March 2023, Finland)
 - j. The Interrelations Between SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), IDGS (The Inner Development Goals), The Six (Seven) Pillars Approach and LbD
 - k. LbD and its Derivations: JOB LABS Methodology Based on the 5E Pedagogical Model (Taught in English for Specific Purposes at FEIT UNIZA)
2. **PRACTICAL GUIDE_InCITIES**, in Annex I: this document aims to serve as a guide for the actual implementation of the pilots and is distributed to all instructors as input before producing their module plans. The Guide takes a Q&A approach, answering the following:
 - Chapter 1: the inner development goals and soft skills
 - Chapter 2: 7 pillars and futures thinking
 - Chapter 3: guidance and roles

-
- Chapter 4: major key design rules
 - Chapter 5: course and real-life assignments (case studies) with authentic challenge
 - Chapter 6: 10 principles of the pilot course

The assessment of how the above-mentioned 10 principles were implemented in the pilots (to be seen in deliverable D6.3 - 2 roll-out pilots in the widening countries, June 2025) will be provided in the final evaluation and lessons learned (to be seen in deliverable D6.4 - Lessons learned and outlook, September 2025).

4.2 Planning and Implementation of LbD pedagogical model principles

Personality test

To maximise the probability that course participants groups operate in an optimum way, participants' personality characteristics are considered in the group creation process. Each selected course participant completes a Team role META test which aims to estimate the dominant personal characteristic of the participant and classify them into one of the following four categories:

- **Motivators** have the ability to equally value results and people. They are natural participative persons who work with and through people.
- **Energizers** are optimistic personalities who love imaginative and innovative things. They are fun-loving, highly sociable, and sometimes flamboyant.
- **Teamers** are good at collaborating and coordinating with others. They can adapt easily to changes in their environment and know how to create harmony if conflict arises.
- **Analysts** are known for their love of rationality. They make decisions with their head rather than their heart and are often the critical thinkers in a team.

The complete description of all personality types^{3,4} is provided in Annex III. The test statements and evaluation methodology is depicted in Figure 2 below. Course participants rank the statements in each line (A-F) of the META test in the order of their relevance to their personality by assigning each statement a score from 4 (the most relevant) to 1 (the least

³ Hemdan, J.T., Taha, D.S. & Cherif, I.A. (2023). Relationship between personality types and creativity: A study on novice architecture students. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 65, 847-857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2022.09.041>

⁴ Flavián, C., Guinalú, M. & Jordán, P. (2022). Virtual teams are here to stay: How personality traits, virtuality and leader gender impact trust in the leader and team commitment. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(2), 2444-8834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iiedeen.2021.100193>

relevant). Sum of scores in each of the four columns represents the total score for the respective personality type. The test is implemented as an online form in Microsoft Forms and every test line (A-F) is presented separately (see Figure 3). The objective of this way of test implementation is to minimise the risk of a potential conscious skew of the test results by making the connections between statements across the test lines less obvious.

Team role META TEST								
Rank the statements in each line by their relevance to you (4, 3, 2, 1 based on relevance)								
4 points – the most relevant				1 point – the least relevant				
The result (highlighted in row "O") is a sum of values in each highlighted column								
A	I enjoy initiative.		I enjoy coming up with new ideas.		I enjoy company of others.		I enjoy getting to the bottom of things.	
B	The overall goal is important.		New procedures are important.		Comfort is important.		Thorough work is important.	
C	I easily take over responsibility.		I easily come up with new things.		I easily make concessions.		I easily assess reality objectively.	
D	Sometimes I can come off as too passionate.		Sometimes I can come off as overly dissatisfied.		Sometimes I can come off as overly reserved.		Sometimes I can come off as overly confident.	
E	I do not like slacking.		I do not like tedious routine.		I hate conflicts.		I hate being under pressure.	
F	I take interest in progress.		I strive to have a diverse life.		I enjoy being in a good mood.		I strive for dutifulness.	
O	Motivator	0	Energy	0	Teamer	0	Analyst	0

	columns of scores characterizing the Motivator personality type
	columns of scores characterizing the Energizer personality type
	columns of scores characterizing the Teamer personality type
	columns of scores characterizing the Analyst personality type

Figure 2 - Team role META test statements and evaluation methodology.

Team role personality test

* Required

Please rank the statements from most preferred to least preferred. *

1st place - most preferred, 4th place - least preferred

- 1 I enjoy coming up with new ideas.
- 2 I enjoy initiative.
- 3 I enjoy getting to the bottom of the things.
- 4 I enjoy company of others.

Back Next

Page 2 of 7

Figure 3 - Illustrative screenshot of the Team role META test implementation.

Group creation process

Considering the group work assignments and participant interaction during the online Modules, as well as the capacity of resources in terms of available instructors per Module and tools, it is deemed appropriate to split participants into 4 Groups, having 8-9 participants per group. **The Groups remain the same throughout the duration of the course**, building up on the communication and team skills among group members while collaborating on different assignments.

Once all course participants complete the Team role META test, the dominant personal characteristic of each participant is revealed, enabling a categorisation of all participants across the 4 personality types: Motivators, Energisers, Teamers, and Analysts. Every participant has usually more than one personality type; in some cases, only one type is dominant, while in other cases the personality might be composed of multiple types. The aim of this test is to ensure participants are grouped in a balanced way, having at least one dominant personality type in each Group and at the same time a similar variety of personality types across Groups.

The Groups are created making sure gender and level of education of participants is distributed evenly across groups i.e. each group is gender balanced and has a similar share in PhD, Master and Bachelor students. This approach aims to ensure that students with different levels and disciplines, and from various countries and cultural background can work together efficiently.

Planned group interaction

Throughout the course, different interaction activities among course participants are foreseen.

- Slido tool is used, mostly during the online Modules, to engage participants with **live polls** and Q&As. Such a tool helps to create presence, and provides a good introduction to the course content. It breaks the ice in Introductory sessions and creates a sense of togetherness especially during online meetings when this is missing.
- During online Modules, all 4 Groups **brainstorm** on different topics and discuss course related questions suggested by instructors, using separate virtual rooms. The group work is performed using Microsoft Teams or Zoom rooms and Whiteboards for taking notes.
- Towards the end of each Module, a **home assignment** is presented to course participants, which is to be discussed and delivered in groups. Participants meet online to work on the different home assignments, and present their work at the beginning of each Module.
- All 4 Groups are also working closely during the on-site week. Different interaction activities are planned, including warm up games, collaborative work on the course content, and group presentation with proposals on the authentic real-life assignments.

Module feedback form

After each online module, students are asked to fill in a module feedback online form, which is designed with the following goals in mind:

- to evaluate the relevance, added value, complexity and clarity of the module content;
- to learn about the course participants' expectations of the module and the level of their fulfillment;
- to evaluate the level of participants' engagement and sufficiency of room for expressing themselves during the module;

- to collect feedback on instructors’ performance during the online module;
- to keep track on lessons learned to be applied in potential subsequent courses.

The module evaluation form is implemented in Google Forms separately for every module. The illustrative screenshot of Module 1 feedback form and a general form template containing all answers are presented in Figure 4 and Annex IV respectively.

MODULE 1 EVALUATION SHEET

Dear participant,

We kindly request your participation in this survey, comprising of 9 questions. Your feedback is significant for all individuals contributing to the development of the course. Your responses will remain confidential. We sincerely appreciate your valuable ideas and time.

Ak chcete uložiť svoj postup, [Prihlásiť sa do Googlu](#). [Ďalšie informácie](#)

InCITIES SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY INNOVATIONS

From climate anxiety to action

On completion of this course, you will walk away with:

- Practical skills and strategies applicable to real-life urban mobility challenges
- Analytical frameworks for critically thinking about mobility, inclusion, sustainability and resilience
- Tools and methods for planning and assessing urban mobility innovations
- Effective communication and teamwork skills together with experts, stakeholders, and peers
- An invaluable experience and professional network

A certificate of competence from the University of Žilina, a world leading transportation science university.

Course CURRICULUM

- 1. Sustainable mobility planning
- 2. Healthy planning & financing
- 3. Quality service delivery
- 4. Digital service delivery
- 5. The urban form & equity assessment
- 6. Transportation and economic sustainability
- 7. Design & innovation challenges
- 8. Digital transition to safe mobility
- 9. Partnership for the smart city

Case studies

- Starymova
- Cornet
- Georgiou
- Wuolam
- Koeb
- Stavros
- Kilonen-Oksa
- Ogata
- Stefan Diaz
- Tilko
- Lukova
- Petrov
- Hradsko
- Vestnicky
- Pikar
- Stavicka

Deadline for applying: 7.2.2024

www.incities.eu/course/

1. How do you evaluate the relevance of the content of this module against your expectations?

totally non-relevant

non-relevant

no opinion

partially relevant

totally relevant

2. What was the most important thing you learned during this module?

Vaša odpoveď

Figure 4 - Screenshot for Module 1 evaluation form.

4. PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING LbD CHALLENGES

Learning by Development suggests a general ‘ideal’ approach to identifying and selecting authentic real-life assignments involving and identifying potential partners, then finding an adequate challenge. Applied to the InCITIES project, this process consists of contacting the ecosystem institutions (in InCITIES pilots’ implementation these institutions are the project Associated Partners), and asking them to provide authentic real-life challenges related to ISR, which is the focus of the project and the pilots. More information about the theory and application of the LbD approach is presented in Deliverable 6.1.

In practice, for both organisations, the process followed was not linear but iterative. Both UNIZA and ISCTE are constantly running projects and initiatives with their local respective stakeholders (usually the city or organisations working for the city): the **first step** was therefore to contact them about already existing and known challenges, and asking whether they would be interested to ‘enroll’ a class of multidisciplinary, international students of different levels (bachelor, master and PhD) to take a fresh look at their projects and to propose solutions. For example, UNIZA was already involved in supporting the Office of the Chief Architect of Žilina (UHA) with analysing traffic data around two schools in one neighbourhood. As the initial solution proposed by the office had been rejected following a citizen consultation, they welcomed the opportunity to revisit the case.

The **second step** was to review the real-life assignment with the instructors that had offered to teach the online modules, and to confirm whether the material could be adapted to contribute to it. For the UNIZA example, this was partially the case: 6 out of 9 modules could contribute directly to solution design for the “safe and sustainable access to school” topic (e.g. traffic calming, cycling infrastructures, inclusivity), but the remaining modules needed to consider adding a second real-life assignment, which was done in the same way.

Once the two real-life assignments (aka case studies) with authentic challenges were settled and agreed with the stakeholder, the **third step** of designing the learning material was done in collaboration with instructors and local LbD experts.

ISCTE asked also the local inCITIES Associated Partners (APs) to provide challenges for the ISCTE pilot. Several challenges were provided by the APs in the beginning of 2024, that are related with valuing data of train and bicycle usage, transport data sensing and promotion of the inclusion of autistic persons and other neurodiversities. These real-life challenges will be used in the ISCTE pilot.

How this process was implemented is detailed in the next section, and the challenges that are confirmed at the time of writing of this deliverable are available in Annex V and Annex VI.

5. PROCESS OF CREATION OF THE LEARNING MATERIAL

The process of creation of the learning material is outlined in Figure 5 below and consists of 5 main steps with various feedback loops and connections among them. Before starting this process, different considerations are considered such as the different InCITIES 7 thematic areas and requirements of the Grant Agreement. Moreover, it is crucial to find and secure availability of instructors with appropriate skills and expertise who can deliver the expected outcomes.

Figure 5 - Steps for creation of learning material and feedback loops.

The process of identifying the relevant theoretical learning contents and learning activities stems from the authentic real-life challenges proposed by the ecosystem in a bottom-up approach. The content of the course is organised so that participants are able to solve these challenges. Within the InCITIES context the challenges are provided by the Associated Partners and pilots ecosystem members. The nature of challenges depends on the context and specific characteristics of the pilot local area.

The challenges are then decomposed into requirements and skills that students need to acquire to propose solutions for these challenges. Based on these requirements and skills, theoretical learning contents and main unit courses that need to be part of the course are identified in a bottom-up approach.

As the course participants are international, multidisciplinary, multi-level and partially online, it is important to have activities that enable the diverse and multidisciplinary student teams

to work smoothly together. Thus, to improve the soft skills, activities such as team building and breaking the ice activities need to be included in the course.

As a final step before the completion of the learning material, involved instructors are invited to develop and adjust the content of the courses based on the cases studies, the identified challenges, required skills and LbD principles. For both pilots, 1:1 meetings were organised with every instructor, to ensure content is appropriate, LbD principles are incorporated in the course flow, and teaching is planned with an engaging way so that clues are presented to students on how to look for information and knowledge emerges rather than “imposed” on students.

The learning material handed out to participants of the UNIZA pilot, as the outcome of this process, is presented in Annexes V and VI which include details on the real-life assignments (case studies) and in Annex XIV which outlines the preparatory material handed out to students before each one of the Modules.

6. PILOT PLAN WORKFLOW

This section describes the process of planning for both InCITIES pilots. First, a pilot plan workflow followed by ISCTE and UNIZA when planning the pilots is described. Following sections 7.1 and 7.2 outline the actions taken to address the identified institutional challenges and present plans for online and on-site course components at UNIZA and ISCTE respectively.

Figure 6 - Pilot plan workflow.

Figure 6 above presents the pilot plan workflow followed by both pilot institutions, which consists of five main dimensions.

1. First, an institutional framework has been created to set up the necessary institutional common ground in terms of course organization such as the definition of course schedule and format and to identify and follow the required institutional approval procedures, and micro-credentials definitions for accreditation.

2. Second, requirements and procedures related to the course students (course participants) have been defined.
3. Third component includes the processes related to the associated partners, contacts, the need to inform the methodological approach based on LbD, the partners commitment and engagement, and definition of authentic challenges.
4. Fourth dimension represents the definition and preparation of course materials and planning of course activities.
5. Finally, the fifth component addresses the issues related to the building of international and multidisciplinary team of course lectures for both pilots and coordination with associated partners.

Prior to the implementation of the steps presented above, discussions among partners and contributors to the pilots took place introducing LbD pedagogical model and training all staff members.

7. PILOT PLANS

In this section the pilot plans of UNIZA and ISCTE are presented, outlining general course characteristics, the marketing plan and the online and on-site course planning.

7.1 UNIZA PILOT PLAN

Based on deliverable D6.1, the UNIZA pilot is planned during the summer semester of the academic year 2023/2024. This section provides a summary of the course characteristics, marketing plan deployed to secure wide participation of domestic as well as foreign students and outlines the plan for the online and on-site course components.

As already described in section 3, several practical challenges and institutional constraints had to be addressed first before proceeding with the rollout of the pilots. In the case of UNIZA pilot, the following institutional challenges have been addressed prior to the course launch:

- **Issuing ECTS credits for course completion.** As the time plan of the UNIZA pilot rollout does not allow sufficient time in order to fully formalize a new course, after consultations with the UNIZA management, a decision has been taken to issue ECTS from an already existing course provided by the UNIZA's Faculty of Operation and Economics of Transport and Communications called "The transport planning and sustainable mobility". This has been identified as the course whose description matches the envisaged UNIZA pilot curricula the closest. The consent of the guarantor of the study program which this course belong to has been secured and the course instructor has been involved in the preparation of the UNIZA pilot course learning material from the start.
- **ERASMUS+ funding is insufficient to cover travel costs.** In collaboration with the Vice-rector for International Relations and Marketing, additional funding has been secured to cover course participants' accommodation expenses by providing them rooms in UNIZA dormitories free of charge. Refreshments and lunches will be provided to all participants throughout the on-site part and free shuttle bus from Vienna to UNIZA and back will be arranged to further reduce their travel costs.
- **Ensure enough instructors come to the on-site week.** At UNIZA, this challenge is addressed by involving instructors since the beginning of the pilot planning for the preparation and deployment of the course and their continuous engagement in the course program planning process. In the case of foreign instructors, UNIZA team and all InCITIES partners collaborate closely on defining the course content and identifying the right instructors for online and on-site modules at InCITIES partner institutions.

- **Keeping authentic challenge owner (city stakeholders and associate partners) engaged at an adequate level and satisfied with the outcome.** The course organizing team at UNIZA will closely and continually collaborate with the authentic challenge owners to ensure their needs are reflected in the authentic challenge descriptions. Furthermore, course instructors with expertise relevant to all aspects of the authentic challenges are selected to guide the course participants work. Finally, a review of the course participants' outputs by expert panel is planned at the end of the course, in order to provide recommendations and professional feedback on the proposed solutions.

7.1.1 General course characteristics

Main topic

- **Sustainable Mobility Transitions**, within the wider topic of **Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities**

This requires that all the material selected as part of the course is demonstrated to contribute directly to transition **goals, methods** and **solutions**.

Course type

- Based on principles of a Blended Intensive Programme (BIP)⁵
- Hybrid format: 9 online modules (2h each), followed by 5-day on-site participation.

Course organizers

- Coordinator, host, and main content provider: UNIZA
- Partner #1 LbD process support: LAUREA
- Partner #2 content provider: ISCTE
- Partner #3 content provider: Gustave Eiffel

Pedagogical format

- Based on LbD approach: case-based, engaging, active, bottom-up, workshop style, with stakeholder involvement where/when possible (see D6.1 chapter 3 for a description and section 2.3 for implementation details)

⁵ BIP Requirements are 1) online participation (from 1 hour to 1 semester) 2) on-site participation at the host institution (from 5 to 30 days) 3) the course is worth of at least 3 ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) credits, either under the name of the BIP course or as one of the courses from the student's study plan 4) the course must be organised as a cooperation between at least 3 partner universities (1 coordinator + 2 other partners).

Authentic real-life assignments

- The first real-life assignment takes place in the neighbourhood of Vlčince, Žilina, spanning the two schools of Gorazda and Martinská. The stakeholder and real-life assignment owner is the Office of the Chief Architect of Zilina (UHA). See Annex V for a complete real-life assignment description which is shared with students.
- The second real-life assignment takes place in the centre pedestrian zone of Zilina. The stakeholder and real-life assignment owner is the City of Zilina. See Annex VI for a complete real-life assignment description which is shared with students.

Timing

- The summer school follows UNIZA “summer” semester schedule from February to May 2024
- Duration: 12 weeks, consisting of 9x2h online modules (changed from 10 in D6.1), and 1 week on-site (20h)
- Online preparatory courses: starting week 8 (week of February 19th), aligned with the official start of the summer semester.
- Final on-site course is held on week 16 (week of April 19th), finishing earlier than the end of the semester to allow students to participate before the exam period, and to avoid weeks with bank holidays (week 18&19).

Participants

- Target of a minimum of 15 master and/or PhD students to qualify for Erasmus+ minimum requirements. Internal target of minimum 20 maximum 30 students, to allow for the creation of four study groups.

Workload and accreditation

- 3 ECTS i.e. the equivalent of 75-90 working hours, including reading, attending online and on-site course, related visits, and preparing contributions. The breakdown is
 - Online participation: 9x2h = 18h
 - Preparatory reading: 9x1h = 9h
 - Weekly group assignments preparation for the online course: 8 x 1.5h = 12h
 - on-site participation: 5x6h = 30h
 - on-site activities (e.g. traffic counting) and visits: 3x2h = 6h
 - Current total: 75h
- Course organisers issue a certificate of completion (see Annex VII) if all conditions for passing each module are approved. Attendance is monitored automatically by Teams and recorded in the students list.

-
- The equivalent course for issuing formal ECTS credits from the existing course base at UNIZA is Transport Planning and Sustainable Mobility⁶. The guarantor of the course is Marián Gogola from the Faculty of Operation and Economics of Transport and Communications

Tools

To facilitate the online part of the course, UNIZA uses tools available through its Microsoft 365 cloud productivity suite license. Digital infrastructure necessary to host the online course activities are set up with the collaboration of UNIZA Centre for Information and Communication Technologies (CIKT) in such a way that only free versions of the respective software is required to access the course materials. In particular, the following tools from the Microsoft 365 suite are used:

- **Teams** – to host and access the online course modules and manage breakout rooms for individual student groups during the online modules;
- **SharePoint** – to provide cloud storage and access to the online course materials in a shared folder, accessible to all the registered course participants and instructors;
- **Whiteboard** – to facilitate online group collaboration activities, such as ideation and brainstorming during and after the online modules.

To host the online modules, a recurring **Teams meeting** is preconfigured and scheduled. To improve the accessibility of the online modules, all of them are accessible through the same shortened Uniform Resource Locator (URL) <https://bit.ly/incities-course-2024>.

Course participants are able to access course preparatory materials uploaded by the course instructors prior to every online module through the **online shared folder** “InCITIES_Students”. Also in this case, a shortened URL (<https://bit.ly/incities-shared-folder>) is prepared to improve user comfort.

Whiteboards for online collaboration activities are prepared in advance for each of the four groups of course participants. A whiteboard is activated by sharing it on the screen during the Teams online meeting and all of the meeting participants assigned to the respective group are automatically assigned editing rights for their group’s whiteboard for the remainder of the course. The data entered into the group whiteboards is stored throughout all the online modules and remains accessible even after the Teams meeting is terminated. This allows the students to refer back to and/or continue in their previous work at any time.

⁶ <https://vzdelavanie.uniza.sk/vzdelavanie/planinfo.php?kod=317337&lng=en>

Additional short-term engagement activities, such as quick opinion polls and real-time voting are facilitated throughout the course using **Slido**. Course participants can use a link or a specific code to access the Slido polls using any of their online devices.

In order to facilitate efficient communication between course participants, instructors and the core organizing team, three **email lists** are created:

- **circular.incities@uniza.sk** containing email addresses of the UNIZA core organizing team. This list is used to share all internal organizational and operational information concerning the course such as course planning, enquiries of course participants, etc.
- **instructors.incities@uniza.sk** containing email addresses of all participating course instructors across InCITIES consortium. This list is used to share internal course information relevant to instructors and serves as a contact point for course participants for contacting all instructors.
- **students.incities@uniza.sk** containing email addresses of all course participants. This list is created to streamline communication with enrolled course participants for the course organizers and instructors, as well as to facilitate easy communication between the course participants.

In addition to the email lists, a **contacts list** is prepared and made available to the instructors and course participants on the course shared folder. The list contains the names and email addresses of all course instructors and enrolled participants and serves both instructors and course participants to easily contact individuals for course related matters.

7.1.2 Marketing plan

The marketing campaign aims to promote the course and recruit students starting on week 48 (27th of November 2023).

The course promotion consists of

Attracting UNIZA master and PhD students

- **Printed posters** are presented in areas with high presence of students, i.e., near UNIZA building entrances, on each UNIZA faculty's bulletin boards, at designated rest zones for students.
- **UNIZA and UNIZA faculties'** social media channels post the course information.
- **UNIZA scientific secretaries**, i.e., first points of contact at each UNIZA unit responsible for distributing the received information within their respective unit distribute the course information through their units' respective communication and dissemination channels.

- **Digital board** advertising in the café at the rectorate building. See Annex VIII for a snapshot.
- **UNIZA Instructors** in InCITIES project present the course to their students, they are asked to issue additional points towards the successful completion of their own courses.
- **Vice Dean of Education** for each faculty is asked to establish contact and offer the summer schools to all students.
- **UNIZA ERASMUS coordinators** distribute the course information to all visiting students.
- **Internal UNIZA mailing lists** is used to distribute the course information to relevant target audience, e.g. to scientific secretaries, employees, students.
- **Newspaper article** in the form of an interview, providing basic information about the InCITIES project and the course is published in the special issue of Slovak nationwide daily newspaper “Pravda” on 30 January 2024. This issue is dedicated to providing information about Slovak higher education institutions. The scanned article (in Slovak) is provided in Annex IX.

Attracting foreign students (minimum 15 from EU institutions)

- Course marketing materials is shared with all InCITIES partners who spread the information to their students using available communication and dissemination channels.
- Relevant contacts and organisations (e.g. PIONEER Alliance members⁷, ECTRI, EIT Urban Mobility etc.) are reached to disseminate the course content to further networks.

Proposed marketing text

The text in Table 3 below is to be used across the various marketing instruments. The full text is also used on the InCITIES website. The marketing design contractor can choose to use the whole text or its parts in other mediums.

Table 3 - UNIZA pilot marketing text.

<European Commission logo>	<InCITIES logo>
University of Žilina SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY INNOVATIONS Blended Intensive Programme Course	

⁷ All InCITIES beneficiaries are members of the PIONEER alliance network of European Universities.

<p>19 February - 26 April 2024</p> <p>InCITIES</p> <p>Trailblazing Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities</p>				
3 ECTS	9 weekly online modules (2h)	1 week on-site seminar in April	2 Authentic real-life assignments	Learning-by-Developing (LbD) approach
<p>On completion of this course, you will walk away with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Practical skills and strategies applicable to real-life urban mobility challenges – Analytical frameworks for critically thinking about mobility, inclusion, sustainability and resilience – Tools and methods for planning and assessing urban mobility innovations – Effective communication and teamwork skills together with experts, stakeholders, and peers – An invaluable experience and professional connections – A certificate of competence from the University of Žilina, a world-leading transportation science university 				
From climate anxiety to action				
<p>Course curriculum</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainable mobility principles 2. Mobility planning & modelling 3. Traffic calming in cities 4. Cycling and active mobility 5. Air pollution and air quality measurement 6. Understanding and assessing vulnerability 7. Transport as critical infrastructures 8. Digital transition for safe mobility 9. Cybersecurity in the smart city <p>The course ends with one week on-site seminar. Expect site visits and keynotes from local government, civil society, industry, and academia.</p>		<p>Real-life assignments</p> <p>You will contribute to real planning needs for the city of Žilina.</p> <p>“Safe and sustainable access to schools” <picture illustrating the real-life assignment></p> <p>“Intelligent transport solutions for safe and efficient mobility” <picture illustrating the real-life assignment></p>		
Dana Sitányiová		Yannick Cornet		Christina Georgouli

Construction management & environmental protection	Sustainable mobility, worthwhile travel time	Sustainable urban mobility & indicator frameworks
Tiina Wikström Planetary wellness, social and cultural sustainability <LAUREA logo>	Matúš Kováč Road design & diagnostics	Pedro Sebastião Technological innovation and entrepreneurship <ISCTE logo>
Sanna Ketonen-Oksi Transformative futures, foresight methods <LAUREA logo>	Marián Gogola Urban transport planning & active travel	Miguel Sales Dias AI, data science and design thinking <ISCTE logo>
Michal Titko Disaster preparedness & resilience assessment	Mária Lusková Critical infrastructure & urban resilience	Tibor Petrov ITS & CAV communication technologies
Peter Holečko Information systems, IoT & cyber security	Peter Vestenický ITS & communication networks	Marek Drličiak Road design & urban transport planning
Dušan Jandačka Environmental engineering & transport air pollution		
Deadline for applying: 7 February 2024 www.incities.eu/course/		<QR code containing registration link: https://www.incities.eu/course/ >
<InCITIES partner logos>		
https://incities.eu/	1 October 2022 - 30 September 2025	Grant agreement ID - 101071330
Funded under the Horizon Europe Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence Program		

Course marketing materials and visual identity

Marketing materials used for the course promotion include a digital course flyer, printed posters and a digital board slide. To maintain a unified visual identity of all the course-related marketing materials, they share the same design as presented in Figure 7.

Subcontractor Michales Media, s.r.o. was selected by a public procurement to follow the national legislation and is in charge of creating the marketing materials using the Summer School hosting budget.

The digital version of the course flyer is published on the InCITIES website and shared through social media and email together with the course description and call to action for the intended target audience. Twenty-two printed posters of A3 size are distributed throughout the UNIZA premises and displayed prominently near building entrances and at every faculty's bulletin boards (see Figure 8).

The figure displays three versions of the course marketing materials: a flyer, a poster, and a digital board slide. All three share a consistent green and white color scheme and layout.

Course Flyer (Left): Features the InCITIES logo, a photo of a green building, and the text: "SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY INNOVATIONS Blended Intensive Programme Course 19 February - 26 April 2024". It lists benefits: 3 ECTS, 9 weekly online modules, 1 week on-site seminar in April, 2 authentic urban challenges, and Learning by Developing approach. Logos of partner institutions and the EC logo are at the bottom.

Poster (Middle): Titled "From climate anxiety to action". It lists learning outcomes:

- Practical skills and strategies applicable to real-life urban mobility challenges
- Analytical frameworks for critically thinking about mobility, inclusion, sustainability and resilience
- Tools and methods for planning and assessing urban mobility innovations
- Effective communication and teamwork skills together with experts, stakeholders, and peers
- An invaluable experience and professional connections
- A certificate of competence from the University of Žilina, a world-leading transportation science university

Digital Board Slide (Right): Titled "Course details". It includes:

- Course curriculum:** 1 Sustainable mobility principles, 2 Mobility planning & modelling, 3 Traffic calming in cities, 4 Cycling and active mobility, 5 Air pollution and air quality measurement, 6 Understanding and assessing vulnerability, 7 Transport as critical infrastructures, 8 Digital transition for safe mobility, 9 Cybersecurity in the smart city.
- Case studies:** "Safe and sustainable access to schools", "Intelligent transport solutions for safe and efficient mobility".
- Instructors:** Daga Sitányiová, Yannick Cornet, Christina Georgioulis, Tine Wikström, Mihail Kováč, Pedro Sebastião, Sanna Ketonen-Oksi, Martin Gogola, Miguel Sales Dias, Michal Titko, Mária Lusková, Tibor Petrov, Peter Holečko, Peter Vesterický, Marek Drličiak, Dušan Jandačka.
- Deadline for applying: 7.2.2024**
- Website:** www.incities.eu/course/

Figure 7 - Common design of the course marketing materials (course flyer, poster and digital board slide).

In addition to the course marketing materials, the subcontractor provides also a digital version of **MS Teams background** (see Figure 9) and a **PowerPoint template** (see Figure 10) to be used by course participants and instructors throughout the course online modules. The purpose is to ensure a unified and professional look to the course offering.

The design of the MS Teams background follows the project visual identity and contains image of a green building purchased for the project website and social media use, InCITIES logo, logos of project partners and the European Commission (EC) as well as the InCITIES website URL.

Figure 8 - An example of course poster placement at UNIZA premises.

Figure 9 - MS Teams background designed for use throughout the course online modules.

Figure 10 - Course PowerPoint presentation template.

The course PowerPoint template design is based on the InCITIES visual identity and displays, from left to right, the InCITIES logo, course motto and the EC logo prominently on the top of the title slide. The centre part of the title slide contains Module title and subtitle, names of the module instructors and the current date. Bottom of the title slide contains a list of key course features, InCITIES partners' logos and the project website URL. Following slides contain InCITIES and EC logos on the top and slide number, InCITIES partners' logos and the current date on the bottom, all on a plain white background to minimize visual distraction of the course participants.

Signing up process

Students interested in the course are able to sign up for the course using the registration prepared on the InCITIES website (<https://incities.eu/course>). To improve accessibility, the registration page URL is encoded in a QR code present in all the course marketing materials.

Application deadline is set to February 7th, 2024, i.e., two weeks before the first online module.

After the registration deadline, an email containing basic information about the course is sent to every registered participant. The purpose of this email is twofold:

1. to provide basic information about the course schedule, conditions for successfully completing the course, covering of travel expenses, and the schedule for notifying the selected course participants;

2. to make sure the potential participants understand the requirements for successful course completion, especially **the requirement to attend both online and on-site parts**, and to confirm their continued interest in joining the course on those terms.

The full text of this email is presented in Annex X.

Two days after the course registration deadline, i.e., on February 9th, 2024, an invitation to join the course is sent to the selected course participants via email. In the invitation, the course schedule is reiterated. Furthermore, the email contains the following information:

- Information about the online tools that will be used during the course together with a link to a guide on how to download and install them;
- Request for a consent to record the course introductory session
- Link to the course shared folder
- Link to the personality META test (see section 4.2 for more details) and a request to complete the test with a deadline
- Contact information for technical support in the case of experiencing difficulties associated with the course online tools

The invitation email template is presented in Annex XI.

Student selection process

Once all emails are received by potential course participants confirming their attendance, the final list of potential students is created and reviewed. Those who registered for the course but were not responsive to the emails, are excluded from the final selection process. The selection criteria for choosing the final list of course participants are (in order of priority):

1. Students from InCITIES partners' institutions
2. Students from PIONEER Alliance institutions
3. MSc. and PhD. students
4. Bachelor students from PIONEER Alliance institutions.
5. Other applicants.

Given the fact that the course is being developed within InCITIES project, **priority is given to InCITIES partner universities**. The long-term collaboration with PIONEER Alliance institutions and the aim of the InCITIES project to formalise this sustainably, adds importance to the

second criterion. At the same time, attention is paid to the **level of education** of participants, to maintain a good level for the course content and secure diverse skills. The final list of course participants, is also reviewed to make sure it is **gender balanced**.

The preferable amount of total course participants, considering the BIP requirements, and course operational capacity is set to **approximately 30 students**. However, the maximum number of course participants to be accepted is set at 35, to account for any drop-outs or last-minute cancellations.

Website communication

Registration form

A registration form to sign in for the course has been prepared and published at the InCITIES website (<https://incities.eu/course>). The form was designed to collect basic information about the registrants, their motivation to join the course and their educational background. The screenshot of the complete registration form as available on the InCITIES website is presented in Figure 11 below, and the type of data collected by the course registration form is detailed in Annex XII.

Home - Sustainable Mobility Innovations Course

Sustainable Mobility Innovations Course

[Course description](#) | [FAQ](#)

Sustainable Mobility Innovations

Blended Intensive Programme Course

Your Name *

E-mail *

Motivation *

Describe shortly why you would like to attend the course and what you hope to gain by attending it.

Short bio *

Introduce yourself briefly to the course instructors and your fellow students.

Field of study

Study degree

- Bachelor's
 - Master's
 - PhD.
 - Other
- Which degree are you currently pursuing?

University/Institution

Job title

Special dietary requirements

Gender *

- Male
- Female
- Other
- I don't want to disclose

Nationality *

I agree *

- By submitting this form, I agree to my details being used for the purposes of organizing the Sustainable Mobility Innovations course. The information will only be accessed by the organisers. I understand my data will be held securely and will not be distributed to third parties. I have a right to change or access my information. My data will be kept for a maximum period of 12 months after the end of the course.

Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 applies to the processing of your personal data collected for the organisation and management of the Sustainable Mobility Innovations course. The processing of certain categories of your personal data as described in this privacy statement will be carried out based on your consent (Article 5(d) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725).

The following personal data will be processed: 1. information necessary for your registration: title, first name, last name, country, e-mail, phone number, name of organisation 2. information necessary for access to the conference venue: ID card / passport number. Your consent is required for: 1. photos, audio and video recordings and web streaming related to the course 2. attendee list containing your name and affiliation, which will be shared among participants 3. receiving the InCITIES Newsletter and press releases.

Figure 11 - Screenshot of the course registration form on the InCITIES website.

Course description (flyer)

The information about the course is provided also on the InCITIES website in the Events page (<https://incities.eu/event/sustainable-mobility-innovations-course/>). The page contains elements of the course flyer cropped for better readability, textual description of the course, contact information and links to the registration page and Questions and Answers (Q&A) page. Figure 12 presents the screenshot of the part of the course description web page.

The screenshot shows the InCITIES website's FAQ section. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Home, About, Advisory Board, Partners, Project Outcomes, News, Upcoming Events, Newsletter, Useful Links, and Contacts. The main content area features a 'FAQ' heading with a question mark icon. Below the heading, a paragraph states: 'The University of Žilina (UNIZA) in collaboration with the InCITIES project partners are organizing the Sustainable Mobility Innovations course. The course is taking place between the 19th of February and the 26th of April 2024 with 9 weekly online modules and 1 week of on-site seminars. Upon completion of this course, you will walk away with:'

- Practical skills and strategies applicable to real-life urban mobility challenges
- Analytical frameworks for critically thinking about mobility, inclusion, sustainability and resilience
- Tools and methods for planning and assessing urban mobility innovations
- Effective communication and teamwork skills among experts, stakeholders, and peers
- An invaluable experience and professional connections
- Working life skills with the Learning by Developing pedagogical model
- A certificate of competence from the University of Žilina, a world-leading transportation science university, equivalent to 3 ECTS

To the right, there is a list of events:

- 26. February 2024: InCITIES Kick-Off Meeting (Online) - 8. October 2022
- 13. October 2022: Presentation Of InCITIES At The PORTUGAL SMART CITIES SUMMIT 2022
- 16. November 2022: Invited Session At TRA 2022 Conference
- 19. November 2022: Blended (Physical & Online) Project Meeting At ISCTE

At the bottom, there is a 'Course curriculum' section listing 9 topics: 1 Sustainable mobility principles, 2 Mobility planning & modelling, 3 Traffic calming in cities, 4 Cycling and active mobility, 5 Air pollution and air quality measurement, 6 Understanding and assessing vulnerability, 7 Transport as critical infrastructures, 8 Digital transition for safe mobility, 9 Cybersecurity in the smart city. It also mentions 'The course ends with one week on-site seminar. Expect site visits and keynotes from local government, civil society, industry'. A 'Case studies' section highlights 'Safe and sustainable access to schools' and 'Intelligent transport solutions for safe and efficient mobility'.

Figure 12 - Screenshot of the course description web page.

Questions and Answers (Q&A)

The course web page includes a section with Q&A about the course, accessible at URL: <https://incities.eu/faq/>. The questions are divided into two categories: general Q&A and course content Q&A. The general Q&A section provides practical information about the course including the schedule, online tools necessary to join the course, requirements for

successful course completion, travel and contact information. The course content Q&A addresses specific questions related to the course content and methodology received from the registered course participants. The Q&A section of the website is being updated throughout the course. The screenshot of the Q&A web page is provided in Figure 13. The full list of Q&A updated until March 13th, 2024 is presented in Annex XIII.

Figure 13 - Screenshot of the course Questions & Answers webpage.

7.1.3 Online course planning

Before the course

A number of different tasks are planned before starting the course and prior to each module.

A few weeks before the start of the course, one-to-one meetings are organised with all module instructors to discuss the content of each module, the structure and timing, delivery methods, and the **integration of the LbD approach** including group interaction activities. For

this purpose, a **module template** (Annex XIV) is created and shared with instructors in advance, to adopt a common approach, making sure all necessary elements are considered in each module. In addition, a presentation template is provided to all instructors, based on which the lectures are prepared.

One week ahead of the start of the course (Week 7), two **Introductory sessions** are held, lasting 1hr each (Annex XIV). During these sessions, course participants are welcomed and introduced to the course, presenting information regarding the thematic areas to be covered, the context and aim of the course, its structure and schedule, as well as the real real-life assignments to be studied. Using Slido, course participants are asked to indicate how they feel about the course. A get-to-know each other session is held in virtual breakout rooms, **where students share their background and expectations** for the course. Moreover, the personality test results are presented and information regarding logistics, tools, and course requirements are discussed, allowing room and time for questions.

One week before each module, the reading material is uploaded at the online shared folder “InCITIES_Students” so that course participants can prepare for the upcoming module. The recording file of the previous module and all lecture slides are also uploaded, so that those who miss the module can keep up with the course pace. The evaluation form for each module is also prepared. This information is communicated by email with students every week, together with a reminder regarding the home assignment for next module or any other pending issues.

At the same time, one week before each module, module instructors are contacted again to make sure the content of the module is completed, and finalise any pending items on the structure and/or course delivery methods.

One day before each module, course participants are contacted with information regarding the thematic topics of the upcoming module and the instructors to be present. Participants are also reminded about providing their feedback on the previous module, and the home assignments. Technicalities are also presented in the same email, including timing and link to the module.

During the implementation of the course, any issues raised by course participants or any lessons learned during the delivery of modules are addressed and discussed with instructors.

During the course

The online course modules take place over a period of 9 weeks starting from Week 8 (Table 4). In practice, each 2h course is covered by two instructors, with the first hour focused on students’ presentations, followed by a discussion hosted by the instructor from the previous

week's module, and the second hour hosted by the instructor for this week's module. The following Table shows the lead instructor(s) for each module and the different thematic areas covered.

Table 4 - Online course overview, 9 modules.

Module	Week (2024)	Online session (2h)	Lead Instructor(s) + Partner Instructor
#1	8	Sustainable mobility principles	Yannick Cornet, Dana Sitányova, Christina Georgouli & Sanna Ketonen-Oksi (LAUREA)
#2	9	Mobility planning & modelling	Marek Dričiak
#3	10	Traffic calming in cities	Matúš Kováč
#4	11	Cycling and active mobility	Marian Gogola
#5	12	Air pollution and air quality measurement	Dusan Jandacka, Aurélie Charron (Gustave Eiffel)
#6	13	Understanding and assessing vulnerability	Michal Titko
#7	14	Transport as critical infrastructures	Maria Luskova
#8	15	Digital transition for safe mobility	Tibor Petrov
#9	16	Cybersecurity in the smart city	Peter Vestenický, Peter Holečko

Each module consists of homework presentation by students, lectures by instructors and different student interaction activities. The modules are logically organised so that the content and real-life assignment homework flow from one course to the next. Each module has a real-life assignment homework due for presentation in the following week, which is linked to the challenges and real planning needs of the two real-life assignments of the course. Home assignments are discussed and presented by each one of the 4 groups.

Modules are organised starting at 3 pm CET sharp, on Wednesdays. A typical module breakdown is shown in Table 5 below while the detailed content for each Module is provided in Annex XIV.

Table 5 - Typical module breakdown.

Time	Description
14:50 – 15:00	Online session opens and attendees are accepted into the online room
15:00 – 15:05	Introduction to the module
15:05 – 15:30	Student(s) presentation(s) of the real-life assignment homework from the previous week & discussion
15:30 – 15:55	Lecture and warm-up exercise (small survey or simple question asked in small groups)
15:55 – 16:00	Break
16:00 – 16:20	Lecture - Presentation of new material in an interactive way
16:20 – 16:50	Group discussion in break out rooms on the material and discussion with students
16:50 – 16:55	Next real-life assignment homework presentation
16:55 – 17:00	Closure and questions

Each module is recorded in order to go back for clarifications and/or allow participants to watch it retrospectively in case they miss a session. Moreover, the recorded material is used for improving the content and quality of the course, and might be also shared or used for educational purposes in the future. For these purposes, and to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation and ethical standards, a **Participant Information Sheet** together with an **Informed Consent Form** was prepared (Annex XV). Course participants, both students and instructors, are asked to complete, sign and return the form. At the same time, permission to start the recording is asked at the beginning of each module.

7.1.4 On-site course planning

Accommodation and travel plans

To accommodate the course participants travelling from abroad, the course organising team pre-books 10 rooms, with a capacity of 2 persons in each room, at the UNIZA student dormitory for the week of the on-site course. This pre-booking is done even before the registration to the course opens, in order to make sure, enough rooms are available.

Once the final list of course participants is finalised, the course organisers approach each participant to confirm the details of their travel for the on-site course. Participants are asked

to report if they require accommodation at UNIZA dormitories for the duration of the on-site course, the date of their planned arrival to and departure from Zilina, their preferred roommate and the dates, times and airport of their arrival and departure in case they are travelling by plane. The full text of the email used to collect this information is presented in Annex XVI. **The UNIZA organising team closely collaborates with ERASMUS+ coordinators and partners from remaining InCITIES institutions throughout this period to ensure that all potential barriers to their respective participants' visit to Zilina are resolved in time.**

When all information is collected, UNIZA organising team compiles an internal document with course participants accommodation and travel plans, which is used to:

- make final room bookings at UNIZA dormitories and assign participants to rooms according to their stated preference
- to schedule and organise a shuttle bus from Vienna airport to Zilina and back on dates and times suitable to most travelling participants

Based on the course participants' travel plans, the airport shuttle bus is scheduled as follows:

- Sunday 21st of April, departure at 6:00 pm CET from Vienna airport with a stop at Bratislava airport at 7:30 pm CET
- Saturday 27th of April, departure at 4 am CET from Zilina to Vienna airport

Both the accommodation at the UNIZA dormitory and the airport shuttle bus are provided to the course participants free of charge. Course instructors can use the shuttle bus free of charge and accommodation at UNIZA dormitory guest rooms for the price between 24 and 50 EUR per night, depending on the size and the equipment of the room they select.

[on-site week detailed planning](#)

The on-site week is planned as shown in Table 6 below, to include a variety of group activities, keynote speeches and presentations, visits to relevant sites and adequate breaks for rest and meals or refreshments. The planning is hourly, to ensure all activities are performed timely. Each day a location is booked, depending on the requirements of different activities and the suitability for group work and screen presentations. Meals are organised by each hosting facility, adjusted to accommodate less flexible activities.

For every group activity, all necessary material (flipcharts, post-its, markers etc.) is made available. Course participants have the opportunity to visit the location of both course use cases (Gorazda and Martinska schools, Martincka school, pedestrian area near Marianske square), a public transport operator and a car manufacturing site. Transportation to site visits when necessary is also organised.

Signatures of participants will be collected at the start of each day.

Table 6 - On-site week schedule.

CET time	Monday 22 nd April	Tuesday 23 rd April	Wednesday 24 th April	Thursday 25 nd April	Friday 26 th April
7:00-08:45	---	Traffic counts & Air quality measurements.	---	---	Car free day: Walking bus, air quality measurements & group activities (Location: Gorazda and Martinska schools)
08:45-9:00	Refreshments	Site visit to real-life assignment 1: the school area (Location: Gorazda and Martinska schools)	Refreshments	Refreshments	
9:00-09:30	Welcome speech by rector (Location: UNIZA)	Miroslava Valaskova (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Karol Haas (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Pedro Sebastião, ISCTE (Location: UNIZA)	Groupwork: Finalisation of proposals (Location: UNIZA)
09:30-10:00	Introduction: warm-up games, getting to know each other, expectations for the week (Location: UNIZA)	Lesson + Groupwork (vision exercise) (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Lesson + Groupwork (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Lesson + Groupwork ALL together (Location: UNIZA)	
10:15-10:30		Refreshments			
10:30-10:45		Lesson + Groupwork (Location: UNIZA)			
10:45-11:00	Refreshments	Refreshments	Refreshments	Lesson + Groupwork (Location: UNIZA) + DPMZ visit	Refreshments
11:00-12:00	Lesson + Groupwork (Location: UNIZA)	Lesson + Groupwork (vision exercise) (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Lesson + Groupwork (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Group 1 (10:30-12:30) max ~34 students + 2 lecturers	Feedback, Evaluation forms, wrap-up, Certificates (Location: UNIZA)
12:00-12:30				Lunch break (Location: UNIZA)	Lunch break (Location: UNIZA)
12:30-13:00	Lunch break (Location: UNIZA)	Lunch break (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Lunch break (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)		
13:00-13:30				Lesson + Groupwork	Group presentations

13:30-14:00	Daniela - Union of Slovak Towns and Cities (Location: UNIZA)	Lesson + Groupwork (vision exercise) (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	Lesson + Groupwork (Location: Stanica Žilina-Záriečie)	(Location: UNIZA) + KIA visit Group 2 (12:30-15:30) presentation on KIA plant, excursion, and final presentation and discussion on sustainable mobility (e.g. drones used for delivery in cities) max 25 students and 2 lecturers	(Location: Gorazda and Martinska schools)
14:00-14:30	Lesson + Groupwork (Location: UNIZA)				
14:30-15:00	---	---	---		---
15:00-15:30	---	---	---	---	---
17:00-18:30	Guided tour & site visit to real-life assignment 2: pedestrian area (Location: Marianske square)	---	---	---	---
19:00-21:00	---	---	Dinner/picnic (voluntary)	---	---

Key

Group activity
Visit
Keynote speech/presentation
Break / Meal & Refreshments

7.2 ISCTE PILOT PLAN

Based on deliverable D6.1, the ISCTE pilot is planned during the winter semester of the academic year 2024/2025. This section provides a summary of the course characteristics, marketing plan deployed to secure wide participation of domestic as well as international students and outlines the plan for the online and on-site course components.

Several practical challenges and institutional constraints had to be addressed before proceeding with the rollout of the pilots and their respective implementation of the LbD pedagogical model. In the case of ISCTE pilot, the following challenges have been addressed prior to the course launch:

- The need to fully understand the reach of the LbD pedagogical model;
- To set the organisational conditions for properly implement the LbD pedagogical model;
- To articulate the recognised quality of the teaching and the current relations with society that ISCTE have acquired, with the new demands that LbD model requires.

Issuing ECTS credits for course completion. ISCTE has decided to formalise a new internal unit course description for its school pilot, which as to be approved by the ISCTE scientific council.

7.2.1. General course characteristics

Main topic

- **Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges**, within the wider topic of **Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities**.

ISCTE will focus on Interdisciplinary Challenges related to **Cities Futures** and their embracing with the thematic areas identified in WP2, towards developing future consciousness and agency for building the future. Concrete and authentic real-life challenges proposed by the InCITIES Associated Partners, in a bottom-up strategy implementation, are the building-block of the ISCTE Pilot Plan, through putting in practice the LbD pedagogical model.

The school pilot/BIP organized by ISCTE, which is open to all InCITIES partners and PIONEER network, aims to develop an innovative perspective for the future of cities, based on the principles and pedagogical practices of LbD, involving from the outset the Associated Partners of the project directly linked to the Lisbon Metropolitan Area.

There are multiple challenges that the Lisbon Metropolitan Area faces, similar to other international cities, and with which it can benefit from the development of this project and in particular from the realization of this pilot on **Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges**.

The disciplinary areas that ISCTE offer to **Future Cities - Interdisciplinary Challenges** school pilot/BIP are the following ones: social sciences, informatics, data science, information systems, public policies, architecture and urban studies, business and marketing. These interdisciplinary approach aims to give participants the knowledge for addressing challenges delineated by the Associated partners. Notably, participants will engage in collaborative teamwork exercises, culminating in presentations to be delivered during the on-site component of the program hosted in Lisbon.

ISCTE will also promote a Hackathon during the Lisbon' BIP/school pilot to help engage the learners, that will have the following title: **Future Cities From Vivid Reality: Inclusive and Sustainable and Challenges in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area**.

Course type

- Based on the principles of a Blended Intensive Programme (BIP)⁸
- Hybrid format: 10 online modules (2h each), followed by 5-day on-site participation.

Course organizers

- Coordinator, host, and content provider: ISCTE
- Partner #1 LbD process support and content provider: LAUREA
- Partner #2 content provider: UNIZA

Pedagogical format

- Based on LbD approach: challenge-based, engaging, active, bottom-up, workshop style, with the Associated Partners and other stakeholder involvement where/when possible (see D6.1 chapter 3 for a description and section 2.3 for implementation details).

⁸ BIP Requirements are 1) online participation (from 1 hour to 1 semester) 2) on-site participation at the host institution (from 5 to 30 days) 3) the course is worth of at least 3 ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) credits, either under the name of the BIP course or as one of the courses from the student's study plan 4) the course must be organised as a cooperation between at least 3 partner universities (1 coordinator + 2 other partners).

Multidisciplinary challenges

The course will have a set of multidisciplinary authentic real-life assignments proposed by the InCITIES Associated Partners (APs), with an envisioned futuristic framework. Based on the reality of each AP the challenges are designed and thematic linked, and are to be tackled by the participants of the course.

While combining the multidisciplinary authentic real-life assignments proposed by the APs with the WP2's thematic areas, the themes of the ISCTE pilot school are data-driven, centred on people, mobility, social inclusion and well-being, as follows:

1. People centredness: User-focused data analysis and decision-making
2. Application accessibility: Data presentation and visualisation
3. Sensing mobility data: Trends and incentives for the use of bicycles and train as green means of mobility
4. Inclusiveness:
 - a. Promotion of inclusion in the labour market of Autistic and other neurodiversities
 - b. Human centred Artificial Intelligence.

Timing

- The ISCTE winter school pilot happens in 1st semester of 2024-2025 academic year and is scheduled for end of October 2024 to January 2025.
- Duration: 12 weeks, consisting of 9 x 2 h online modules, and 1 week on-site (20h)

The on-site course will be held on week of 20th to 24th of January 2025.

Participants

- Target of at least 15 bachelor, master and/or PhD students, including some from partnering institutions (with Erasmus+ BIP travel and accommodation funding). The maximum number of students is 30.

Workload and accreditation

- 6 ECTS i.e. the equivalent of 150 working hours, including reading, attending online and on-site course, related visits, and preparing contributions. The breakdown is as follows:
 - Online participation: 9x2h = 18h

- On-site participation: 20h
- Preparatory reading: 9x1h = minimum 9h
- Weekly group assignments preparation for the online course: 8 x 1.5h = 12h
- On-site visits: 8h
- Conclusion of writing report after on-site week: 20h
- Independent Autonomous Work: 63h
- Current total: 150h
- Course organisers will issue a certificate of completion if all conditions for passing each module are approved.

Tools

For the online sessions an appropriate platform will be used, according to the existing licences in ISCTE (Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Moodle). To share documents and activities it is possible to work with shared virtual areas (e.g., Google drive, Microsoft Sharepoint and Moodle).

7.2.2 Marketing plan

The marketing plan follows the same guidelines of the UNIZA school pilot with the necessary adaptations for the ISCTE school pilot, assuming different dissemination channels and means (physical and digital) for the communication and dissemination strategy. Materials for dissemination are planned and are being finalised to facilitate the information access by students on different educational levels.

The information and dissemination materials will be spread across the InCITIES and PIONEER partners, and online (ISCTE, InCITIES and Erasmus BIP Search websites) to reach and attract several international students.

The visual identity of ISCTE school pilot will follow InCITIES image and visual rules, referring the coordinator and participant partners.

The dissemination materials in physical and digital format, such as posters, flyers, e-mails, posts for social media, institutional website, and internal video channel will be used.

Proposed marketing text

The text in Table 7 below is to be used across the various marketing instruments. The full text will also be used on the InCITIES website. The marketing plan uses the whole text or its parts in other mediums.

Table 7 - ISCTE pilot marketing text.

<European Commission logo>		<InCITIES logo>		
ISCTE - University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges Blended Intensive Programme Course 30 October 2024 - 24 January 2025 InCITIES Trailblazing Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities				
6 ECTS	9 weekly online modules (2h)	1 week on-site seminar in January 2025	2 sets of Authentic real-life assignments	Learning-by-Developing (LbD) approach
On completion of this course, you will walk away with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Practical skills and strategies applicable to real-life real-life assignments – Analytical frameworks for critically thinking about mobility, inclusion, sustainability and resilience – Tools and methods for assessing application accessibility, urban mobility trends, inclusiveness and people centredness – Learning-by-Developing hands-on approach – Effective communication and teamwork skills together with experts, stakeholders, and peers – An invaluable experience and professional connections – A certificate of competence from the ISCTE, a research-driven university 				
A futuristic approach to urban inclusion and sustainability				
Course curriculum <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. People centredness: User-focused data analysis and decision-making 2. Application accessibility: Data presentation and visualisation 3. Sensing mobility data: Trends and incentives for the use of bicycles and train as green means of mobility 4. Inclusiveness: 		LbD challenges You will contribute to real challenges needs of: CP Trains of Portugal and Wegenblock Genesis companies <hr/> <picture illustrating the real-life assignment> Inovar Autismo NGO <picture illustrating the real-life assignment>		

<p>a. Promotion of inclusion in the labour market of Autistic and other neurodiversity persons</p> <p>b. Human centred Artificial Intelligence</p> <p>The course ends with one week on-site seminars and the Hackathon Future Cities From Vivid Reality: Inclusive and Sustainable Challenges in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. Expect site visits, keynotes and round-tables from local government, civil society, industry, and academia</p>	
<p>Deadline for applying: 20th September 2024</p> <p>www.incities.eu/course2/</p>	<p><QR code containing registration link: https://www.incities.eu/course2/></p>
<p><InCITIES partner logos></p>	
<p>https://incities.eu/</p>	<p>1 October 2022 - 30 September 2025</p> <p>Grant agreement ID - 101071330</p>
<p>Funded under the Horizon Europe Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence Program</p>	

Before the online scheduled modules, meetings with instructors will be organized in order to finish the details of modules articulation and participants activities.

7.2.3 Online course planning

To present the ISCTE school pilot online modules, table 8 show the sessions and the involved institutions.

Table 8- Online course overview of the ISCTE school pilot, 9 online session modules

Module	Dates	Sessions	Institution
#1	30 October 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Introduction to the ISCTE pilot school – LbD for students – Discussion 	ISCTE, LAUREA

#2	6 November 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Presentation of the Hackathon challenges – Q&A 	ISCTE, Associated partners
#3	13 November 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Futurism - cities foresight – Q&A 	LAUREA, ISCTE
#4	20 November 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Information, Data Visualization and Accessibility for User Decision Making – Q&A – Group sessions – Tutors support 	ISCTE
#5	27 November 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Design thinking for envisioning cities futures focused on the LbD challenges – Q&A – Group sessions – Tutors support 	ISCTE
#6	4 December 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sensing mobility data – Q&A – Group sessions – Tutors support 	ISCTE
#7	11 December 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Transport innovation - Sustainable Urban Development – Q&A – Group sessions – Tutors support 	UNIZA, ISCTE
#8	18 December 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Intermediate presentations to the associated partners – Q&A 	ISCTE, Associated partners
#9	15 January 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Human centred Artificial Intelligence – Q&A – Group sessions – Tutors support 	ISCTE

Before the online and the on-site course execution, meetings with instructors and the stakeholders will be organized in order to finish the details of participants activities.

7.2.4 On-site course planning

The on-site week includes several activities, such as group workshops, visits, round-tables and a Hackathon. During the Hackathon a jury will decide on 2 student groups who will win prizes in 2 different categories. This is also part of the ISCTE strategy to attract student participants. The jury is composed of different members from local government, civil society Non-

Governmental Organisations, industry, and academia. Table 9 summarises the on-site week schedule of ISCTE school pilot.

Table 9- On-site week schedule.

Time	20 January 2025	21 January 2025	22 January 2025	23 January 2025	24 January 2025
9h00-10h30		Workshop Session	Workshop Session	Workshop Session	Hackathon presentations & Jury Contest Final Decisions
10h30-11h		Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break
11h-12h30m		Round table on future cities thinking with the APs	Inclusive Social Design & project E3UDRES2 Ent-re-novators (IPS)	Workshop Session	Wrap-up and Farewell!
12h30-14h		Lunch Time	Lunch Time	Lunch Time	
14h-16h	Welcome Session! Orientation @ISCTE	Visit Associated Partner	Tech innovation and entrepreneurship / Visit AUDAX-ISCTE tech. transfer unit	Visit Associated Partner	
16h-18h			Visit Lisbon Historical sites		

8. KEY TAKE-AWAYS

This final section summarises the important aspects that similar Higher Education Institutions should consider before starting co-creating with partners a short-term (Winter, Summer) school pilot encompassing a multidisciplinary international LbD approach and a Erasmus+ BIP according to the 2024 EC rules.

Deliverable D6.1 Pedagogical Model Strategic Plan introduced the 7 core themes that form the scientific basis for a systemic and integrated approach to making cities ISR. Building on these core themes, the purpose of the InCITIES pilots to take place at UNIZA (Slovakia) and ISCTE (Portugal) is to contribute towards creating a common knowledge base on ISR cities in a holistic way.

This document, D6.2. - Learning material and pilots plan - provides a practical guide for organising and implementing LbD-based training events, ensuring practical, real-world learning experiences that contribute to the development of inclusive, sustainable, and resilient cities.

During the process of planning and organising both WP6 InCITIES pilots, **several constraints and institutional challenges** were identified and had to be addressed to enable successful implementation of the pilots. The main challenges include attracting and retaining instructors and students, issues related to micro-credentials such as issuing ECTS credits for international new courses, challenges concerning planning and minimizing the travel costs for course participants. Most of those challenges can be addressed by efficient coordination and collaboration between key partners within the institution, such as the institution's management, relevant study programme guarantors, departments for marketing and international relations as well as ERASMUS+ coordinators. Furthermore, continuous collaboration and coordination between InCITIES partners and their respective ecosystem stakeholders is key for ensuring the international exchange of students, creation of engaging and relevant course learning material and, crucially, ecosystem stakeholders' satisfaction with the produced outcomes, enabling the uptake of LbD pedagogical approach in the widening institutions beyond the initial pilot courses.

As LbD approach is a rather novel pedagogical model at UNIZA, **several efforts were necessary to share knowledge around LbD pedagogical model and get instructors and educational staff familiar with its principles**. These efforts included discussing the different pedagogical approaches, methods and practices already in use in the respective institutions and their difference from LbD.

At ISCTE a very similar approach to LbD is already applied since several years, the main difference being the professional formal relation LAUREA establishes with its regional ecosystem.

A set of training materials, such as webinars and guides, was produced and made available for the involved course instructors. Furthermore, a mentorship was established between LAUREA and two pilot teams to provide guidance and feedback on the LbD implementation, enhancing the InCITIES collaboration and ensuring its continuation towards the end of the project and beyond the project lifespan.

In accordance with the LbD pedagogical approach principles, the **course teaching materials were developed based on genuine authentic real-life assignments** which are real and relevant to be resolved and provided by an Associated Partner. Applied to the context of InCITIES, the process of identifying authentic real-life assignments is iterative rather than linear and consists of several steps. First, relevant ecosystem institutions, i.e. Associated Partners, are contacted and asked to provide authentic challenges related to ISR which they are facing and need to have addressed. Second, a team of experts including the course instructors reviews the authentic challenges and confirm the course material can be adapted to contribute to the solutions. Finally, the course material itself is produced by instructors collaborating with local LbD experts.

The **process for the preparation of the course learning material** stems from the identified authentic real-life assignments proposed by the stakeholder ecosystem. The challenges are decomposed into requirements and skills required to solve them and theoretical learning contents and main unit courses that need to be part of the course are identified in a bottom-up approach. Especially in the international and multidisciplinary environment, soft skills-improving activities, such as team building and breaking the ice activities, need to be included in the course to facilitate connection and rapid uptake of collaboration between the course participants.

To **ensure that students with various disciplinary, educational and cultural backgrounds can effectively collaborate on real-life projects**, a comprehensive approach to implementing LbD is necessary. This includes building and maintaining a supportive learning environment and forming diverse teams to work on authentic real-life assignments which are well balanced in terms of **participants' study degree, discipline, nationality/culture, gender and personality types**.

Furthermore, **leveraging technology for collaboration and providing structured mentorship and support in terms of regular feedback, opportunities for community building and reflection and continuous assessment** are essential components to successful LbD implementation.

All these LbD steps are fundamental to increase the cohesion of the institutional partnership of InCITIES, and PIONEER Alliance more broadly, setting the stage for international and multidisciplinary LbD implementations. For that, LbD co-creation processes will be fundamental.

ANNEXES

Annex I - PRACTICAL GUIDE_InCities

UNIVERSITY OF ŽILINA
Institute of Lifelong
Learning

InCities

**PRACTICAL GUIDE TO PILOT
COURSE DESIGN**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER 1: THE INNER DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND SOFT SKILLS

CHAPTER 2: 7 PILLARS AND FUTURES THINKING

CHAPTER 3: GUIDANCE AND ROLES

CHAPTER 4: MAJOR KEY DESIGN RULES

CHAPTER 5: COURSE AND CASE STUDIES WITH AUTHENTIC CHALLENGE

CHAPTER 6: 10 PRINCIPLES OF THE PILOT COURSE

THE INNER DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND SOFT SKILLS

GOALS:

- to bring focus on the importance of soft skills in our course, engineering, education, and personal and professional growth
- to explain the relationship of hard skills + soft skills + attitude = competence
- the roles of IDG, 4Cs and soft skills in Learning by Developing (LbD) and lifelong learning

WHAT IS THE FRAMEWORK FOR TEACHING AND LEARNING WORKING-LIFE COMPETENCES?

Various approaches mean various sets of soft skills. Following the **Learning by Developing** action model, our experience, engineering job descriptions and future challenges in our branches and societies, we should concentrate on the ones in the graph below:

Picture 1. Generic working-life competences. (www.laurea.fi)

"The Competence flower" figure shows the combination of Knowledge, Skills, Soft Skills, Attitudes and Mindsets, which is the ultimate goal of learning. We do not develop these components separately – on the contrary, we use the potential of their relationship in our methods. In life, we do not learn hard skills separately, but we develop them within “a set” of other important components. We create **competences**.

WHAT ARE PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT GOALS?

IDG: The Inner Development Goals

In today's fast-paced world, personal growth and societal change are more intertwined than ever. Should we like to prepare our participants for the world to come, we must consider various competences and educational approaches towards them. Some professionals and official EU documents use terms such as **hard skills, soft skills, knowledge, attitude, and mindset**. However, these terms are not used separately, as individual entities – on the contrary, they are viewed as components that form one efficient whole.

Picture 2: The Inner Development Goals (<https://www.innerdevelopmentgoals.org/framework>)

When discussing the dimensions above and the set of skills they include, one realizes that these dimensions function as parts of the whole. For the purpose of their development, acquisition and education and easier comprehension, they are defined and described separately.

In the book “Inner Development Goals” Kristian Stålné, and Stefanie Greca aim at the expansion of individual and collective capacity to respond to perceived challenges that arise from the standpoint of individual skills as well as collective perspective.

Firstly, we must cultivate our inner life and develop and deepen our relationship to our thoughts. Afterwards, we can develop our cognitive skills by taking different perspectives, evaluating information and making sense of the world as an interconnected whole.

The third dimension helps us to create more just and sustainable systems and societies for everyone, in the fourth one we need to develop our abilities to include, hold space and communicate with stakeholders with different values, skills and competencies.

The last – although equally important – dimension discusses qualities such as courage and optimism, which help us to acquire true agency, break old patterns, generate original ideas and act with persistence in uncertain times.

WHAT ARE THE SOFT SKILLS WE NEED TO DEVELOP?

Key competences in the area of knowledge, skills and attitudes appropriate to each context are fundamental for each individual in a knowledge-based society. They provide added value for the labour market, social cohesion and active citizenship by offering flexibility and adaptability, satisfaction and motivation. (www.europa.eu)

8 key competences for lifelong learning, were defined, namely

- Literacy
- Multilingualism
- Numerical, scientific and engineering skills
- Digital and technology-based competences
- Interpersonal skills, and the ability to adopt new competences
- Active citizenship
- Entrepreneurship
- Cultural awareness and expression

“Soft skills” as a term in the world of work are associated with a person’s emotional intelligence, the cluster of personality traits, social graces, communication, language proficiency, personal habits, feelings, optimism, and teamwork that characterise relationships with other people. Though soft skills are hard to quantify or measure, they are needed for everyday life as well as for work (comp. soft skills for engineers, teachers, etc.).

Soft skills often refer to characteristics and abilities that are necessary for dealing with other people and for working together in a team. These include communication, teamwork, time management, problem-solving and leadership.

Soft skills have become an inevitable potential that employers seek in their employees, professors in their teaching and research staff and teachers in their students. We gain these skills through life and work and that is why the LbD action model also fully supports and concentrates on them.

They will be developed, trained, obtained and evaluated hand-in-hand with other “hard skills” during the course, as, naturally, it is not feasible to concentrate solely on only one set of skills. Our course aims to assist in the creation and acquisition of competences, i.e., skills, knowledge and attitudes as one unit.

HOW CAN WE DO IT?

First of all, we prepare activities that will require intertwined development and training of soft skills, hard skills and attitudes. For example, in our educational activities concerning cities' needs of inclusion, sustainability and resilience, we may focus on the elements of the smart city and their definition (hard skills). We will approach them critically (what are their functions, positives, negatives, future challenges?), we will work on partial tasks in teams and then the teams can present their opinions and have a classroom discussion with a summary of results. It is about complexity, but, at the same time, about the combination of individual sets of skills.

4 Cs

The concept of 4 Cs has been a part of lifelong learning for a while and there is a strong and efficient bond with STEM or STEAM education (more: <https://education.ec.europa.eu/>). The term 4 Cs means Creativity, Critical Thinking, Collaboration and Communication. Do you see their importance in the work environment as well as education?

Communication means sharing of thoughts, ideas, and questions. There are multiple ways you can deliver your message effectively, and we need to encourage students to find them and use them.

Critical thinking is an absolute must for future engineers. Looking at problems in a new way is an intrinsic feature of every single professional with an inner need to explore, experiment, evaluate, measure, discuss...

Creativity a.k.a. thinking out of the box. Being innovative, challenging traditions and providing new and unexpected solutions. Brainstorm, brainwrite, create a mind map....

Collaboration vs working on your own. Yes, some deeds must be performed individually. But can you imagine solving issues, problems, and projects like InCity project on your own? No way...

SUMMARY

The aim of LbD and our course is to develop a set of competences, i.e., we need to implement soft skills as well as hard skills and attitudes. Thus, we must implement such activities, through which we focus on all three components. For example, the activity through which the students learn and understand what the concept of e.g., the smart city is (hard skills), what its advantages and limitations (soft skills and attitudes) are, they will work in a group (cooperation), they will present and discuss their findings (communication).

GLOSSARY:

Competence

Attitude

Soft skills

Hard skills

Critical thinking

Creativity

Interpersonal skills

Communication skills

Collaboration

Responsibility

Self-management

RESOURCES

https://idg.tools/assets/221215_IDG_Toolkit_v1.pdf

https://eures.ec.europa.eu/strengthening-your-soft-skills-doesnt-need-be-hard-2022-08-10_en

<https://www.ktit.pf.ukf.sk/images/clanky/Dokumenty/Desire/Softskillsforengineers.pdf>

<https://ops.laurea.fi/index.php/attachment/36431/18679>

7 PILLARS AND FUTURES THINKING

GOALS:

- to explain 7 Pillars for the futures thinking in terms of our course and the whole project
- to make sure that all the stages are comprehensible and form a background for our course content, goals and methods

WHAT ARE THE 7 PILLARS OF FUTURES THINKING?

Futures thinking is a creative and exploratory process that uses divergent thinking, seeking many possible answers and acknowledging uncertainty. It is a different mind-set to analytical thinking which uses convergent thinking to seek the right answer and reduce uncertainty.

In the InCITIES Grant Agreement, it is said that the deployment and scalability design for the LbD activities is made in line with the transformative frame of Six Pillars of Futures Thinking for Transforming” and that “[...] the pillars will serve as guidelines to challenge existing structural, cultural and/or behavioural barriers to the implementation of LbD in the InCITIES alliance.”

What Are These Pillars and What Is Their Purpose for Our Course?

The Seven Pillars provide a theory of futures thinking that is linked to methods and tools and developed through praxis. The pillars are: mapping, anticipation, timing, deepening, creating alternatives and transforming. The framework helps to define which methods and tools are appropriate for which national, institutional, organisational, and personal contexts.

CURIOSITY Mapping skills and knowledge to think about the future	INSPIRATIONS Setting goals that challenges the existing anticipatory assumptions about the future	EXPERIMENTATIONS Increasing the creation and uses of futures oriented information and knowledge	CO-CREATION Creating a shared understanding of the alternative futures, based on the uses of futures oriented approaches, methods and tools	DEVELOPMENT The active and impactful uses of the gained new knowledge and experiences	ACTION The systematic use of the created novel thinking patterns and operational models	
The used future: <i>mapping</i> the current understanding about the future SOCIAL JUSTICE through empowerment	The disowned future: <i>anticipation</i> seeking for disruption in the ways to look for the future RISK MITIGATION as a means to see beyond risks	Alternative futures: <i>timing</i> understanding the need to shape established practices ALTERNATIVE FUTURES to shift mindsets	Alignment: <i>deepening</i> creating a common language between different stakeholders DIRECTIONALITY to create change with impact	Models of social change: <i>building alternative futures</i> MAKING THE VISION REAL is creating ownership	Uses of the future: <i>managing change in everyday life, transforming</i> METAPHOR that supports the new vision	MANTRA that opens up for transformation on an individual level

The six (seven) pillars framing the uses of the future (see Ketonen-Oksi 2020; 2022), adopted from Inayatullah (2008; 2022)

What Will Be the Future of Cities Like?

Pollastri et al. (2017) wrote about city futures, claiming that “city futures, generated by a polyphony of multiple voices, should be envisioned in ways that enable their inherent pluralism to emerge as a defining characteristic of the vision.” It means that typical features of future cities will be variability, diversity, pluralism, multiplicity, etc. Our main task is to **strengthen inclusiveness** and to do so, we have to be concentrated on the **mindset**.

The pillars are the guidelines or a transformative frame referring to the means of enlarging the understanding of how we approach the futures. It is about how to create the needed practices and processes to transform our cities toward inclusion, resilience, and sustainability.

In our efforts – not only in the course but also in the project as a whole – we need to know our situation, set goals, as well as competence efficient in the future, shift the mindsets, and create the change with the expected impact. Afterwards, we systematically apply the gained knowledge, skills and information. The final stage is the transformation.

There are similar 7 stages in the course/project cycle. We start with the theme for the course and we end with closing discussion. (Elina Wainio, Laurea)

SUMMARY

The seven pillars model focuses on the importance of transforming the way we think about the future and our roles within as well as methods, tools and processes of anticipation of the futures. Our main aim is to strengthen inclusiveness in future cities and thus we must deal with the mindset primarily.

GLOSSARY:

Mapping

Anticipation

Timing

Deepening

Creating alternatives

Transforming

Inclusiveness

Mindset

Inclusion

Resilience

Sustainability

Peer to peer learning model

RESOURCES

<https://www.bbvaopenmind.com/en/articles/futures-studies-theories-and-methods/>

<https://www.benlandau.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/Inayatullah-2008-Six-Pillars.pdf>

GUIDANCE AND ROLES

GOALS:

- to explain roles within a course: a teacher, a student, a partner
- to discuss what competences a teacher and a student need to work in the LbD course
- to concentrate on the multilevel competence of a student

WHAT ARE THE KEY ROLES OF PARTICIPANTS?

A successful course of study based on Learning by Developing a pedagogical model requires a lot of knowledge and understanding from all parties: students, teachers, course creators and working life partners. The most important issue is the change in partners' roles, such as seeing the student as a junior colleague in a team, the working life expert as a partner and the teacher as a senior colleague or a **facilitator, partner and expert** in his or her own field. Competence-based education as a part of the new learning culture, including the development of innovations with society and for society, as well as internalizing the model of the three integrated tasks, led to the discovery of a pragmatic learning theory as the basis of **learning by acting together on an authentic challenge**.

TEACHER	STUDENT	PROJECT MANAGER (student)	PARTNER
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • directs the work to start • guides in team formation and work, helps in conflicts • motivates & inspires • guides to stay on schedule • guides the work to stay in line with the goals • guides in methodical solutions • guides general working life competencies • guides the construction of the theory base • gives, receives and reacts to constant feedback • Evaluates the process and the final result 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • does project work as a responsible and active team member • Creates and agrees to follow the team rules • Seeks for solutions in conflicts • Aims the actions and learning towards the goals • communicates with colleagues and teachers • constructs the theory base • makes methodological choices • evaluates the process and the end result (incl. self and peer evaluation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • guides the work to stay in line with the goal • guides to stay on schedule • Participates in construction of the theory base • participates in choosing methods • Is the communication link between the team, teachers, partner and other stakeholders • Motivates & seeks solutions to conflicts • gives, receives and reacts to constant feedback • evaluates the process and the final result (incl. self and peer evaluation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • assigns an authentic challenge • helps in finalizing the focus and the goal of the project • Provides the team with adequate and relevant knowledge and information • communicates with the project manager & teacher when needed • reviews the advancement of the project • gives, receives and reacts to constant feedback • evaluates the process and the final result

Examples of roles and activities of teachers (senior colleagues), students (junior colleagues) and partners in the LbD course. (P. Nurkka, Laurea)

WHAT ARE THE ROLES OF A TEACHER?

The LbD Guide (2011) describes the new roles of transformative teachers as 1) **creators and organisers** of the LbD implementation process, 2) **implementers** and 3) **evaluators**.

A teacher has the role of facilitator, partner, developer and researcher. The teacher provides space for students and facilitates their competence-construction processes in relation to practical experiments. As an evaluator, the teacher is involved in assessing the achievements of student's competences as well as the outcomes and the process of the research and development project in cooperation with all the partners involved (see Taatila & Raji 2012).

This means it is not only about the transmission of intellectual actions e.g., in the form of a lecture, but also about the preparation and implementation of educational activities which will develop new ways of action in participants. Integration of various aspects from the field of expertise (e.g., smart city challenges) by the application of various efficient and interesting educational methods, forming a creative and friendly atmosphere with the goals of competence development.

Picture: Teacher's perception towards their role in Course Level Project-Based Learning environment. (Bhaveshkumar Pasi)

The figure shows that the role of a teacher is multifaceted. In other words, the LbD led to a discussion about transformative teaching (see Kallioinen 2011). A **transformative teacher** is seen as

a facilitator, co-actor and coach, representing his or her own expertise and, at the same time, as a senior colleague of a student.

WHAT ARE THE ROLES OF A STUDENT?

A student is seen as a partner who can develop his or her own idea in a project, and simultaneously achieve competences and produce innovations. They are junior colleagues in a team hierarchy. Acting together in an authentic project is seen as an enabler. The student's central role is emphasized. To develop his or her competences (knowledge, soft skills, attitude, mindset) we must **integrate** components of learning knowing, understanding, acting and situation management and the different types of knowledge. At the same time, we must support his or her **creativity, experience, moral values and innovation**.

To do so, we must also pay attention not only to educational methods but also to the connection with real-life issues and a friendly and safe environment during the course. Learning by Developing model demands active participation, commitment, and the construction and sharing of expertise within teams.

The close collaboration with the working life helps students and teachers to establish networks with various partners. To give you an example, thanks to the close collaboration with the working life, the graduates have excellent employment prospects. 96.4% of Laurea graduates find employment within one year of graduation (Finnish National Agency for Education, 2019).

Picture: Learning by Developing model demands active participation, commitment, and the construction and sharing of expertise within teams. The close collaboration with the working life helps students and teachers to establish networks with various partners. (<https://www.laurea.fi/>)

WHAT ARE THE ROLES OF A PARTNER?

The role of the partner from the work environment is key, as it fully supports **partnership, authenticity, research and experimental nature**. The external partner is involved in not only in the forming of an authentic challenge to be dealt with, but also in evaluation and feedback. On the other hand, a working life partner must also understand the principles of the LbD model so that he/she can act as efficiently as possible. The real life projects are our focus and, by **participating as equals**, sharing experiences and finding meanings for consequences, we produce new competence in their varying roles and responsibilities.

SUMMARY

Students are at the centre of research and development activities. They become equal partners with increasing responsibilities (see Taatila & Raji 2012), but they cannot be left alone to struggle with their problems in different projects; they need the presence of teachers as experts in their respective fields as well as facilitators, i.e., people who will guide them to find the meaningful theories and models to be reflected in workshops.

The roles of teachers change along with the world around them. They are facilitators, co-actors, coaches and experts.

The hard knowledge from their fields of expertise is no longer enough - they must master and apply their educational skills which cover the development of students' competence for future life in a friendly and creative environment.

GLOSSARY:

Facilitator

Working life expert

Competence-based education

Evaluator

Preparer

Researcher

Atmosphere

Co-actor

Coach

Transformative teacher

Participant

RESOURCES

<https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/745205/LintilaTMarstioTHighereducationworking.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

<https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/159833/Laurea%20julkaisut%20101.pdf>

VESA TAATILA & KATARIINA RAIJ (2012) Philosophical Review of Pragmatism as a Basis for Learning by Developing Pedagogy, *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 44:8, 831-844, DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-5812.2011.00758.x

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341371130_Teacher%27s_perception_towards_their_role_in_Course_Level_Project-Based_Learning_environment

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270576129_Entrepreneurship_Education_in_the_LbD_action_model_-_review

MAJOR KEY DESIGN RULES

GOALS:

- to provide basic rules following necessary the LbD requirements
- to pay attention to competence development
- to explain the steps, roles and responsibilities of teachers, students and partners
- to state examples of individual issues

WHAT DO WE CONSIDER WHEN DESIGNING A COURSE?

Students' Competence

Dialogue and team learning transform the role of the teacher into that of a coach and facilitator. Project learning includes the basic idea of **flipped learning**, that is, the coach introduces the students in a team to independent learning at their own initiative and supports the freedom of choice as a pedagogic solution (Toivola, Peura & Humaloja 2017, 29).

It is important to **create an atmosphere** that promotes learning, development and participation, which enables thinking and innovation and ensures their utilisation in everyday life.

In **dialogic learning environments**, there is room for co-thinking, promoted by active and committed participation, open and confidential **interaction** and support, as well as the building and sharing of knowledge and reflection on knowledge (Syvänen, Tikkamäki, Loppela, Tappura, Kasvio & Toikko 2015).

Teachers' Competence

The teacher's role as a coach involves helping the team members to solve problems and reflect on their learning. The coach uses questions to help the team focus on the relevant aspects concerning the project. The greatest strength is the development of new insight during the work, as the students do not previously know a solution to the problem to be resolved. The most efficient learning is achieved in a **completely new environment** in which the problems are unexpected and unusual (Partanen 2014, 28).

Partners' Competence

Learning by Developing strategy is based on authentic cooperation between Laurea staff, students and working life partners. LbD is usually implemented in co-creation projects with students and

working life partners (Ojasalo, 2018). Partnership means cooperation with working life, students, and teachers. A genuine working life connection brings authenticity. A research-oriented approach refers to studying within the context of higher education. Experimental nature can be understood in different ways, e. g. experiences with given meanings constructing competences.

Team Learning Aspects

It is important for the team coach to keep in mind the three key aspects of team learning (Partanen 2014, 35):

- students learn best when they are personally committed to **the assignment**
- the subject to be learned becomes significant when it is discovered and understood as a result of personal **contemplation and searching**
- personal commitment to the goals of learning and appreciation of the student’s participation in the joint learning process promote learning. (Sanna Juvonen, Päivi Marjanen & Tarja Meristö (eds.)

101 LEARNING BY DEVELOPING 2.0)

Table 1. *Guidance challenge: student’s competence vs. guidance resources*

INSTRUCTOR \ STUDENT	NOVICE	PROGRESSING NOVICE	SKILLED, INDEPENDENT
INSTRUCTOR FROM CAMPUS, NOT INVOLVED IN THE PROJECT	A LOT OF EXTRA WORK IS REQUIRED TO THE INSTRUCTOR TO FAMILIARISE THEMSELVES WITH THE PROJECT	THE INSTRUCTOR’S WORKLOAD DECREASES WHEN THE STUDENT CAN FAMILIARISE THEMSELVES WITH THE PROJECT INDEPENDENTLY	
INSTRUCTOR FROM CAMPUS AND FROM THE PROJECT	A LOT OF WORK, DIVISION OF WORK BETWEEN INSTRUCTORS IS IMPORTANT	AN IDEAL SITUATION FOR THE GUIDANCE OF STUDENTS	
INSTRUCTOR FROM THE PROJECT	THE MOST CHALLENGING GUIDANCE SITUATION	A SKILLED, INDEPENDENT STUDENT MAKES THE GUIDANCE SITUATION EASIER	

With respect to team learning, it is useful to have students with different strengths and competence backgrounds as team members. In addition to the efficient creation of ideas, the requirements for team members include flexibility and good **organisational skills**, excellent skills for encountering the client as well as punctuality, precision and perseverance. According to the circumstances, a quiet creator of ideas and a team member with a calming and balancing effect are also important. In their peer assessment, team members pay particular attention to the other members’ successful everyday work, utilising it in their own work under the principles of developmental evaluation.

When carrying out peer assessment of learning, students reflect their own behaviour on the everyday behaviour of the other team roles in the projects. This assessment mainly targets the teammates' individual strengths, which as resources enable and further motivate the development of teamwork skills:

“Creates a positive spirit”

“A cohesive system”

“Creative, improvising”

“Takes the reins”

With regard to the guidance challenge, the most challenging situation is one in which the student is a novice requiring a lot of guidance, for which only the project employee is responsible. With novice students, LbD work requires splitting the tasks related to the project into smaller, easily comprehensible, units.

This requires a lot of resources from the project employee, which in turn decreases the resources available for the actual project work. In an ideal guidance situation, the student is competent and independent or at least a novice who is progressing well, and the guidance resources come from both the project and the campus teaching personnel, who also contribute to the project – at least to some extent.

WHICH KEY ASPECTS OF THE LBD MODEL MUST BE INCLUDED IN THE COURSE?

Key aspects of Learning by Developing (LbD) include:

- learning through research, reflection, and development in collaboration with teachers, students, and professionals from the working life
- building a knowledge base through academic studies
- practicing skills in real-life contexts
- developing creative problem-solving approaches
- acquiring the necessary expertise in their field by participating in a diverse range of development projects
- establishing professional connections during their studies, as active interaction with the working life is integral to our education
- engaging in self-directed learning, including online courses and automated learning

Throughout their studies, students gain the confidence to tackle challenges and act autonomously. They acquire the ability to integrate theory and practice, develop problem-solving skills, and engage in critical thinking and reflection. Through purposeful and guided work, they learn to manage complex tasks and project work, with a focus on investigative and developmental approaches to learning.

Implementing a LbD study unit with an authentic project

E. Wainio, Laurea

The Figure shows a procedure how to implement a LbD pilot study unit.

When organizing the course, we must bear in mind several issues in terms of its content, methods, goals, objectives, organization, environment, participants, etc.

We need to imagine our course as a story and a good story has certain stages: introduction, main parts, and conclusion. Moreover, each part – in our case, the module – has also its own structure to make it comprehensible not only for a teacher but also for a participant – where they are, what they have already achieved and what is still waiting for them to experience.

When one considers all the components of the course, it is obvious that the course must be divided into smaller units (modules). When each module contains several methods with various focuses on competence development, one must also divide the module into smaller parts – activities. And,

again, each activity has its own structure. The structure depends on its position within the module, its main goals, the methods applied and the ways of evaluation.

SUMMARY

When designing an educational course implementing the aspects of the LbD model, we must bear in mind the competence of teachers and the competence of students.

We also have to utilize the benefits of team learning methods and environment. The course must be divided into smaller units – modules – due to efficiency, creation of atmosphere and educational environment. Even they must be divided into smaller parts – activities – arranged in logical order to form a meaningful unit.

GLOSSARY:

Flipped learning

Environment

Atmosphere

Participation

Dialogic learning environment

Interaction

Assignment

Contemplation and searching

Real-life contexts

RESOURCES

<https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/159833/Laurea%20julkaisut%20101.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

<https://www.laurea.fi/en/laurea/laurea-as-a-university/learning-by-developing-lbd/>

https://papers.iafor.org/wp-content/uploads/conference-proceedings/IICE/IICEHawaii2021_proceedings.pdf

IICEHawaii2021_proceedings.pdf (iafor.org)

COURSE AND CASE STUDIES WITH AUTHENTIC CHALLENGE

GOALS:

- to bring **inclusiveness, sustainability, and resilience** into the course content and activities
- to explain the principles of the **Blended Intensive Programme (BIP)**
- to describe the main principles of pilot case studies with authentic challenge in Žilina

WHAT ARE THE MAIN PILOT DESIGN PRINCIPLES?

The main outcomes of WP6 Task 6.3 are to design, test, run, and conceptualise a course that addresses specific challenges faced by European cities under the overarching themes of the InCITIES project, i.e., **inclusiveness, sustainability, and resilience**. The focus of our pilot will be on **Sustainable Mobility Innovations**, thus drawing from UNIZA's and the partners' expertise in their respective fields. To facilitate the pilot organisation, including the opportunities for international student participation and study accreditation, the pilot design is made in line with the principles of the Blended Intensive Programme (BIP), a mobility programme running under Erasmus+.

HOW WILL STUDENTS PARTICIPATE?

Our primary target is Master's and PhD students and the aim is to have **multiple disciplines represented** (social science, environmental science, engineering etc.). We are designing a course in which both local (50 %) and visiting Erasmus students (50 %) can join. The pilot course will be held online. The course opens with a minimum of 15 participants. There will be 3-5 students per case study (a case study is a specific problem to be addressed by students).

Although the intention here is to equip students with knowledge and tools to start the work on their case study as early as possible, the teaching itself should be also designed as much as possible in an **LbD-style, interactive way**: small study cases with authentic challenge are brought in as starting points for applying the theory, or, if really necessary, the theory is presented within specific cases. For example, Sustainability Principles can be introduced by a reflection on the wider impacts of Electric Vehicles, from which principles can be derived as a group.

WHAT IS THE KEY ISSUE OF THE UNIZA COURSE?

UNIZA will focus on case studies relating to **Sustainable Mobility Innovations**. This refers specifically to processes of change and urban retrofitting of the passenger transport system towards best practices enabling more inclusive, sustainable and resilient mobility practices. The core of the case studies will be transport because transport is considered an important action zone for achieving sustainable development, as it plays a significant role in the economic sector. In addition, it affects the daily life of people in the city. It belongs among the largest consumers of energy and has a significant impact on nature and the environment in the city and the health of the people living there. At the same time, it belongs to sectors that develop dynamically and use the latest innovations. In this way, the case study will cover all **7 Inclusive Sustainable and Resilience** themes.

HOW IS THE COURSE ORGANIZED?

The course is divided into smaller units, so-called modules and each module is composed of several activities which are ordered according to their role within the module. They all deal with a common authentic challenge. That means that some are introductory, some focus on modelling competences, during others the students practice their skills, and some provide us with feedback. It is like a good story that is remembered for a long time: it has to have an appealing beginning, a challenging central part and a clear end.

We have to “granulate” the time, content and methods into smaller units which also have their own focus, methods and organization. This fully supports the management of learning and teaching by students and teachers. Smaller units are more convenient for progress tracking, we can focus on specific components of competences, they are more flexible, and, in the end, we can manage feedback and assessment easily.

Traditionally, the organization of the module could be represented by the chart below.

MODULE	ACTIVITIES	FOCUS AND OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITY STRUCTURE	RISKS COMMENTS
	Introduction	To know	Lead-In	
	Modelling of competences	To understand To apply	Ask and motivate	
	Practicing the competences	To analyse To evaluate	Give the instruction	
	Evaluation and Feedback	To create	Make the reflection	
		Conclusion		

WHAT IS A CASE STUDY WITH AN AUTHENTIC CHALLENGE?

There are several definitions of case studies as a method applied in education. For example, “case studies represent realistic, complex, and contextually rich situations that often involve a dilemma, conflict, or problem where one or more characters in the case must negotiate” (Pratibha Patanka,2022). Fry et al. describe case studies as complex examples which give an insight into the context of a problem as well as illustrate the main point (Fry et al., 1999). According to Stake, a case study is both the process of learning about the case and the product of our learning (Stake, 1995, p. 28).

In our case, a case study is key for our triad course – module – activities. That means, it typically has a structure or format that allows participants to examine the issue comprehensively. It means that it requires a focus on a specific problem, detailed analysis and research, and an understanding of the situation and context. All these components should be authentic, and very frequently connected with both, individual and team work and presentation of the results followed by a discussion and feedback.

The picture shows different components of the case study as an educational method.

And an authentic challenge? **Authenticity** means that development work is close to working life, someone is genuinely interested in the results of the development work and both individuals and communities learn. It refers to a genuine working life connection. A working life-oriented R&D project is viewed as a learning environment that enables the formation of new habits of actions. The authenticity of a challenge is secured by the cooperation and involvement of the external partners and their organization. They help us not only to formulate it, but also to define goals, means of evaluation or timeline.

WHAT ARE THE MAJOR COMPONENTS OF THE CASE STUDY WITH AN AUTHENTIC CHALLENGE?

The specific structure can vary depending on the context, purpose, outcomes, and environment. Nevertheless, we can list the key components that comprise a case study.

1. **Introduction:** in this part, we provide background information about the issue, we also define key players and outline the purpose and focus of the study.
2. **Problem statement or challenge:** we define the challenge clearly. We also mention issues requiring research.
3. **Methodology:** participants define and describe methods for data collection and other activities involved.
4. **Analysis:** sometimes called the heart of the case study, as we analyse collected data in detail. That requires critical thinking, identification of key issues and factors, evaluation of the first solution, and different perspective approaches.
5. **Solutions:** following the results of the analysis, we propose potential solutions and recommendations. They are data-based.
6. **Implementation plan:** we define and describe steps to the solutions based on the selected strategies.
7. **Evaluation and results:** after the implementation stage, we assess the outcomes and evaluate the effectiveness of the strategy and applied solutions.
8. **Conclusion:** we provide the summary of key points, and we emphasize the main findings and the significance of the outcomes. The conclusion may also suggest points for further research.

The picture shows potential activities in our own case study.

WHAT IS THE TIMELINE OF OUR COURSE?

Module	Week (2024)	Online session (2h)	Lead Instructor + Partner Instructor
#1	8	Sustainable Mobility Principles	Yannick Cornet
#2	9	Mobility Planning & Modelling	Marek Drličiak
#3	10	Traffic Calming in Cities	Matúš Kováč
#4	11	Cycling and Active Mobility	Marian Gogola
#5	12	Air Pollution and Air Quality Measurement	Dusan Jandacka
#6	13	Understanding and Assessing Vulnerability	Michal Titko
#7	14	Transport as Critical Infrastructures	Maria Luskova
#8	15	Digital Transition for Safe Mobility	Tibor Petrov
#9	16	Information Security	Peter Holecko & Peter Vestenicky

The timeline will be modified following the LbD principles before the pilot course.

SUMMARY

When designing the course, we have to bear in mind our three main challenges, namely **inclusiveness, sustainability, and resilience** and the focus on **Sustainable Mobility Innovations**. So, what are we going to do? We will apply the pedagogical model of LbD in the methods of case studies. We state an authentic challenge to deal with. We organise our course into smaller units – modules – which will be further divided into smaller, more efficient units. We understand and apply pedagogical components of case studies since they assist us in the competence development of students. Moreover, they are a suitable means for our teachers and professional participants.

GLOSSARY:

Inclusiveness

Sustainability

Resilience

Mobility Innovations

BIP

Case study

Challenge

Methodology

Analysis

Summary

RESOURCES

https://www.edureform.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/EDUREFORM-manual_compressed-1.pdf

Fry, H., et al. (1999). *A Handbook for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*. Glasgow: Kogan Page

Stake, R. (1995). *The Art of Case Study Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

<https://www.easymanagementnotes.com/blog/everything-you-should-know-about-the-case-study/>

<https://www.simplypsychology.org/case-study.html>

SUMMARY: 10 PRINCIPLES OF THE PILOT COURSE

GOALS:

- to provide main principles with examples to create an efficient course
- to explain individual principles and state specific examples
- to show connections between the principles and experience of teachers

WHAT ARE THE STARTING POINTS FOR THE COURSE DESIGN?

When designing and dealing with the overall course, i.e., modules and individual activities within the LbD model, we have to answer 3 basic questions:

1. What are the competences (skills, knowledge, attitudes, mindset) of students after the course completion? In other words: What are its objectives and results?
2. Which educational methods must be applied so that the students will acquire the expected competence?
3. How can we evaluate and assess the defined objectives of the course?

Following these three questions, we have to: 1. define clear, measurable and achievable educational objectives; 2. set and define criteria for evaluation to objectively measure obtained results; 3. identify educational methods whose application ensures that participants reach the defined objectives. From the organisational standpoint, smaller units of the course, the modules and activities, are not separate components. Their content, methods and defined results form a mutually intertwined set. When designing an educational activity, one must know its place within a module and also within the course, so that its partial outcomes will follow the main goals of the module and the whole course.

The figure shows the alignment of the objectives and materials within the course – modules – activities.

PRINCIPLE 1

Define Objectives and Learning Outcomes That Are Clear and That Are Challenging for Students

Based on the LbD methodology, we must know the competence level of students after the activity, module and course completion. Do objectives and outcomes of activities and modules align with the whole course? Are the objectives and outcomes connected with real-life issues (authentic challenge) and do they provide innovation, creativity and soft skills development? When we define objectives and outcomes clearly, we can select efficient activities and methods.

PRINCIPLE 2

Define the Initial Level of Competence of Our Students

When education is a way to reach the peak of the mountain, we have to plan an efficient way to reach it – if we wish to succeed. We know the conditions on the peak, we have just defined them in Principle 1. But we also need to know the level of hikers... We need to know the basic characteristics of our target group to tailor the course for them through the appropriate selection of methods and tasks. In our case, it is the obtained degree, level of English, field of study, etc.

PRINCIPLE 3

Design a Sophisticated Combination of Methods for Online and On-site Education

The LbD model is a resourceful way to get inspired not only in terms of methods, approaches and activities but also from the standpoints of the competences and roles of teachers, students and partners; learning environment, atmosphere and evaluation. Still, teacher (creators of the course) must ask the question: what do we want our students to develop? Usually, we combine educational

methods and techniques (e.g., lectures, teamwork); forms of education; extent and time slot; order and sequence of activities.

PRINCIPLE 4

Activate and Motivate the Students

One of the basic characteristics of the LbD methodology is the application of methods which motivate and stimulate. Students are actively involved in activities, they communicate, conduct research, and provide innovative solutions in activities with teachers and professionals. We aim at creativity, experience, moral values and innovation.

PRINCIPLE 5

Provide Students of the Course with Course Content of High Quality

What does that mean? The content must be up-to-date, research-based, and connected with real-life issues. Students and teachers deal with authentic issues. The issues within the course must also pose a challenge to them, stir their interest, team flow and willingness to deal with them. What we have in mind are international, integrating research results from various fields.

PRINCIPLE 6

Educational Material Must Be Comprehensible and Attractive

The form is equally important as the content and the methodology applied. It also contributes to meeting the defined objectives and outcomes. Online or on-site, the material must meet or exceed the expectations of students. Specifically, the material should have a comprehensible structure that is easy to follow and assists students in learning. It must also provide space for their own comments, feedback, terminology or any kind of issues connected with their development.

The material must provide variability in methods and educational components, so the students are not easily distracted. It must be easily available and accessible and must also meet the requirements of students with specific needs.

PRINCIPLE 7

Create an Atmosphere That Contributes to Security and Team Dynamics

In other words, it is the atmosphere that means openness, freedom of action and encouragement, as well as a sense of security, trust, and equality. All the participants are welcome, respected and involved in activities. One thing to bear in mind: teachers and students will work as a team – in order

to support their active participation, they need to get to know each other or “break the ice”. This will reflect in the sharing of new ideas and innovative outcomes and getting feedback, as well as comments on their performance from their peers. The sense of cohesion, trust, and mutual inspiration and joy stimulates not only soft skills but also professional and personal development as such.

PRINCIPLE 8

Apply Continuous Assessment as a Proof and Stimulus for Learning and Development

Evaluation and assessment can also serve as motivation for learning. Everybody likes to be praised and appreciated and to understand the benefits of activities. Continuous assessment is also a way to intervene in the process. We need to know immediately which issues and methods are efficient or what boundaries we may face. Students also learn about the level of their development.

PRINCIPLE 9

Provide the Assessment That Is Valid, Reliable and Transparent

Validity means that we accurately measure what we intend to measure. It can mean hard skills (knowledge, facts, etc), soft skills, attitudes or mindset. Our objective is competence development... Reliable means that results are fair, and transparent assessment is when students know the method (tests, questionnaires).

PRINCIPLE 10

Provide students with Efficient Feedback

This is one of the key elements in the process of learning. It enables them to track their own development and to approach it critically. The feedback should not be only at the end of the course, it is too late. Let us use it continuously and be sure the feedback is connected with the defined objectives and outcomes.

SUMMARY

Creating a course or its smaller unit, a module, is not an easy job. There are too many elements not only of educational character that one needs to consider. There are requirements related to the content, environment, participants, real-world issues, research, etc... That is why one must

approach his/her module patiently and organise its individual components in an attractive and efficient manner.

These ten simple steps are more about questions one has to ask himself/herself when preparing the educational material. They follow the LbD pedagogical model. Its typical features and benefits for our course are discussed in previous chapters. When we apply its key elements, we provide our students with the activities → modules → course that will develop their competence, with the application of modern and efficient methods in an open and creative atmosphere. Their engagement is guaranteed.

GLOSSARY:

Design

Assessment

Feedback

Objectives

Outcomes

Competence

Soft skills

Knowledge

Attitude

Mindset

Performance

RESOURCES

<https://www.usu.edu/teach/help-topics/online-teaching-orientation/writing-learning-objectives>

Annex II - LbD - SECI - ISR Six Pillars Framework Job Labs methodology

UNIVERSITY OF ŽILINA
Institute of Lifelong
Learning

InCities Methodology for Pilots Execution

**LbD - SECI - ISR - Six Pillars
Framework - Job Labs
Methodology**

Content

1.	LbD and Problem-Based Learning	2
2.	Background Philosophy of LbD and SECI Model	2
3.	The Essential Features of LbD	3
4.	LbD as a Problem-Solving and Dialogue-Based Model	5
5.	Learning Environments and Dialogue in the Coaching of Teams	6
6.	Guidance Challenge: Student’s Competence vs. Guidance Resources.....	7
7.	An Example of the General Overview of LbD Course	7
8.	Six Pillars of Futures Thinking.....	8
9.	The ISR Themes	9
10.	An Example of LbD Using Future Foresight Strategy (Worskhop March 2023, Finland)	11
11.	The Interrelations Between SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), IDGS (The Inner Development Goals), The Six (Seven) Pillars Approach and LbD.....	12
12.	LbD and Its Derivations: JOB LABS Methodology Based on 5E Pedagogical Model (Taught in English for Specific Purposes at FEIT UNIZA)	13

Aims:

- **to briefly explain the necessary components to be covered in InCities pilot execution**
- **to understand the overlapping of the components and their synergy**
- **to put forward empirically proven ways of carrying out the pilots**

1. LbD and Problem-Based Learning

There are several approaches analogical to the LbD (Learning by doing) approach. They should be seen as a small part of a big mosaic picture of LbD. Thus, LbD is sort of compatible with problem-based learning and peer-to-peer learning.

2. Background Philosophy of LbD and SECI Model

Tacit Knowledge and SECI Model of Tacit Knowledge

The concept of tacit knowledge comes from philosopher Polanyi (1958)

- we can know more than we can tell
- tacit knowing is an unconscious process
- synonymous term for “unconscious knowledge”, “implicit knowledge” (riding a bicycle and recognizing faces)
- explicit knowledge a person may enjoy is achieved only through the tacit use of other knowledge and capacities being deployed

SECI Model

SECI is an acronym that stands for socialisation, externalisation, combination and internalisation.

The SECI process consists of four modes of knowledge conversion. An organisation creates knowledge through the interactions between explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge. Through the conversion process, tacit and explicit knowledge expands in both quality and quantity. There are four modes of knowledge conversion (Nonaka, Toyama & Konno, 2000):

1. Socialisation (from tacit knowledge to tacit knowledge)
2. Externalisation (from tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge)
3. Combination (from explicit knowledge to explicit knowledge)
4. Internalisation (from explicit knowledge to tacit knowledge)

Figure 1: Applying the SECI-Model in the Creation Process (www.laurea.fi)

While carrying out the LbD learning model, we limit our operations to cover the last three phases of the SECI model:

- the process begins with externalisation, or unearthing tacit knowledge being shown as explicit knowledge. The basic steps of the LbD model at a general level are easy to communicate and make visible
- after having looked deeper into practices, we begin to discover that there are things that are easy to express and things that, (even for an expert), require a longer time and substantial amount of application before they can be properly understood. This tacit knowledge based on experience was unearthed through dialogue
- an experienced expert in the LbD model was matched with persons with no prior understanding of the subject. These “outsiders” asked questions and were not content with answers that, to be understood, would have required prior understanding and even practice
- the goal of externalisation was to make information explicit using concepts and models. At this stage, tacit knowledge was also transformed into a form that can be understood by others, not just the expert himself

3. The Essential Features of LbD

LbD has taken the form of holistic cooperation between regional stakeholders, researchers and students. The theoretical characters of the LbD are presented in Figure 2 (Raij, 2014). **Partnership** means cooperation with working life, students and teachers. All the partners participate as equals, sharing experiences and finding meanings for consequences to produce new competence in their varying roles and responsibilities. A genuine working life connection brings **authenticity**. **A research-oriented approach** refers to studying within the context of higher education. **Experimental nature** can be understood in different ways e.g. experiences with given meanings thus resulting in competences’ creation. Experiencing can also be inspected on the basis of processes that lead to new forms of action. Learning by developing is value-driven and takes a more holistic outlook on students where real-life projects are the focus (Raij, 2014).

There is room for every partner’s **creativity**, which also leaves room for professional growth. **The production of new knowledge** and the development of competence become evident as the work progresses.

Figure 2: Elements of LbD and their definitions (www.laurea.fi)

When learning according to the LbD model, the goal is to experience both the individual and the community shaped learning, as well as to produce new competence. In practice, **the elements of LbD** can be realized, for example, in the form of:

EXPERIENTIAL NATURE

The student is encountered as an individual (student orientation)

- feedback is the engine of learning
- learning is realized through doing and experiencing
- one's own activities and competence development are reflected in relation to the learning outcomes
- different ways of acquiring skills are offered and accepted

Experiencing can be understood from different viewpoints. First, experiences with given meanings construct competence. Second, experiencing can be examined based on processes that lead to new forms of action. When the consequences of established forms of action turn out to be insufficient in a new situation, the need arises to reflect on personal experiences and create new habits of action.

PARTNERSHIP

- group work and group guidance
- learning activities are communal and entrepreneurial
- each actor works responsibly in their own expert role (student, supervisor, work partner, junior colleague vs. senior colleague)
- multi-professional cooperation

Partnership refers to cooperation among students, lecturers, working life partners and users, and it features mutual commitment. A partnership is built on trust and is characterized by equality. It enables continuous interaction with the learning environment. Joint efforts require that the involvement and different competences of each participant enable the formation of new habits of action and the discovery of solutions that transform practices.

CREATIVITY

- solutions for the development of working life are sought and found using modern methods (service design, co-creation, facilitation of workshops)
- thoughts and competences are shared in a group
- freedom within the Framework

Creativity is vital for bringing forth something new. The starting point of LbD is the ability to function in a constantly changing world; hence, acting within the context of change is a natural approach. As a result, new ways of action require creative and curious involvement in activities that renew the world of work.

AUTHENTICITY

- development work is close to working life, someone is genuinely interested in the results of the development work
- both individuals and communities learn

Authenticity refers to a genuine working-life connection. A working life-oriented R&D project is viewed as a learning environment that enables the formation of new habits of action. The progress of an R&D project opens new doors and creates situations where previous ways of action are no longer sufficient and must be replaced by new ones.

RESEARCH-ORIENTED APPROACH

- academic skills are developed
- information is obtained from appropriate sources and the information is applied to everyday life, however, information is viewed critically.
- the activities are justified based on researched information
- striving for conceptual thinking

The requirement for a **research orientation** arises within the context of higher education. In a pragmatic approach, truth is linked to inquiry as it transforms during the study.

4. LbD as a Problem-Solving and Dialogue-Based Model

Besides, the doubled circle's design shows another possible application when we engage its metaphorically transferred extension to the finding problem's solution (Figure 2: Stages of LbD and their definitions): First, LbD poses a problem or task to be resolved by a working life partner (e.g. municipality, county's representative). Second, three red parts of the inner circle show people talking about the problem or task mentioned. Third, five blue parts of the outer circle – people listening to people talking about the

problem to be solved. Next, after the people belonging to the inner circle finish the discussion, the people of the outer circle are prompted to add their ideas to what they had been just listening to. As a result, after reviewing the ideas the final discussion between the inner and outer circle people generates some creative and innovative ideas.

5. Learning Environments and Dialogue in the Coaching of Teams

- dialogue and team learning transform the role of the teacher into that of a coach and **facilitator**
- project learning includes the basic idea of **flipped learning**; meaning the coach introduces the students in a team to independent learning at their own initiative and supports the freedom of choice as a pedagogic solution (Toivola, Peura & Humaloja 2017, 29)
- creating an atmosphere that promotes learning, development and participation, which enables thinking and innovation and ensures the utilisation of these in everyday life
- dialogic learning environments promote room for co-thinking, promoted by active and committed participation, open and confidential interaction and support as well as the building and sharing of knowledge and reflection on knowledge (Syvänen, Tikkamäki, Loppela, Tappura, Kasvio & Toikko 2015)
- the teacher's role as a coach involves helping the team members to solve problems and reflect on their learning
- the coach uses questions to help the team focus on the relevant aspects concerning the project The greatest strength is the development of new insight during the work, as the students do not previously know a solution to the problem to be resolved
- a completely newly formed environment caters for the most efficient learning in which the problems are unexpected and unusual (Partanen 2014, 28)
- it is important for the team coach to keep in mind the three key aspects of team learning (Partanen 2014, 35):
 - students learn best when they are personally committed to the assignment
 - the subject to be learned becomes significant when it is discovered and understood as a result of personal contemplation and searching
 - personal commitment to the goals of learning and appreciation of the student's participation in the joint learning process promotes learning

Concerning team learning, it is useful to have students with **different strengths and competence backgrounds** as team members. In addition to the efficient creation of ideas, the requirements for team members include **flexibility** and **good organizational skills**, excellent skills for encountering the client as well as **punctuality, precision and perseverance**. According to the circumstances, a **quiet creator of ideas** and a **team member with a calming and balancing effect** are also important. In their peer assessment, team members pay particular attention to the other members' successful everyday work, utilising it in their own work under the principles of developmental evaluation. When carrying out peer assessment of learning, students reflect their own behaviour on the everyday behaviour of the other **team roles** in the projects. This

assessment mainly targets the teammates' individual strengths, which as resources enable and further motivate the development of teamwork skills:

“Creates a positive spirit” *“A cohesive system”* *“Creative, improvising”*
“Takes the reins” *“Calming, balancing”*

6. Guidance Challenge: Student’s Competence vs. Guidance Resources

Instructors from campus and the project are in an ideal situation for the guidance of students. In this case, the large amount of work is to be divided among instructors. Other possible scenarios are put forward in Figure 3:

STUDENT INSTRUCTOR	NOVICE	PROGRESSING NOVICE	SKILLED, INDEPENDENT
INSTRUCTOR FROM CAMPUS, NOT INVOLVED IN THE PROJECT	A LOT OF EXTRA WORK IS REQUIRED TO THE INSTRUCTOR TO FAMILIARISE THEMSELVES WITH THE PROJECT	THE INSTRUCTOR’S WORKLOAD DECREASES WHEN THE STUDENT CAN FAMILIARISE THEMSELVES WITH THE PROJECT INDEPENDENTLY	
INSTRUCTOR FROM CAMPUS AND FROM THE PROJECT	A LOT OF WORK, DIVISION OF WORK BETWEEN INSTRUCTORS IS IMPORTANT	AN IDEAL SITUATION FOR THE GUIDANCE OF STUDENTS	
INSTRUCTOR FROM THE PROJECT	THE MOST CHALLENGING GUIDANCE SITUATION	A SKILLED, INDEPENDENT STUDENT MAKES THE GUIDANCE SITUATION EASIER	

Figure 3: Guidance challenge: student’s competence vs. guidance resources:

Sanna Juvonen, Päivi Marjanen & Tarja Meristö (eds.): LEARNING BY DEVELOPING 2.0 - CASE STUDIES IN THEORY AND PRACTICE

7. An Example of the General Overview of LbD Course

A brief overview of the LbD-based course done in Laurea UAS is depicted in Figure 4:

Implementing a LbD study unit with an authentic project

E. Wainio, Laurea

An example of a LbD study unit with a project follows this structure:

1. Content - overview of the module works and task. In some modules academic LbD articles or part of them are available for reading to get a deeper understanding of the subject
2. Guidance – getting into the LbD mindset and enabling specific actions with “hands-on” advice on what and how to do in practice
3. Tools – project tools and templates help the teacher and his/her students in implementing the LbD project
4. Quiz – the quiz questions help the teacher to reflect and identify the essential discoveries in the module
5. Feedback – giving feedback to course organizers

8. Seven Pillars of Futures Thinking

The ideas mentioned above focused on LbD pedagogical model. Nevertheless, the pilots are supposed to involve methodological/practical applications of futures thinking across different activities. Thus, providing an introduction lecture or workshop to futures thinking and transformative futures should be reflected in course preparation as well.

The deployment and scalability design for the LbD activities are made in line with the transformative frame of Seven Pillars of Futures Thinking for Transforming” and that “[...] **the pillars will serve as guidelines to challenge existing structural, cultural and/or behavioural barriers** to the implementation of LbD in the

InCITIES alliance. To put it simply, this approach shall answer the question: **How to build future orientation/resilience?**

Figure 5: The Seven pillars framing the uses of the future ((Ketonen-Oksi (2020), adapted from Inayatullah (2008: Six pillars) and Inayatullah (2022-2023: Anticipation to Emancipation)Anticipation to Emancipation: Toward a Stage Theory of the Uses of the Future * Journal of Futures Studies (jfsdigital.org))

The table (Figure 5) is to be interpreted as follows:

A) the original Seven pillars (see the pillars simplified in **red**) were more directed toward a process, method-based approach to anticipating the future,

B) the idea behind the stage theory (see the focus areas in **blue**) is more in emancipation, in bringing forth the importance of **transforming the way we think about the future** and our roles within. Thus, the additional seventh pillar that describes transformations at an individual level plays an important part in the updated version.

- if we aim to **strengthen inclusiveness** in the cities, we should think **beyond planning good practices and structures**, and think of how we can have **an impact on the mindsets** instead
- Types of foresight - the transformative frame basically refers to the means of enlarging the understanding of how we approach futures. It thus focuses on the **interpretive structures of foresight actors** and not on an outward description of activities

Pillars are to be viewed as guidelines:

- they offer a powerful tool to make foresight more approachable and less prone to its biased use,
- to make sense of the ongoing foresight systems and capabilities and to thereby help create the needed practices and processes to transform our cities toward inclusion, resilience, and sustainability

9. The ISR Themes

The following six main challenges of future cities were identified in 2021 by the founding members of the PIONEER alliance, i.e., the InCITIES partners:

- carbon-neutral urban areas

- safety, security and risk management for resilient cities
- technology-enhanced solutions with and for smart and citizen-centred cities
- service design with and for socially, culturally, ecologically, and economically sustainable future cities
- sustainable urban life and tourism
- circular economy with and for urban citizens

The abbreviation ISR stands for **Inclusiveness, Sustainability, and Resilience**. Let's have a look in greater detail at what ISR exactly means.

- **Inclusiveness** points to the need for sustainability and resilience interventions to be implemented fairly on one hand, and to be the outcome of a true collective perspective based on values of mutual trust, solidarity, helpfulness and friendliness on the other. In any change process, there is a risk of, for example, further deepening inequalities in wealth distribution, gender, age, or ethnic group. Processes of change must, therefore, be built from the ground up by embedding participatory urban planning practices and paying special attention to the voices of those in vulnerable situations.
- **Sustainability** implies that cities need to tackle jointly the three pillars of sustainable development, addressing for instance climate change by enabling a sustainable economy, and protecting ecological systems and the services the natural environment provides by shifting from resource-based economies towards circular and higher quality economies. Concrete sustainability interventions in cities also include paying special attention to air quality and waste management (e.g. SDG goal 11.6).
- **Resilience** can be built by ensuring more redundancy and variety in essential services (e.g. in health or transportation) and enabling more local, distributed, and flexible production systems (e.g. in energy or food production). Resilience also implies widening risk management practices to include the interplay of complex disruptions in parallel to the ever-present climate crisis and its impacts: droughts, fires, storms, and floods, health and virus threats, wars and refugees from wars or other calamities, energy and food supplies etc.

Supporting quotations:

“City futures, generated by a polyphony of multiple voices, should be envisioned in ways that enable their inherent pluralism to emerge as a defining characteristic of the vision.” (Pollastri et al. 2017)

“Moments of great historical change are underwritten by shifts in collective imagination.”

(Finn & Wylie, 2021)

10. An example of LbD Using Future Foresight Strategy (Worskhop March 2023, Finland)

Problem: **What kind of ecosystem would be the most suitable for foresight supporting decision-making at a cities' level together with companies and educational organisations?**

The task consists of two parts:

- A) Create positive and negative future headlines for **trailblazing, inclusive, sustainable and resilient European cities** which address the challenges of urban development
 - Time frame 10 – 20 years
- B) List **core actors, supportive and related actors and enablers** for creating a foresight ecosystem
 - You can utilize elements of your home city
 - What kind of ecosystem would support the positive future headline (defined in task A)
 - When building a foresight ecosystem what should be considered?

University's current implementation:

1. Stakeholder meetings and gatherings

- Will inspire and deepen understanding around different foresight themes

2. Mentor network will be created for company and educational organisations together with the City of Vantaa

- The aim is to strengthen foresight capabilities
- Selected mentors are experienced at a national level and are familiar with company foresight challenges

3. Learning content on foresight studies will be created on MOOC (massive open online courses) web-based distance learning program

- allows strengthening one's own foresight knowledge

Teams' task: *Having the pictures of both (+) and (-) future outcomes, prepare a poster about your future foresight of the City of Vantaa in a 10–20-year frame.*

11. The Interrelations Between SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), IDGS (The Inner Development Goals), The Six (Seven) Pillars Approach and LbD

Figure 7 clarifies the interrelations between **SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)**, **IDGS (The Inner Development Goals)**, the **six (seven) pillars approach** and **LbD**. In short, the **seven pillars approach is integrated in blue** and the **IDGs in golden yellow**. On the left side, the blue is lighter, meaning that these aims and objectives are quite hard to attain in one process. The aim is to engage the partners in a profound rethinking of their future goals (future-oriented thinking) e.g. possible ecosystem actors in the target cities.

Figure 7: An integration of LbD with IDGs and the seven pillars approach

The actual pilot execution takes place in **3 stages**: **First**, attention should be given to introducing the students and the entire community to new ways of learning together by mapping their different skills and knowledge to think about city futures. We prefer to do that e.g. by testing their level of futures consciousness (see Ahvenharju et al, 2019). To enhance this stage with the IDG approach, the reflections should include thinking about how the students relate themselves to others and the world.

In the second stage, the focus turns to the means of building new competences. The competences involve **expanding the uses of futures-oriented information** and knowledge – e.g. by introducing the students to different forms and interests of knowledge and challenging them to develop their **critical-analytical approach** to the knowledge at hand. Or, in terms of engaging the students to play with new thinking patterns and operational models, to simultaneously motivate them to use scientific knowledge and to enhance their creativity in defining what is possible/plausible or not. The students should learn about their role in making the future either intentionally or unconsciously and understand how the choice between these two often is theirs.

Next, instructors guide the students to question their own **agency and attitudes toward transformation**. Considering sustainability goals and how hard it is to change one's mindset or habits, this is an essential phase to make **long-lasting effects on the students**. All in all, the question is not just simply creating solutions

for certain challenges. Instead, it is about challenging the students' minds about how they approach these challenges overall and how those changes in their agency may only then result in alternative solutions for the cities. The new solutions will potentially be **based on a collective, shared understanding** of how to use the futures.

12. LbD and its Derivations: JOB LABS Methodology Based on the 5E Pedagogical Model (Taught in English for Specific Purposes at FEIT UNIZA)

The 5E pedagogical model below is deployed in teaching English for specific purposes lessons at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. This model resembles project/problem-based learning, which the LbD approach resembles in a variety of ways.

ENGAGE

- random group creation (buzz groups) or
- personalities' meta test employing team roles
- Teacher's role as a facilitator
- Teacher's assistance
- Student's salient influence on the learning process

EXPLORE

- gathering and widening topic-related vocab
- the preparation of several challenges beforehand
- challenges (e.g. How could we ...?) meant to be topic-related questions suggesting areas of interest to be solved
- choice of the challenge and writing it on the big sheet of paper

Teacher's role:

- maintaining an upbeat and focused learning environment
- drawing on current research
- using an inquiry improvement cycle

EXPLAIN

- getting a deeper knowledge of the stakeholder's/company's background.
- one paragraph-description
- students' own contribution with hypotheses, assumptions, possible explanations why a problem could have happened, etc.
- thinking about possible solutions to the problem
- getting a more thorough view

Teacher's role:

- developing student's capacity to collaborate
- conveying high expectations of learning, effort and engagement for all students
- supporting students to explore the construction of knowledge

ELABORATE

- the brainstorming itself
- writing the ideas ranging from 2 – 6 words

- two rules: 1. quantity must outweigh the quality of the ideas
2. instead of using “no, but” use “yes, and”
 - move from surface to deep learning: engaging own experiences, knowledge, inventiveness
 - helpful clue: futurist approach, i.e. imagine in 10-20 years that ...
 - three criteria for ideas: realistic, non-realistic, crazy ideas
 - discussing the variety of arguments within the whole group
 - preparation of a short presentation (1,5 min per student) for prototyping the solution
- Teacher’s role:
- drawing on current research and using an inquiry improvement cycle
 - supporting students to explore the construction of knowledge

EVALUATE

- overall course feedback using focus groups

Teacher:

- evaluation of each team’s solution and presentation
- received individual as well as team feedback
- using internal English for specific purposes (ESP) assessment form
- students prompted to be reflective, questioning and self-monitoring learners

Resources

Uusitalo, T. & Kyrö, J. (2021) From Tacit Knowledge to Explicit – Taken for Granted Pedagogical Practices Made Visible. In The IAFOR International Conference on Education – Hawaii 2021. Official Conference Proceedings, 405-419.

https://papers.iafor.org/wp-content/uploads/conference-proceedings/IICE/IICEHawaii2021_proceedings.pdf

[Anticipation to Emancipation: Toward a Stage Theory of the Uses of the Future * Journal of Futures Studies \(jfsdigital.org\)](https://jfsdigital.org)

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9291410>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0016328717301611>

Deliverable D6.1 - InCITIES-30.09.2023- draft-version-0.5

Laurea’s methodological materials presented on Laurea’s international week

<https://journal.laurea.fi/laurea-international-week-2023-co-creating-international-learning/#b8cccb6a>

Annex III - Complete description of personality types as assessed by the Team role META test

UNIVERSITY OF ŽILINA
Institute of Lifelong
Learning

InCities

PERSONALITY TYPES: DESCRIPTION

Motivators

Motivators have the ability to equally value results and people. They are natural participative persons who work with and through people. Motivators dislike detailed work but do it to achieve a specific objective. Both contacts and the respect of people are important to Motivators. They are good decision makers who consider others in making unpopular decisions. They enjoy public recognition and work assignments which they believe makes them look good. However, they may be too optimistic about what they and other people can produce. Motivators are socially assertive and typically good communicators and can lead and motivate others. They may be difficult to manage. Motivators are not natural administrators. Some people may see them as dynamic personalities with a great deal of enthusiasm while others see them as indiscreet and often hasty individuals. Motivators need a variety of activities and the opportunity of working in a people environment. They like work requiring mobility and the chance to travel. Challenges and opportunities are key to their success. They may become 'workaholics' if not aware of their limits.

Energizers

These optimistic personalities love imaginative and innovative things because they adore novelty and innovations of all sorts. Energizers are fun-loving, highly sociable, and sometimes flamboyant personalities who can be the life of the party. Energizers are usually throwing off positive energy in all directions. These mostly right-brain dominant people become sales and marketing professionals, entrepreneurs, motivational speakers, media celebrities, and politicians. Communicative, motivational, entertaining, and visionary are the traits that describe Energizer personality types.

Teamers

Teamwork is an important part of maintaining a successful workflow in many workplaces. For most teams, collaborating and coordinating with others is a necessary part of completing assigned tasks. Team-workers are also people-oriented. Their extroverted personalities help them function well with others and listen to their teammates. These team members can adapt easily to changes in their environment and they know how to create harmony if conflict arises.

If one team member has too much on their plate or another has a family emergency, team-workers are the first to step in and offer support. Because team-workers are natural collaborators, they'd excel within a larger team. To sum up a teamer is someone who prioritizes the goals of the team rather than just their interests. Teamers often believe the best way to achieve personal success is to help their entire team succeed. For example, a strong teamer might volunteer to work late to help their co-workers achieve a goal. They're often loyal, flexible, and reliable professionals who prioritize their peers and the group over themselves, meaning they're willing to make personal sacrifices if it leads to a better outcome for everyone.

Analysts

The personality type is known for the love of rationality. Because the persons share the Thinking trait, these people often aim to make decisions with their head rather than their heart. But Analysts are far from being robots. Their Intuitive personality trait energizes their imaginations, helping them to come up with creative strategies and motivating them to explore things deeply – whether that's an intellectual pursuit, a new interest, or even a crazy scheme or thought experiment. These personalities are driven to understand and create. They have no problem switching between speculative musing and tactical problem-solving. Of course, these broad abilities need to be honed – and, when appropriate, they need to lead to action. Otherwise, Analysts' active minds can give them a false sense of accomplishment.

93% of Analysts say they listen to their heads rather than their hearts when making important decisions.

To sum up - the Analyst personality is the critical thinker on a team. They are often cautious and do not rush into decision making but prefer to take time to make a well-researched, informed judgement. Their critical thinking ability assists teams to keep from jumping to conclusions. They're more involved with the world of ideas, rather than motivating their team members. Analysts may not be the easiest to handle due to their diligent and long process of decision-making. However, their ability to see both short term and long-term gains and issues is incredibly valuable for a high-performing team.

Further reading:

J.T. Hemdan, D.S. Taha, I.A. Cherif, Relationship between personality types and creativity: A study on novice architecture students, Alexandria Engineering Journal, Volume 65, 2023, Pages 847-857, ISSN 1110-0168, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2022.09.041>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1110016822006354>)

Carlos Flavián, Miguel Guinalú, Pau Jordán, Virtual teams are here to stay: How personality traits, virtuality and leader gender impact trust in the leader and team commitment, European Research on Management and Business Economics, Volume 28, Issue 2, 2022, 100193, ISSN 2444-8834, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100193>.

<https://www.16personalities.com/free-personality-test>

<https://www.humanmetrics.com/personality>

Annex IV - Complete general template for module feedback form

Dear participant,

We kindly request your participation in this survey, comprising of 9 questions. Your feedback is significant for all individuals contributing to the development of the course. Your responses will remain confidential. We sincerely appreciate your valuable ideas and time.

INCITIES SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY INNOVATIONS

From climate anxiety to action

On completion of this course, you will walk away with:

- **Practical skills and strategies** applicable to real-life urban mobility challenges
- **Analytical frameworks** for critically thinking about mobility, inclusion, sustainability and resilience
- **Tools and methods** for planning and assessing urban mobility innovations
- **Effective communication and teamwork** skills together with experts, stakeholders, and peers
- **An invaluable experience** and professional connections
- **A certificate of competence** from the University of Žilina, a world-leading transportation science university

Course details

Course curriculum

- 1 Sustainable mobility principles
- 2 Mobility planning & modelling
- 3 Traffic calming in cities
- 4 Cycling and active mobility
- 5 Air pollution and air quality measurement
- 6 Understanding and assessing vulnerability
- 7 Transport as critical infrastructures
- 8 Digital transition for safe mobility
- 9 Cybersecurity in the smart city

The course ends with one week on-site seminar. Expect site visits and keynotes from local government, civil society, industry and academia.

Case studies

You will contribute to real planning needs for the city of Žilina

- Safe and sustainable access to schools
- Intelligent transport solutions for safe and efficient mobility

Speakers:

- Dávo Sitányiová**: concrete management & environmental protection
- Yannick Cornet**: sustainable mobility, worthwhile travel time
- Christina Georgouli**: regional urban mobility & indicator frameworks
- Tina Wikström**: planetary wellness, social and cultural sustainability
- Manu Kováč**: Road design & diagnostics
- Pedro Sebastião**: technological innovation and entrepreneurship
- Sanna Ketonen-Oksi**: Transformative futures, foresight methods
- Martin Cigola**: Urban transport planning & active travel
- Miguel Sales Dias**: AI, data science and design thinking
- Michal Třítko**: Disaster preparedness & resilience assessment
- Mária Lusková**: Critical infrastructure & urban resilience
- Tibor Petrov**: ITS & UAV communication technologies
- Peter Holečko**: Information systems, IoT & cyber security
- Peter Vestenický**: ITS & communication networks
- Marek Dričiak**: Road design & urban transport planning
- Dušan Jandačka**: environmental engineering & transport air pollution

iscte | **UNIVERSITY OF ŽILINA** | **UNIVERSITÉ GUSTAVE EIFFEL** | **Technology Arts Sciences TH Köln** | **LAU REA** | **ANAKATHINOS GEORGIOU** | **UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES** | **Urh** | **Metu Zilina**

Deadline for applying: 7.2.2024

www.incities.eu/course/

1. How do you evaluate the relevance of the content of this module against your expectations?

- totally non-relevant
- non-relevant
- no opinion
- partially relevant
- totally relevant

2. What was the most important thing you learned during this module?

3. How do you evaluate complexity of the content of this module?

- very easy
- easy
- optimal
- difficult
- very difficult

4. What was the muddiest -least clear- point in this module?

5. What important questions remain unanswered?

6. Did activities in groups develop social skills (e.g., communication, creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, etc)?

- I strongly disagree
- I disagree
- no opinion
- I agree
- I strongly agree

7. Did you have an opportunity to express your opinions in this module?

- I strongly disagree
- I disagree
- no opinion
- I agree
- I strongly agree

8a. How do you evaluate the performance of lecturer <1st instructor name> on <1st lecture topic>?

- poor
- below average
- satisfactory
- above average
- outstanding

8b. How do you evaluate the performance of lecturer <2nd instructor name> on <2nd lecture topic>?

- poor
- below average
- satisfactory
- above average
- outstanding

9. Your input, comments, ideas, and concerns are highly valued in shaping the content of the course. Please share any other feedback. Thank you.

Annex V - Complete description of the Safe and sustainable access to school authentic urban challenge

SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE ACCESS TO SCHOOL

ANALYSIS OF THE AREA

ZŠ s MŠ SV. GORAZDA, ZŠ MARTINSKÁ

Útvar hlavného architekta Žilina

rudolf.chodelka@zilina.sk
michaela.macekova@zilina.sk
brislava.kajanova@zilina.sk
jana.kotrc@zilina.sk

UTVAR
HLAVNÉHO
ARCHITEKTA
ŽILINA

"As planners of our built environments, we must seriously begin to ask ourselves, why is driver comfort so often prioritized over health and well-being of children when designing our streets."

Negative influence of cars on children

- absence of active mobility of children (physical health)
- less socialization (mental health)
- air pollution in the vicinity of facilities intended for children
- worse orientation in space
- dangerous streets (risk of collision between children and cars)

How to improve mobility a children in the streets and public places of residence

- streets in residential areas that encourage children to play
- temporary closure of the street
- creation of public spaces in front of school facilities
- safe way to school/kindergarten
- greenery (insulating, solitary, low)
- making pedestrian routes more attractive
- creating communities

Access to Nature

Social Interaction

Playability

Active mobility

Sense of ownership

Agency and Decision-making

ANALYSE OF PROBLEMS IN THE AREA

ZŠ s MŠ SV. GORAZDA

Legend

- problem areas of pedestrian mobility
- buildings
- - - pedestrian routes
- ▲ main entrance to school

1. bad view to crossing of pedestrians, because of parking cars
2. bad view to crossing of pedestrians, because of parking cars
3. bad view through parked cars
4. under the slope
5. undefined walking routes, missing path and crossing of pedestrians
6. space barriers

- Legend
- local collection communication
 - local service communication
 - local cycle route
 - static traffic
 - bus
 - pedestrian crossing
 - crossing for cyclists

SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE ACCESS TO SCHOOL

ANALYSE OF CURRENT TRAFFIC IN THE AREA

ZŠ s MŠ SV. GRAZDA _ PROPOSAL I. STAGE

- Legend
- local collection communication
 - local service communication
 - local cycle route
 - static traffic
 - bus
 - pedestrian crossing
 - crossing for cyclists
 - proposal

PROBLEMS IN THE AREA

ZŠ s MŠ SV. GORAZDA

Černovská ulica

- absentujú pešie priechody a chodníky
- umiestnenie kontajnerov
- podpora pešej trasy stromoradiím

Ulica Sv. Cyrila a Metoda

- slabý výhľad na priechody
- I. etapa - kiss and ride na ľavo od 7³⁰ do 8⁰⁰

ZŠ MARTINSKÁ

- Legend
- local collection communication
 - local service communication
 - public transport
 - static traffic
 - bus
 - pedestrian crossing
 - crossing for cyclists

URBAN STUDY IN THE AREA

ZŠ MARTINSKÁ

LEGENDA :

	HRANIČA RIEŠENÉHO ÚZEMIA
	POLOHOPIS
	STAVBY V ÚZEMÍ
	OBJEKTY (VÝHLAD)
	PODZEMNÉ GARÁŽE
	OBJEKTY TECHNICKEJ VYBAVENOSTI (TRANSFORMAČNÁ STANICA, VÝMENIKOVÁ STANICA)
	OZNAČENIE SÚPISNÉHO / ORIENTAČNÉHO ČÍSLA OBJEKTU
	OZNAČENIE POČTU BYTOVÝCH JEDNOTIEK V OBJEKTE BYTOVÉHO DOMU
	EXISTUJÚCA PODLAŽNOSŤ (SUTERÉN / NADZ. ČASŤ / PODKROVIE - USKOCENÉ PODLAŽIE)
	VYMEZENIE SEKTOROV V RIEŠENOM ÚZEMÍ
	PLOCHY VEREJNEJ ZELENE
	PLOCHY VEREJNEJ ISOLAČNEJ ZELENE
	PLOCHY VYHRADENEJ ZELENE
	PLOCHY IHRISK
	PLOCHY IHRISK NA PLOCHÁCH VEREJNEJ ZELENE (PŘÍRODNÉ IHRISKO)
	REKREAČNÉ PLOCHY PŘÍRODNÉHO CHARAKTERU
	ĽADOVÁ PLOCHA PRE SEZÓNNE REKREAČNÉ KORČULOVANIE
	ZBERNÁ KOMUNIKÁCIA, FUNKČNÁ TRIEDA B1
	OBSLUŽNÁ KOMUNIKÁCIA, FUNKČNÁ TRIEDA C3
	PEŠIE ZÓNY A OBYTNÉ ULICE FUNKČNÁ TRIEDA D1
	PEŠIE PLOCHY A KOMUNIKÁCIE FUNKČNÁ TRIEDA D3
	MLÁTOVÝ CHODNÍK
	KRYTÝ VEREJNÝ PEŠÍ CHODNÍK
	CYKLISTICKÝ CHODNÍK
	VYZNAČENÝ CYKLOPRUH NA KOMUNIKÁCIÍ D1, C2 A C3
	ZIAZDNÉ A PREVÁDZKOVÉ PLOCHY
	UMIESTNENIE HLAVNÉHO PEŠIEHO VSTUPU DO OBJEKTU
	UMIESTNENIE HLAVNÉHO VJAZDU DOPRAVNEJ OBSLUHY DO OBJEKTU
	OZNAČENIE VETVY KOMUNIKÁCIE
	VYMEZENÁ PLOCHA PODZEMNEJ GARÁŽE
	PARKING V OBJEKTE
	PARKOVACIE PLOCHY S POČTOM STOJÍSK NA OBSLUŽNEJ KOMUNIKÁCIÍ
	PARKOVACIE PLOCHY S POČTOM STOJÍSK NA OBYTNEJ KOMUNIKÁCIÍ
	JAZDNÝ PRUH, SMER POHYBU
	ZÁBRANA OBMEZUJÚCA PREJAZD VOZIDIEL
	PRIESTOR PRE UMIESTNENIE NÁDOB NA ZBER TKO / POLOPODZEMNÉ, KLIETKOVÉ STOJISKO
	PRIESTOR PRE UMIESTNENIE NÁDOB NA ZBER TKO - VARIANTNÉ UMIESTNENIE
	OPLOTENIE
	TERASY PRI PREVÁDZKE
	VÝTVARNÉ DIELO
	PLOCHA PRE UMIESTNENIE VODNÉHO PRVKU

TRAFFIC CHANGES

- traffic signs
- defining pedestrians and cyclists routes
- material and height differences on the pedestrian crossings
- reduction of permitted speed (slow down)
- remove spatial barriers on pedestrians routes
- proper view of pedestrians crossings
- change parking schedule (7³⁰ - 8⁰⁰)
- warn drivers about pedestrians (lights, traffic signs,retarders....

TASKS FOR STUDENTS COULD CONTAIN

- observation in the area
- practising empathy in the area - view on the level of children,
- walking bus- attend at event for children
- street chalk and layouts for creating engaging
- appropriately-distanced zones for street games
- and physical activities (maze, race track)
- traffic study - proposal
- thinking about the creation of public spaces for children to play

Žiaci v určený čas čakajú na vyznačených zastávkach.

Stretnú sa so sprievodcom pešibusu a ostatnými žiakmi. Sprievodca je označený reflexnou vestou a nálepkou.

Spolu odchádzajú peši do školy.

O PROJEKTE PEŠIBUS

Pešibus je aktivita, ktorej cieľom je motivovať deti k pešej doprave do školy. Počas pešibusu skupinu detí vedie do školy dospelý sprievod, tzv. sprievodca autobusu. Pešibus má zastávky na rôznych trasách, ktoré sú určené podľa bydliska detí tak, aby sa vedelo zapojiť čo najviac z nich.

Ako pešibus funguje?

Žiaci v určený čas čakajú na vyznačených zastávkach.

Stretnú sa so sprievodcom pešibusu a ostatnými žiakmi. Sprievodca je označený reflexnou vestou a nálepkou.

Spolu odchádzajú peši do školy.

PROGRAM CELÝ DEŇ	PROGRAM ULICA	WORKSHOPY	PROGRAM PÓDIUM
<p>09:00 ZÁČIATOK FESTIVALU TBILISKÁ NA HRANIE</p> <p>Gastro stánky Športové aktivity Spoločenské hry Rôzne formy sedenia pre susedské stretnutia</p> <p>Vzdelávacie aktivity: OZ Znepokojené matky</p> <p>Platforma rodín detí so zdravotným znevýhodnením + Raná starostlivosť, n.o.</p> <p>Ministerstvo životného prostredia</p> <p>Dopravný podnik Bratislava</p> <p>OZ Mládež ulice</p>	<p>09:15 WORKSHOP SEBAOBHRANA DETÍ ZÁKLADNÁ OPRAVA BICYKLA</p> <p>10:00 DISKUSIA Ako sa nebať cesty do školy?</p> <p>10:00 WORKSHOP STAVANIA BUNKROV Z KARTÓNU</p> <p>11:30 BUBNOVAČKA ORCHESTRA S BUBNOVOU ŠKOLOU RYTMIKA.SK</p> <p>Spoločná bubnovačka pre deti a dospelých. Účastníci dostanú bubon a stane sa súčasťou rytmického orchestra, ktorý vedú skúsení dirigenti z bubnovej školy Rytmika.sk a kapely La3no Cubano. Orchester budeme dotvárať pesničkami, gitarou, drumblou, koncovkou atď. Netreba k tomu žiadne hudobné skúsenosti alebo špeciálny talent. Rytmus máme všetci v sebe, stačí ho objavovať.</p> <p>12:30 BÁBKOVÉ DIVADLO TRI KOCKY DROZDIA</p> <p>Marionetová dobrodružná komédia, 45 min, vhodné pre deti (aj dospelých) od 3 rokov</p>	<p>13:30 ČÍTANIE KNIH v slovenskom (30min.) a ukrajinskom jazyku (30min.)</p> <p>14:00 MODELÁRSKY WORKSHOP - MALÍ ARCHITEKTI (6-14)</p> <p>Vytváranie 3D modelov z balzy a dupla ktorými by deti chceli vyplniť svoje susedstvo. Architektka Zuzana Kapráliková bude viesť workshop, na ktorom sa deti oboznámia s technikami a materiálmi a následne môžu voľne tvoriť. Pre menšie deti bude pripravené duplo, staršie či odvážnejšie budú mať pripravené balzové drevo na lepenie a skladanie ich dizajnov.</p> <p>14:00 SPEVÁCKY ZBOR FUSION RACA</p> <p>Moderný pop-rockový spevácky zbor pre mladých od 13 do 19 rokov. Je to miesto, kde tínedžeri objavujú a rozvíjajú svoje schopnosti a talenty.</p> <p>14:40 ČÍTANIE KNIH v slovenskom (30min.) a ukrajinskom jazyku (30min.)</p> <p>15:00 QUIZZ - MINISTERSTVO ŽIVOTNÉHO PROSTREDIA</p> <p>16:00 ROLLER DISCO</p> <p>Zatancuj si a už si Tbiliskú bez áut na korčulkách :)</p> <p>17:00 KONIEC FESTIVALU TBILISKÁ NA HRANIE</p>	

Annex VI - Complete description of the Zilina pedestrian zone authentic urban challenge

Vehicle Access Restriction

Pedestrian zone authentic urban challenge

The city of Žilina

Background

- Combined circle and radial pattern of transport infrastructure
 - 3rd city circuit – main urban arteries
 - 2nd city circuit – roads circling the city center where motorized traffic is allowed
 - 1st city circuit – the historical city center with heavy VRU traffic and landmark buildings
- The area within of 1st city circuit is a mixed-use development containing residential, commercial, cultural, religious and institutional facilities

Background

- The historic city center of Zilina is a designated pedestrian zone
- car access allowed only for residents and tenants based on a permission
- until 2018 – access restrictions enforced by municipal police officers – labor-intensive & costly
- Since 2018 – hybrid manual/automated system based on retractable bollards & manual enforcement
- Mixed results after 5 years of operation – the new system partly succeeded in restricting access for non-residents, but people keep coming up with creative ways how to bypass the restrictions – car traffic in the pedestrian zone is still too heavy

The Problem

- City goal – **To decrease the vehicle traffic in the pedestrian zone**
 - How:
 - Regulate the access of the vehicles into the pedestrian zone more efficiently
 - To ensure the vehicles allowed to enter the zone use their respective parking spaces
- Some causes of the current issues:
 - Users with Disability permissions
 - New parking policy
 - National legislation allows them to park anywhere
 - No legal distinction of persons with reduced mobility for the purpose
 - Flexible definition of “inevitable time”
 - Transferable permits
 - Inefficient manual enforcement
 - too few police officers available for the task
 - low motivation

Potential solution requirements

- Long-term deployment horizon (~10 years)
- Physical restriction should be part of the solution – EU counterterrorism legislation requirement
- Enforcing both access and correct parking in the pedestrian zone
- Address the issue of reselling of transferable permits

Available data

- Traffic logs from the currently operated system
- City documents describing the current access policy
- Municipal police statistics

Potential student activities

- Analysis of data from the currently operated system and search for useful patterns
- Familiarizing with the pedestrian zone area and its entry points first using available digital tools
- Physical observation of the area and user behavior
- Analysis of technological solution requirements for the pedestrian zone area
- Discussion about potential policy interventions to align the vehicle access rules in accordance with the city goals

- 1st entrance
(Sládkovičova st.)
- 2nd entrance
(Čepiel st.)

Annex VII – Design of the certificate issued after UNIZA pilot course completion

In CITIES

UNIZA BIP course on Sustainable Mobility Innovations
Online modules: 19 February – 19 April 2024
Onsite seminar: 22 – 26 April 2024

European Commission

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This is to certify that
NAME SURNAME

has successfully completed the Blended Intensive Programme course
Sustainable Mobility Innovations
and grasped the principles of Learning by Developing, for which he/she is awarded 3 ECTS credits.

The topics addressed in this course include:

- Sustainable mobility principles
- Mobility planning & modelling
- Traffic calming in cities
- Cycling and active mobility
- Air pollution and air quality measurement
- Understanding and assessing vulnerability
- Transport as critical infrastructures
- Digital transition for safe mobility
- Cybersecurity in the smart city

Marián Gogola
Associate Professor
University of Zilina

iscte UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF LISBON

Université Gustave Eiffel

Technology Arts Sciences TH Köln

LAU REA ANMATTIKORKEAROKULU University of Applied Sciences

UNIVERSITY OF ZILINA

Annex VIII - Photograph of UNIZA pilot marketing material presented at the Digital board in UNIZA rectorate building

Annex IX - Scan of article about the InCITIES project and planned courses published in special issue of "Pravda" newspaper on 30th January 2024

Európske univerzity sa mobilizujú, aby pomohli mestám

Aby boli mestá stále dobrými miestami na život, musia v súčasnosti čeliť rôznym výzvam. Na to potrebujú odborníkov, ktorí rozumejú faktorom ovplyvňujúcim kvalitu života v meste. Ich príprava vyžaduje aj zapojenie univerzít. Ako to vyzerá v praxi? Na naše otázky odpovedal Tibor Petrov, výskumník v oblasti inteligentných dopravných systémov z univerzity v Žiline.

Ktorým najväčším výzvam čelia dnešné mestá?

Klimatické zmeny, ako aj mnohé ďalšie sociálne a ekonomické faktory, neustále zvyšujú tlak na naše mestá, aby zvyšovali svoju mieru udržateľnosti a stali sa odolnejšími pred zhoršujúcimi sa klimatickými vplyvmi a zároveň inkluzívnejšími pre všetkých svojich obyvateľov.

Aby mestá dokázali týmto výzvam úspešne čeliť, budú potrebovať kompetentných odborníkov, stratégov a projektantov, ktorí budú rozumieť širokému spektru faktorov, ovplyvňujúcich kvalitu života v meste a ich vzájomné väzby. Príprava týchto odborníkov si vyžaduje inovátné pedagogické postupy a zvýšenú mieru spolupráce medzi mestami a univerzitami.

Čo to konkrétne znamená pre Žilinskú univerzitu?

Na túto výzvu zareagovalo päť európskych univerzít združených v aliancii PIONEER. Ide o Univerzitu Gustava Eiffela (Francúzsko), Univerzitný inštitút v Lisabone (Portugalsko), Univerzitu aplikovaných vied v Kolíne (Nemecko), Univerzitu aplikovaných vied LAUREA (Fínsko) a Žilinskú univerzitu v Žiline (Slovensko). Tieto výskumno-vzdelávacie inštitúcie, ktoré spoločne vzdelávajú viac ako 70-tisíc študentov v osemnástich mestách, získali prestížny výskumný projekt financovaný zo zdrojov Európskej únie v rámci programu Horizont Európa s názvom InCITIES - Priekopnícke inkluzívne, udržateľné a odolné mestá.

Ako by ste laikom predstavili tento projekt?

Projekt InCITIES bude realizovaný po dobu troch rokov (2022-2025) a jeho cieľom je podporiť transformáciu a modernizáciu univerzít a ich ekosystémov so zameraním sa na budúce potreby miest. Transformácia sa dosiahne vzájomnou spolupracou zúčastnených inštitúcií a ich ekosystémov prostredníctvom budovania znalostných centier. Projektoví partneri vybudujú znalostné centrá zhrmaždením znalostí v rámci siedmich nosných tém - prechod miest na udržateľnú budúcnosť; príroda v mestách; energia v mestách; zraniteľnosť, inklúzia a zdravie v mestách; mobilita; prechod na digitálne technológie; udržateľné a odolné mestá.

Stretnutie riešiteľov projektu InCITIES zo Žilinskej univerzity v rámci pracovnej skupiny zameranej na formovanie stratégie pre rozvoj ľudských zdrojov vo výskume.

Na čo budú slúžiť tieto znalostné centrá?

Znalosti zhrmaždené v znalostných centrách budú využité pre vzdelávanie ďalšej generácie odborníkov v oblasti inkluzívnych, udržateľných a odolných miest. V rámci projektu budú zorganizované dva pilotné kurzy pre študentov a doktorandov. Prvý kurz s názvom „Udržateľné inovácie v mobilite“ je organizovaný na pôde Žilinskej univerzity v Žiline a začne sa v letnom semestri súčasného akademického roka. Kurz, určený pre študentov a doktorandov, bude pozostávať z deviatich on-line modulov a bude ukončený sériou seminárov, ktoré sa uskutočnia prezenčne v týždni od 22. do 26. apríla 2024. Tento, v rámci Slovenska unikátny kurz, je založený

na využití princípov inovátného pedagogického modelu „Učenie rozvíjaním“ (Learning by Developing) a bude prebiehať v anglickom jazyku. Medzinárodný tím účastníkov kurzu bude v spolupráci s lektormi zo Žilinskej univerzity a partnerských univerzít a zástupcami mesta Žilina pracovať na riešení skutočných potrieb plánovania mobility v meste. Týmto spôsobom študenti získajú praktické zručnosti a stratégie aplikovateľné pre riešenie skutočných výziev mestskej mobility, ako aj skúsenosť s prácou v medzinárodnom multidisciplinárnom tíme a profesionálne kontakty. V zimnom semestri súčasného akademického roka bude zorganizovaný druhý pilotný kurz, tentokrát na pôde Univerzitetného inštitútu v Lisabone.

Prečo je potrebná v tejto oblasti medzinárodná spolupráca?

Rozvoj inkluzívnych, udržateľných a odolných miest si vyžaduje postup-

Aby boli mestá stále dobrými miestami na život, musia v súčasnosti čeliť rôznym výzvam. Na to potrebujú odborníkov, ktorí rozumejú faktorom ovplyvňujúcim kvalitu života v meste. Ich príprava vyžaduje aj zapojenie univerzít. Ako to vyzerá v praxi? Na naše otázky odpovedal Tibor Petrov, výskumník v oblasti inteligentných dopravných systémov z univerzity v Žiline.

Ktorým najväčším výzvam čelia dnešné mestá?

Klimatické zmeny, ako aj mnohé ďalšie sociálne a ekonomické faktory, neustále zvyšujú tlak na naše mestá, aby zvyšovali svoju mieru udržateľnosti a stali sa odolnejšími pred zhoršujúcimi sa klimatickými vplyvmi a zároveň inkluzívnejšími pre všetkých svojich obyvateľov.

Aby mestá dokázali týmto výzvam úspešne čeliť, budú potrebovať kompetentných odborníkov, stratégov a projektantov, ktorí budú rozumieť širokému spektru faktorov, ovplyvňujúcich kvalitu života v meste a ich vzájomné väzby. Príprava týchto odborníkov si vyžaduje inovatívne pedagogické postupy a zvýšenú mieru spolupráce medzi mestami a univerzitami.

Čo to konkrétne znamená pre Žilinskú univerzitu?

Na túto výzvu zareagovalo päť európskych univerzít združených v aliancii PIONEER. Ide o Univerzitu Gustava Eiffela (Francúzsko), Univerzitný inštitút v Lisabone (Portugalsko), Univerzitu aplikovaných vied v Kolíne (Nemecko), Univerzitu aplikovaných vied LAUREA (Fínsko) a Žilinskú univerzitu v Žiline (Slovensko). Tieto výskumnovo-vzdelávacie inštitúcie, ktoré spoločne vzdelávajú viac ako 70-tisíc študentov v osemnástich mestách, získali prestížny výskumný projekt financovaný zo zdrojov Európskej únie v rámci programu Horizont Európa s názvom InCITIES - Priekopnícke inkluzívne, udržateľné a odolné mestá.

Ako by ste laikom predstavili tento projekt?

Projekt InCITIES bude realizovaný po dobu troch rokov (2022-2025) a jeho cieľom je podporiť transformáciu a modernizáciu univerzít a ich ekosystémov so zameraním sa na budúce potreby miest. Transformácia sa dosiahne vzájomnou spolupracou zúčastnených inštitúcií a ich ekosystémov prostredníctvom budovania znalostných centier. Projektoví partneri vybudujú znalostné centrá zhromaždením znalostí v rámci siedmich nosných tém - prechod miest na udržateľnú budúcnosť; príroda v mestách; energia v mestách; zdravotnosť, inklúzia a zdravie v mestách; mobilita; prechod na digitálne technológie; udržateľné a odolné mestá.

Na čo budú slúžiť tieto znalostné centrá?

Znalosti zhromaždené v znalostných centrách budú využité pre vzdelávanie ďalšej generácie odborníkov v oblasti inkluzívnych, udržateľných a odolných miest. V rámci projektu budú zorganizované dva pilotné kurzy pre študentov a doktorandov. Prvý kurz s názvom „Udržateľné inovácie v mobilite“ je organizovaný na pôde Žilinskej univerzity v Žiline a začne sa v letnom semestri súčasného akademického roka. Kurz, určený pre študentov a doktorandov, bude pozostávať z deviatich on-line modulov a bude ukončený sériou seminárov, ktoré sa uskutočnia prezenčne v týždni od 22. do 26. apríla 2024. Tento, v rámci Slovenska unikátny kurz, je založený

na využití princípov inovatívneho pedagogického modelu „Učenie rozvíjaním“ (Learning by Developing) a bude prebiehať v anglickom jazyku. Medzinárodný tím účastníkov kurzu bude v spolupráci s lektormi zo Žilinskej univerzity a partnerských univerzít a zástupcami mesta Žilina pracovať na riešení skutočných potrieb plánovania mobility v meste. Týmto spôsobom študenti získajú praktické zručnosti a stratégie aplikovateľné pre riešenie skutočných výziev mestskej mobility, ako aj skúsenosť s prácou v medzinárodnom multidisciplinárnom tíme a profesionálne kontakty. V zimnom semestri súčasného akademického roka bude zorganizovaný druhý pilotný kurz, tentokrát na pôde Univerzitného inštitútu v Lisabone.

Prečo je potrebná v tejto oblasti medzinárodná spolupráca?

Rozvoj inkluzívnych, udržateľných a odolných miest si vyžaduje postupný prechod, interdisciplinárny prístup a nové modely riadenia procesov schopných stavať na formách občianskej participácie, ktoré umožnia obyvateľom aktívne sa zapojiť do rozvoja mesta a vyjadriť svoje potreby. Rovnako si vyžaduje aj novú generáciu odborníkov, pripravených riešiť konkrétne výzvy miest. Výmenou znalostí a skúseností na medzinárodnej úrovni, ako aj nasadením inovatívnych vzdelávacích metód chcú európske univerzity pomôcť riešiť výzvy, ktorým naše mestá v súčasnosti čelia a budú čeliť v budúcnosti.

Projekt je realizovaný Oddelením medzinárodných výskumných projektov - ERAdiate+ Žilinskej univerzity v spolupráci s viacerými fakultami a Ústavom celoživotného vzdelávania.

Stretnutie riešiteľov projektu InCITIES zo Žilinskej univerzity v rámci pracovnej skupiny zameranej na formovanie stratégie pre rozvoj ľudských zdrojov vo výskume.

Projektoví partneri InCITIES projektu sa stretli v priestoroch Univerzity Gustava Eiffela v Paríži, aby diskutovali o prebiehajúcich projektových aktivitách a naplánovali realizáciu ďalších úloh.

Ktorí absolventi vysokých škôl sú na trhu práce najžiadanejší?

Annex X - Full text of email containing basic information about the UINZA Pilot course sent to all registered individuals

Dear <PARTICIPANT_NAME>,

Thank you for your interest in attending the Sustainable Mobility Innovations BIP course organised by the University of Žilina (UNIZA) in collaboration with the InCITIES project partners.

To help you answer some of the questions you might have, we would like to follow up with some practical information about the course. Please read the information carefully and **confirm if you will be able to participate in all online modules** on Wednesdays at 3pm **and travel to (and stay) in Zilina** between 22nd and 26th of April 2024.

Course schedule

The course consists of an introductory session, 9 online Modules and a full-week onsite seminar. The introductory sessions will take place on the **13th of February from 3pm to 4pm** CET and the **16th of February between 10am and 11am** CET – you can attend the session that is more convenient for you. For the next 9 weeks (starting from Wednesday 21st of February), online Modules will take place on **Wednesdays from 3pm to 5pm** CET (with some exceptions in case of holidays or instructor conflicts, where the course could be moved to Thursday at 3pm).

The onsite seminar will take place **from Monday 22nd to Friday 26th of April** at different locations in Žilina, Slovakia. The exact location and content of the classes will be shared with you in due time.

Conditions for successfully completing the course

To complete the course you are expected to **participate in online modules AND to join in person for the onsite week in Zilina** which will take place between April 22 and 26. Lunch and refreshments are included during the physical stay.

Expenses

Attending the onsite seminar has associated travel and accommodation costs, for which students can apply for ERASMUS+ **support from their own institution, or decide to pay the costs themselves**. In some cases, we may be able to support a few visiting students with accommodation and food in the case that they are not eligible for other sources of funding. Please contact us early if you need help.

Notification of accepted participants

We are very happy that the course sparked considerable interest among students. However, since the capacity of the course is limited, this means we may not be able to invite all of you. The final participants **will be informed once the application deadline is past**, just after February 7.

You can find more detailed information and [FAQ](#) about the course on [its website](#).

Please remember to reply to this email and **confirm if you are able to participate** in both the online modules AND the onsite event in April, as this is very important information for us to ensure effective organisation of the course.

Kind wishes,
The UNIZA InCITIES project team

Annex XI - Full text of invitation email sent to course participants selected to attend the UNIZA pilot course

Dear <PARTICIPANT NAME>,

It is our pleasure to invite you to the InCITIES Sustainable Mobility Innovations BIP course. The course starts the next week with the introductory sessions on **13th of February from 3pm to 4pm** CET and the **16th of February between 10am and 11am** CET – you can attend the session that is more convenient for you. Please note that the sessions will be recorded, so we would like to kindly ask you to send us your consent to record them.

The course online Modules will take place on **Wednesdays from 3pm to 5pm** CET. We will contact you in advance if a rescheduling of any of the online Modules is necessary. You can use the following link to connect to the introductory sessions and all the online Modules: <http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024>

We will use Microsoft Teams, SharePoint and other Microsoft Office 365 tools as a platform for the course online activities. To access all the required functionality, you will need a working installation of Microsoft Teams. If you don't have it already, please refer to the following [guide on how to get Microsoft Teams for free](#). We prepared a [shared folder](#) where you can find course-related materials. Before every online Module, make sure to check the respective folder, as we will upload preparatory materials for you there.

We would like to kindly ask you to complete the following [personality test](#) to aid us with constructing efficient teams for the course: <https://forms.office.com/e/3eM9w7gSeC>
Please, complete the test by Sunday, 11 February 23:59 CET. It will take you approximately 5 minutes.

If you experience any software-related difficulties, you can contact our technical support, Mr. Michal Hvizdak (michal.hvizdak@uniza.sk), who will be available online at the beginning of each online Module or by email.

We are looking forward to engaging with you soon!

Warmest regards,
The UNIZA InCITIES project team

Annex XII – Data collected through the UNIZA course registration form

- Full name*
- Email address*
- Motivation*: a short description of why the participant would like to attend the course and what experience and skills he/she hopes to gain by attending it
- Short biography*: a brief introduction of the participant to the course instructors and fellow students
- Field of study
- Study degree (Bachelor's, Master's, PhD, Other)
- University/institution
- Job title
- Gender*
- Nationality*
- Special dietary requirements
- Consent to process personal data with a brief privacy notice*

Fields marked with asterisk (*) in the registration form are mandatory.

**Annex XIII - Full list of Questions and
Answers about the UNIZA pilot course
updated until March 13th, 2024**

Welcome to **Sustainable Mobility Innovations** course! We're excited to have you join this learning experience. This Q&A section is designed to address common questions, provide support, and ensure a smooth transition into the learning environment.

1. What is the course schedule?

The course runs from week 8 (starting on Wednesday 21st of February) to week 17 (ending on Friday 26th of April) inclusively and is preceded by an introductory session. The course combines online and in-person learning.

The course introductory sessions will take place on the 13th of February from 3pm to 4pm CET and the 16th of February between 10am and 11am CET – you can attend the session that is more convenient for you.

For the first 9 weeks of the course, online Modules will take place on **Wednesdays from 3pm to 5pm** CET (with some exceptions in case of holidays or instructor conflicts, where the course could be moved to Thursday at 3pm).

The onsite seminar will take place **from Monday 22nd to Friday 26th of April** at different locations in Žilina, Slovakia. The exact location and content of the classes will be shared with you in due time.

2. What do I need to access the online part of the course?

To participate, ensure you have a reliable internet connection, and a compatible device with Microsoft Teams installed and ready to go <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-teams/download-ap>

We recommend that you take the time to reboot your computer before each course to avoid sound or camera issues, and that you connect 5 minutes before just in case.

3. How do I connect to online modules?

The link to each online Module will be the same throughout all 9 online modules: <http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024>. In case you need technical assistance please contact UNIZA InCITIES project team at circular.incities@uniza.sk or directly our technical assistant Michal Hvizdák michal.hvizdak@uniza.sk. He will be available for the beginning of each module in case of technical problems.

4. How much preparation and follow-up work is involved in the modules?

The course is set to 3 ECTS, which according to European guidelines is equivalent to 75-90 hours of work including everything. A prepared student will spend max 1h in preparation and up to 2h in follow-up team assignments after each module. Workload is split in half between the online and the onsite part of the course (approx. 37.5-45h each).

Trailblazing Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities

HORIZON EUROPE - CSA Project number: 101071330

5. What are the conditions for passing the course?

Attending is passing. We of course expect that you are active in both online and onsite activities. You should expect to present some teamwork results at least once during the course.

6. Is the course graded?

No, the course is not graded. But you will receive a certificate of successful participation for 3ECTS from the University of Žilina.

7. Can I formally transfer ECTS credits to my institution?

If a more formal credit correspondence is needed by your institution, we can issue a certificate of successful completion for the course “Transport Planning and Sustainable Mobility” by Marián Gogola, who is also instructor for module #4 on Cycling and active mobility. You can find the course [details here](#). Do let us know if you experience accreditation problems and we can try to help.

8. Is there a fee for the course?

No, there is no fee to join the course. Costs for running the course are covered by the Horizon Europe project InCITIES <https://incities.eu/>.

There is however an expectation to participate in all online modules AND to join in person for the onsite week in Žilina which will take place between April 22 and 26. Lunch and refreshments are included during the physical stay.

Attending the onsite event has travel costs, for which students can apply for ERASMUS+ support from their own institution, or decide to pay the travel cost themselves. In some cases, we may be able to support a few visiting students with accommodation and food in the case that they are not eligible to other sources of funding. Please contact us early if you need help.

9. Is there a minimum required level for the course?

The priority is given to Master’s and PhD students, however students currently pursuing a Bachelor’s degree are also welcome to apply. Applications will be evaluated based on the student’s motivation and background to join the course (these questions are asked on the application form). We aim for a good diversity in terms of background, level, country, and gender. Priority will be given to students currently enrolled by the Pioneer network of universities <https://pioneer-alliance.eu/>.

10. Can students from other fields of study than transport or mobility also apply?

Yes! We welcome and encourage a multidisciplinary approach to solve real mobility problems. Students in social sciences and humanities (SSH) are also encouraged to join.

Trailblazing Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities

HORIZON EUROPE - CSA Project number: 101071330

11. When will I know if I am accepted?

The list of participating students will be made public and students will be informed once the application deadline is past, just after February 7.

12. How to communicate with us?

You can reach out for any further questions to the course organisers at circular.incities@uniza.sk. You can also stay informed via the InCITIES [website](#), and our social media [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts. Important updates will also be sent via email throughout the course.

13. How to get to Žilina?

Further information on how to arrive in Žilina, local transport, health care and other useful facts can be found in the Welcome Guide available at this link: <https://www.uniza.sk/flexpapers/welcome-guide-inter-students/>. Vienna is the closest transport hub for both night trains and flights from many European cities (we encourage you to consider taking the train). If enough students arrive together, we may organise a direct shuttle bus from Vienna before the event (to be confirmed later).

14. Where to stay in Žilina?

We have prebooked a number of student dormitories, which can be booked for 20eur/night (the room is shared for two people and has its own bathroom). Let us know in advance if you wish to apply for a space.

We look forward to a productive and enriching learning experience. Remember, your success is our priority. Don't hesitate to reach out, and make the most of your learning journey! For any questions, comments or further support please contact us at circular.incities@uniza.sk.

Course content questions

15. How does the course address emerging innovations in sustainable mobility?

Indeed, innovations are novel by definition. The course's underlying approach to innovations is rooted in transition theory, and more particularly on transition management, where innovations are considered as a key enabler for systemic change (this theory is itself loosely based on Roger's older innovation adoption theory). This also means we do not consider innovations to be necessarily technological, they can also be policy-related, behaviour-related, etc.

However, this course is not theoretical, and although we can provide references to these key sources, there will be no time to cover them in detail. The online modules are 2h each: they will be focused on an authentic case study, a genuine problem faced by planners in Žilina, who aim to ensure a safe, pleasant and healthy environment to and around two schools in Žilina and on a specific pedestrian zone in the city centre. This means that specific mobility innovations and their impacts will be generated, proposed, and evaluated by students themselves.

16. How does the course address potential impact on urban air quality?

When considering impacts (such as air pollution or carbon emissions), the underlying frameworks are “The Four System Conditions of a Sustainable Society”, the concept of Planetary Boundaries, and the so-called “doughnut” economic model, which together form the pre-conditions and the indicators for designing societies within a minimum social floor and maximum environmental ceiling. However, the same answer applies here: the theory will be provided as references; but the focus will be on bringing solutions to a real case.

17. Could you provide more insight into the analytical framework for critical thinking mentioned in the course description?

In our course, we apply the Learning by Developing (LbD) pedagogical model which equips students with the skills required to deal with real-life situations. It demands active participation, and the co-construction of shared expertise between participants. Some of the core components of this approach are: the identification of key elements, inquiries development, evaluation of facts and evidence, data analysis, problem-solving, research, logical reasoning, and decision-making.

You can find more information here: <https://www.laurea.fi/en/laurea/laurea-as-a-university/learning-by-developing-lbd/>

Annex XIV - Detailed plan of UNIZA pilot briefing session and course online modules

Briefing session				
<p>Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).</p> <p>How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?</p> <p><i>(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)</i></p>				
Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).	Yannick	
10 minutes	Welcome speech by Vice-rector		Jozef Ristvej	
10 minutes	Introduction to BIP course (1)	-UNIZA + introductory context + course (Dana for 10 minutes)	Dana	
	Introduction to BIP course (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How was the course developed, what are the ISR challenges / IncITIES goals and principles / LbD approach, what's new with this course / real case studies - Topics that will be covered, structure and schedule -Teachers involved (have a slide with a short bio for all instructors) and universities -Modules and structure 	Dana/Christina	Ask questions in the chat

5 minutes	Emotion forecast	Participants will select one of the emotions listed in the Slido	Christina	https://app.sli.do/event/avWgXNFRz9chCJBf9ZZgqk/embed/polls/b9eb65e2-a0bc-421c-af54-8ef3a3338faa
7 minutes		Present groups of Personality test	Albert	
12 minutes	Get-to-know each other	3-4 breakout rooms, one per instructor; instructor takes notes but no need to report to the group. Give the floor to all students	Each instructor joins one room (3), and report	In 1min, introduce yourself briefly (first name, country, education/work) and explain your expectations/motivation for the course
10 minutes	Q&A	<p>Discuss Questions received from students so far (Q&A document) and any new in the chat</p> <p>Logistics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -upload in advance the exercises for students to present 1-2 weeks ahead of the module -Evaluation of the course - Tools we will use, sharing access to reading material, drive - Conditions to pass the course: be present in person April 22-26; prepare one group presentation (for one of the 8 modules with homework) -Admin, accommodation, travel, funding 	Tibor	

Module 1 – Sustainable Mobility Principles

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	Wednesday 21st of February 2024, 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Yannick Cornet, Dana Sitányiová, Christina Georgouli
HELPER <i>to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, timekeeper</i>	Christina Georgouli
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS <i>if any</i>	Sanna Ketonen-Oksi
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p><i>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1.</i></p> <p><i>Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed.</i></p> <p><i>A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</i></p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: <i>What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of what sustainability means and how it applies to mobility • Practice with future envisioning as a tool to plan sustainability
Soft skills: <i>What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?</i>	
Attitudes: <i>What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.</i>	
Mindset: <i>How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?</i>	
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
<i>What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?</i>	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material <i>to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IPCC → Check the carbon budget table on p29 of the IPCC report Summary for Policy Makers. Can you find out on which date the carbon budget for an 83% chance to stay below 1.5C will be used up, at the current average yearly global emission rates? 2. EEA Transport and Mobility https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in

	<p>-depth/transport-and-mobility → What is the % of transport-related carbon emissions in your country?</p> <p>3. UMii-report-2021 → can you give examples of each type of Sustainable Urban Mobility Innovation (see pages 22-23 for a description of the types)</p> <p>4. Watch this video https://www.naturalstep.ca/backcasting</p> <p>5. Inayatullah (2013) Futures Studies theories and methods → What are the different types of benefits the article brings forth about futures studies and foresight?</p>
<p>Additional material for further reading</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ahmed, Stopher - 2014 - Seventy Minutes Plus or Minus 10 – A Review of Travel Time Budget Studies • Banister - 2008 - The sustainable mobility paradigm • Cornet et al. - 2021 - Worthwhile travel time a conceptual framework of the perceived value of enjoyment, productivity and fitness while travelling • EIT-UrbanMobilityNext9_±15-Minute City: Human-centred planning in action • Geels - 2005 - The dynamics of transitions in socio-technical systems: A multi-level analysis of the transition pathway from horse-drawn carriages to automobiles (1860-1930) • McKay et al. - 2022 - Exceeding 1.5°C global warming could trigger multiple climate tipping points • Ryghaug et al. - 2023 - A Social Sciences and Humanities research agenda for transport and mobility in Europe: key themes and 100 research questions • Steffen et al. - 2018 - Trajectories of the Earth System in the Anthropocene

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).	Christina	
10 min	Small exercise	Brainstorming exercise using Slido 3 questions ~2 minutes per question Groups presentation	Christina	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To keep the environment safe for humans, when should we reach net zero carbon emissions? 2. Which mode of transport do you consider the most sustainable? 3. What is the percentage of women working in the transport sector?
25 minutes	Sustainable Mobility Principles	Setting the stage - sustainable development – definition(s) - Co2 data – where we are - SDGs and IDGs - Sustainable mobility innovations (not only technologies, avoid-shift-improve)	Yannick	
15 minutes	Transportation in Zilina	Existing situation/context of Zilina i.e. urban mobility/master plan, traffic patterns, trends or construction plans	Dana	
5 minutes	Break			
15 minutes	Group exercise: Futures thinking, forecasting and	Focus on letting Futures thinking principles emerge from an exercise on a future vision. Students will use a Whiteboards to create a virtual collage with text of either a future based	Yannick Sanna Christina	Backcasts groups 1&4 (Yannick + Sanna) Spend a couple of minutes by yourself, write a few post-its, then share your ideas with

	<p>backcasting exercise</p>	<p>on current trends (future forecast) or a future based on a positive vision (future vision).</p> <p>Students will be divided in 4 groups / 2 for each approach. Each instructor enters the whiteboard area and presents the exercise (2-3 minutes) – 1 instructor per group</p>	<p>the group and add any new post-its that come up:</p> <p>1) Define a future vision of sustainable mobility in Zilina for 2030 and beyond. Put yourself into the future and describe your preferred, desirable, sustainable, plausible future as if it had already been accomplished. Be sure to propose a vision that breaks with current trends</p> <p>2) Explain your societal assumptions for the vision.</p> <p>Be creative, engage in a level of ‘utopian thinking’. Be as comprehensive as possible i.e. cover different modes and needs, including what the city will look like. Put your ideas on post-its (one idea per post-it).</p> <p>Pick one person in the group who will SHORTLY (3min per group) present the vision of their group to the class</p> <p>Forecasts groups 2&3 (Dana + Christina) Spend a couple of minutes by yourself, write a few post-its, then share your ideas with the group and add any new post-its that come up:</p> <p>1) Make some assumptions about the most likely trends for Zilina according to a business-as-usual scenario: population growth, car ownership rates, mode split, urban development, parking infrastructures, technology ..</p>
--	-----------------------------	---	---

				<p>2) Produce a likely future forecast scenario based on these current trends for Zilina 2030 and beyond.</p> <p>Be realistic, consider most likely trends and explain your assumptions. Be as comprehensive as possible i.e. cover different modes and needs, including what the city will look like.</p> <p>Put your ideas on post-its (one idea per post-it)</p> <p>Distinguish between descriptions of the future scenario and its assumptions on the board. Pick one person in the group who will SHORTLY (3min per group) present the future scenario of their group to the class.</p>
15 minutes	Presentation of findings	Presentation by groups of their Whiteboard/discussion		
20 minutes (15+5 for questions)	Futures thinking for transforming: the concept and food for thought	<p>Presentation with ppt slides</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different timelines and approaches • Futures cone • Some examples of transformative thinking • Cognitive biases (with examples) >> IDGs <p>Definition of futures consciousness</p>	Sanna Ketonen-Oksi	The idea is to inform the students of the fallacies that may appear in their thinking about futures, including the used data, and to encourage them to think how they could improve their futures consciousness
10 minutes (5+5 for questions)	Presentation of assignment for the next Module	Starting the course on the following week, group(s) will present 1-2 slides	Yannick	In a slide or two, please list all the pros and cons of the electric car as a replacement to conventional cars and become the primary mode of transport worldwide
30 minutes (optional)	Optional time for questions/discussion			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module *common to all modules*

1. Attending is passing
2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules

Module feedback

<https://forms.gle/nHrwn8osrFbP4or6A>

Module 2 – Mobility planning and modelling

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 28 FEBRUARY 3-5PM
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Marek Drliciak, with help from Dana Sitanyova
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
HELPER <i>to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, timekeeper</i>	one PhD student tbc
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS <i>if any</i>	Not applicable
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: <i>What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?</i>	Design methods that identify traffic problems in the territory using a data collection system, identify areas necessary for the creation of a traffic model, analyze input and output data of the model and define working scenarios for solutions in projects
Soft skills: <i>What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?</i>	Team work, collaboration, problems solving, story telling, public speaking
Attitudes: <i>What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.</i>	Comprehensive evaluation, goal settings and mindfulness of ideas/designs
Mindset: <i>How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?</i>	Through the interaction of teaching, students will be guided to the professional expression of their own solutions with the provision of constant feedback. Ideas will be analyzed with the aim of promoting creativity.
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	

What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?

Preparatory / reading / viewing material to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.

1. Urban mobility plan for Zilina (translated summary?) https://zilina.sk/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/akcny_plan_mobility_zilina_final-1.pdf
2. One Excel file with all needed data (e.g. three sheets): mobility and radar surveys, UHA traffic count, parents survey results

.. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344630009_TRANSPORT_PLANNING_MODELS

4. Juan de Dios Ortuzar ´, Luis G. Willumsen, MODELLING TRANSPORT, <https://dl.thep.ir/Book/TransportationPlanning/Modelling%20Transport.pdf>

Videos:

5. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h2rxC-OrZLU&list=PLLXj22DZPPaABmryrJ39kY0bcc0oZssmv&index=2>

Additional material for further reading

<https://worldwidescience.org/topicpages/t/transportation+planning+models.html>

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up <i>(turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly).</i>	Christina	
25 min	Assignments presentations	2 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	Yannick	
20 min	Case study presentation	Presentation by UHA: case study, traffic counting + survey results	UHA Bronislava	
5 min	Break			
10 min	Intro to modelling	Brainstorming about what is mobility planning: 1 st tool is master plan/urban plan and traffic input/output data	Marek	Common discussion OR quick survey tool e.g. https://www.slido.com/
10 min	Theory	Part 1 basic theory on modelling and spatial planning, main types of traffic models, why we need them	Marek	
10 min	Theory	Part 2: Zilina model based on mobility survey, eg we use this model for problems as in Vlcince	Marek	
20 min	Defining the problem	Define 5 main areas/results, allocate each area to each team: data (surveys) and how to use this data for traffic planning and modelling; what data do we need? Outcome: model-based planning (model feeds results to master plan). Report.	Marek	Prepare a traffic surveys for this area (what type of survys we need, using new types of data e.g. mobile operator, statistics office – students can suggest). e.g. data from radars we need for Work in groups during the course. Each group will be

		Divide in groups; discuss the problem; must use the traffic master plan or sustainable urban mobility plan; need knowledge about traffic behaviour.		<p>assigned an area (e.g. passenger transport). Students in groups must prepare a proposal for a traffic analysis of the given transport. Students will design a traffic survey and explain the meaning and method of incorporating specific data.</p> <p>Students should move smoothly to proposals for calming traffic in the area. (next course). For example, creating scenarios for short-term and long-term planning. New ways of collecting data.</p>
10 min	Presentation of assignment for the next module	Within one group, students evaluate 2 tasks that are given in the form of a questionnaire. In the first task, students will compare traffic planning in their cities, and in the second task, they will identify specific problems in the Zilina case study (Presentation with a maximum of four slides.).		
	Wrap-up			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 3 – Traffic calming in cities

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 6 MARCH 2024 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Matus Kovac
HELPER to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, <i>timekeeper</i>	
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS if any	
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?	Traffic calming measures
Soft skills: What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?	
Attitudes: What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.	
Mindset: How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?	
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.	1. Map of the area, link for Google street view to look around the two schools https://sk.mapy.cz/zakladni?x=18.7629455&y=49.2114483&z=17 https://www.google.com/maps/@49.212843,18.7662432,17.5z?entry=ttu Primary and nursery school of Saint Gorazd https://sk.mapy.cz/zakladni?x=18.7602499&y=49.2145005&z=18

	<p>https://www.google.com/maps/@49.2157467,18.7629336,18.5z?entry=ttu</p> <p>Primary school Martinská https://sk.mapy.cz/zakladni?x=18.7685593&y=49.2096364&z=18 https://www.google.com/maps/@49.2104125,18.7709222,3a,89.8y,83.49h,88.5t/data=!3m6!1e1!3m4!1sHZvg6zEk7o7aQpEnWTEsXw!2e0!7i16384!8i8192?entry=ttu</p> <p>2. Design guide example City of Sparks – Guidelines for Traffic Calming https://cms7files1.revize.com/sparksnv/Document_Center/Department/Engineering%20Services/Transportation%20and%20Traffic%20Engineering/traffic-calming-guidelines.pdf</p> <p>3. UHA – Safe and Sustainable Access to Schools – use case material</p>
<p>Additional material for further reading</p>	<p>4. Distefano, N, Leonardi S.: Evaluation of the Benefits of Traffic Calming on Vehicle Speed Reduction https://www.hrpub.org/download/20190630/CEA3-14813151.pdf</p> <p>5. Gonzalo-Orden: Traffic Calming Measures and their Effect on the Variation of Speed https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S235214651630802X</p> <p>6. Vaitkus, A et al. Traffic Calming Measures: An Evaluation of the Effect on Driving Speed https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319675836_Traffic_Calming_Measures_An_Evaluation_of_the_Effect_on_Driving_Speed</p> <p>7. Chimba, D. Simulating the Impact of Traffic Calming Strategies https://wmich.edu/sites/default/files/attachments/u883/2019/TRCLC_RR_17-10_0.pdf</p> <p>8. FHWA COURSE ON BICYCLE AND PEDESTRIAN TRANSPORTATION, Less 11. https://safety.fhwa.dot.gov/ped_bike/univcourse/pdf/swless11.pdf</p>

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).		
25 min	Assignments presentations	2 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	Marek Drliciak	
5 min	Brainstorming	What is it, why do we do it? What would you do to calm the traffic down?	Matus	Discussion
20 min	Lecture on road design principles and measures	Introduction to Street Design and Traffic Calming <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification of roads and streets • Definition of traffic calming • What is a street? • What is a Traffic calming • Objectives of traffic calming • Process of Designing Traffic Calming Measures in Cities • Guiding Principles 	Matus	
5 min	Break			
10 min	Case study – Location inspection Kids perspective	Review the localization in more detail, critical points e.g. four lanes, where crosswalks are, look at it from the perspective of traffic calming What ways are there to improve the two schools access	Matus Dana	Map, photos, street view Group thinking in breakout rooms. Find critical points, think about street design ideas to improve the situation

20 min	Lecture on real-life traffic measures	Traffic Calming Techniques <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness Measures • Vertical Deflection Tools • Horizontal Deflection Tools • Diversion Measures • Successful implementations in various urban settings. • Challenges and barriers to implementation. • Applicability of traffic calming measures 	Matus Dana	
20 min	Traffic Calming design exercise	For the map exercise, select appropriate measures based on the problems that need to be addressed in the area. The goal is to achieve 'safe and sustainable access to school.	Matus Dana	Assignment: finalise a group solution to share;
10 min	Presentation of assignment for the next module		Matus Dana	Draw the traffic calming measures you propose onto the map of the neighborhood. You may use SketchUp, Photoshop, AutoCAD, or any other software for this purpose

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 4 – Cycling and active mobility

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 13 MARCH 2024 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Marian Gogola
HELPER <i>to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, timekeeper</i>	TBD
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS <i>if any</i>	Not applicable
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: <i>What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?</i>	Design principles of active sustainable mobility, Analyse the problems from perspective of various target groups, analysing of solved area, reading the technical documents, maps, data analyse, numerical skills,
Soft skills: <i>What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?</i>	Team work, collaboration, problems solving, story telling, public speaking
Attitudes: <i>What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.</i>	Goal settings and mindfulness of ideas/designs
Mindset: <i>How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?</i>	Make sure the students understand and give feedback from them. Support them in development of own ideas
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
<i>What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?</i>	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material <i>to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of</i>	Articles: Hussein Mahfouz, Robin Lovelace, Elsa Arcaute,

<p><i>a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.</i></p>	<p>A road segment prioritization approach for cycling infrastructure, Journal of Transport Geography, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2023.103715</p> <p>Juan P. Ospina, Juan C. Duque, Verónica Botero-Fernández, Mark Brussel, Understanding the effect of sociodemographic, natural and built environment factors on cycling accessibility, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103386</p> <p>Yiyang Yang et al. Towards a cycling-friendly city: An updated review of the associations between built environment and cycling behaviors (2007–2017), https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2019.100613.</p> <p>Clare Hume et al. Walking and Cycling to School: Predictors of Increases Among Children and Adolescents, American Journal of Preventive Medicine, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2008.10.011.</p> <p>Videos: Universal design principles- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8mh-GTlvf0w 5 design principles for bicycle infrastructure – videos from Dutch cycling embassy (https://youtu.be/A2kg-FviR5M?si=R1oQG3DULPETI6vS)</p>
<p>Additional material <i>for further reading</i></p>	<p>https://dtvcapacitybuilding.com/blog/5-design-principles-for-successful-bicycle-infrastructure/ https://brtguide.itdp.org/branch/master/guide/pedestrian-access/principles-of-pedestrian-planning https://safety.fhwa.dot.gov/PED_BIKE/univcourse/pdf/swless03.pdf https://globaldesigningcities.org/</p>

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).	Christina	
15 min	Assignments presentations	2 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	Matus Kovac or Marian	Based on the principles of traffic calming implement
45 min	Lecture	Role of active mobility in urban environment Different requirements of different groups (children's, students, parents, handicapped, etc.) Transport infrastructure typology, public space and their limitations Principles of designing a network, factors of attractiveness, show bad or wrong examples, User experience vs. design	Marian	Discussion and engaging students within topic, short survey about the students travel behaviour
-- min				
5 min	Break			
45 min	Working on the case study	Sum up the situation for cyclists/pedestrian and built environment Explain what to do, what is needed to focus on Prepare DRAFT for enhancing the situation for cyclists, scooters or pedestrians on either Gorazda or Martinska school. Deliver what the land use can look like, how they	Marian + helper	Breakout rooms by team: offer various options 1) use GIS, Streetmix.eu (we provide the maps) or use simple hand-writing on the map 2) use MIRO or MS Whiteboard (draw on top of a map) 3) draw it as they can. This will be used as input to the main week where they can revise their plans

		would play with the width of the street (build or not bike lane, traffic calming measures).		
-- min				
10 min	Presentation of assignment for the next module	Continuation/finalising what was started during the class.	Marian	Students can compare Gorazda (traffic calming) and Martinska (cyclists or active mobility) – compete among the teams and Mutual evaluation of the outputs by students; vote on best project (the one or two teams with top votes present)
	Wrap-up			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 5 – Air pollution and air quality management

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 20 March 2024 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Dusan Jandacka
HELPER <i>to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, timekeeper</i>	Dana Sitanyiova
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS <i>if any</i>	
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
<p>Knowledge / hard skills: <i>What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?</i></p>	<p>Students will get information about the environment – air:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - basic information about the environment in which we live and breathe, while clean air is essential for our survival, - students will have knowledge about air pollution, sources of pollution and the consequences that air pollution causes, - further, students will gain knowledge about the origin of air pollution monitoring and modeling of emissions produced by sources and immissions that spread in the breathing zone of the population, - they will be able to use various options and design an environmentally friendly arrangement of the traffic space - last but not least, students will gain awareness of the possibilities of reducing air pollution or its

	elimination in order to maintain a quality environment for future generations
Soft skills: <i>What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?</i>	Team work, collaboration, problems solving, story telling, public speaking, environmental decision-making in the design process
Attitudes: <i>What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.</i>	Goal settings, environmental friendly thinking and solutions
Mindset: <i>How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?</i>	Through the interaction of teaching, students will be guided to the professional expression of their own solutions with the provision of constant feedback. Ideas will be analyzed with the aim of promoting creativity. Individual approach and feeling will be linked with a professional solution.
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
<i>What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?</i>	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jandacka, D.; Durcanska, D. Seasonal Variation, Chemical Composition, and PMF-Derived Sources Identification of Traffic-Related PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM_{2.5-10} in the Air Quality Management Region of Žilina, Slovakia. <i>Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health</i> 2021, <i>18</i>, 10191. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph181910191 2. https://www.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/AIR-TRITIA.html 3. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tlurKqa_78M 4. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3PxaPC2cOFE 5. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cXYbs7CRyiM 6. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8FS_h6pluRXo
Additional material for further reading	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. https://www.eea.europa.eu/ 8. https://www.epa.gov/ 9. https://www.epa.gov/pm-pollution

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).		
25 min	Assignments presentations	4 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	Marian Gogola	
20 min	Lecture on air pollution, measuring air pollution, and pollution problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Air pollution/ Air pollution does not have borders – sources of air pollution, air pollutants o Measurement and monitoring of air pollution o Sensor network as a tool for getting information about actual status of air pollution (Zilina has 8 stations city + 5 uniza) 	Dusan	
10 min	Introductory exercise	What about air quality in your city? Raise awareness about air pollution around us.	Dusan	<p>Exercise in the groups based on the cities that they choose: present air pollution situation in these cities.</p> <p>Description: During the previous presentation the students will gain an overview of sensor networks which are in place in Europe and worldwide used to monitor and assess the air quality. In this group exercise, the students will choose a city and will use the available tools</p>

				to check the current levels of pollutants in the selected city. Their next task is to interpret those readings in terms of their meaning for air quality and discuss their potential health impacts.
5 min	Break			
15 min		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Road transport as a source of air pollution (summary of mobility-related air pollution and the role of mobility in air pollution) o Health effects of air pollution - the most sensitive groups o Environmental impacts of air pollution 	<i>Aurelie</i>	
15 min	Lecture on road traffic related air pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Possibilities for reduce air pollution from road transport o Modelling of air pollution – emission and dispersion of air pollutants 	<i>Dusan</i>	Check the recommend materials – videos related air pollution
15 min	Presentation of home assignment & Group work	<p>Example of modelling air pollution from road traffic – how can influence different parameters production and dispersion air pollution (different air pollutants).</p> <p>Try to understand which parameters we need for calculate the impact of road transport on environment and air pollution and which we need to change to make better air quality.</p> <p>Change base traffic model and create new ‘variant’ include new traffic calming scenarios. Use and add different options and combine them for less air pollution situation.</p>	<i>Dusan</i>	<p>Students can use case study in Žilina as a zero variant for their ideas.</p> <p>Or, they can use any really situation in other cities for application of principles for making better air quality.</p> <p>Students should prepare the plan of changes in chosen situation – sketch and description of changes.</p> <p>Description:</p> <p>The students will combine the tools and methods they learned during this and the previous modules to suggest infrastructural and urban planning measures (e.g. traffic calming, interventions to support shift to active modes, urban greening, etc.) in order to improve the air quality in the Vlcince case study area. Students are welcome to prepare not only textual description, but, depending on their abilities, also visualizations of the</p>

				proposed interventions on a map/street view photos. All groups will share the same assignment. Presenters from each group will present the solutions their group proposes during the next module.
5 min	Discussion of home assignment		<i>Dusan</i>	
5 min	Wrap-up			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 6 – Understanding and assessing vulnerability

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 27/03/2024 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Michal Titko
HELPER <i>to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, timekeeper</i>	Maria Luskova
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS <i>if any</i>	-
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: <i>What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?</i>	Students will be able to identify relevant adaptation measures to the hazards in specific area.
Soft skills: <i>What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?</i>	Team work, collaboration, problems solving, public speaking
Attitudes: <i>What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.</i>	Comprehensive evaluation, goal settings and mindfulness of ideas/designs
Mindset: <i>How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?</i>	Feedback to the proposals of students, discussion of their proposed solutions, supporting creativity and engagement of students.
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
<p><i>What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?</i></p>	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material <i>to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strategy and action plan for adaptation to the adverse consequences of climate change in the territory of the city of Žilina [Stratégia a akčný plán adaptácie na nepriaznivé dôsledky zmeny klímy na území mesta Žilina].

	<p>https://zilina.sk/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/26.-Adaptacny-plan-zmena-klimy.pdf Translated summary.</p> <p>2. Birkmann, J. (Ed.): Measuring Vulnerability to Natural Hazards. Towards Disaster Resilient Societies, Tokyo: United Nations University Press, 2013, pp. 109-126. Available at: https://collections.unu.edu/eserv/UNU:2880/n9789280812022_text.pdf (especially article p. 277). DOI: 10.26552/com.C.2018.2.62-67</p> <p>3. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1pSoQXgnn5s (4:44)</p> <p>4. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e6MCq3kt_YI (2:21)</p>
<p>Additional material for further reading</p>	<p>5. Eklund, G., Sibilía, A., Salvi, A., Antofie, T-E., Rodomonti, D., Salari, S., Poljansek, K., Marzi, S., Gyenes, Z., Corbane, C., Towards a European wide vulnerability framework, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/353889, JRC118850</p> <p>6. Eklund, G., Sibilía A., Salvi A., Antofie T-E., Rodomonti D., Salari S., Corbane C., Pal J., Melchiorri M., Vulnerability to Disasters in Europe, Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre, European Commission, 2022, https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub#/vulnerability-in-europe</p>

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).		
25 min	Assignments presentations	Presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	<i>Previous module instructor</i>	
25 min	Lecture	Introduction to topic of vulnerability (Presentation with ppt slides) - Explanation of vulnerability – definition of vulnerability, dimensions of vulnerability and types of vulnerability. - Introduction to vulnerability assessment – How to measure vulnerability? - Explanation of the current state of climate change vulnerability of the city of Žilina (vulnerability to heat waves, vulnerability to drought, vulnerability to the flash floods).	Michal Titko	Probably questions from students.
5 min	Break			
10 min	Explanation of the task for students	How to reduce vulnerability in the city? Students will asked to work on the proposal of measures to reduce vulnerability in the city of Žilina with focus on close surrounding of schools Sv. Gorazda and Martinská. Students will receive a description of various measures that have already been applied or may be applied. Students will	Michal Titko	Students will be provided by several examples of adaptation measures which could be relevant for the city of Žilina, another cities or its part.

		consider their implementation around the given schools. They also will be asked to look for and propose completely new measures that would help the fight against the effects of climate change in this area in future.		
35 min	Working on the proposal	Working on the proposal of adaptation measures related to the close surrounding of schools Sv. Gorazda and Martinská: - What measures can help reduce vulnerability in this area? - What measures can enhance resilience of people (e.g teachers, students) in this area? - What measures can support safe and sustainable mobility?	Michal Titko + Maria Luskova	Breakout rooms by team. Incorporating students' opinion into adaptation plan to the adverse consequences of climate change.
10 min	Discussion	Discussion of the first drafts and feedback for students.	Michal Titko	
5 min	Presentation of assignment for the next module	Instructions for completing the started task for next week.	Michal Titko	
	Wrap-up			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 7 – Transport as critical infrastructure sector

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 03.04.2024 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Maria Luskova
HELPER to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, <i>timekeeper</i>	Michal Titko
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS if any	
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER –Understandin ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?	Understanding what is critical infrastructure, which entities are critical and how to increase their resilience.
Soft skills: What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?	Problem solving, ability to communicate, creativity, team work and flexibility.
Attitudes: What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.	conscious learning, active involvement
Mindset: How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?	on the basis of feedback from students in terms of understanding the given issue
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> video: Do you know what a critical infrastructure is? https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=byZaR6WbIfU DIRECTIVE (EU) 2022/2557 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 14 December 2022 on the

	<p>resilience of critical entities and repealing Council Directive 2008/114/EC https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/SK/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2557</p> <p>3. David Rehak, Martin Hromada: Failures in a Critical Infrastructure system DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.70446 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325048978 Failures in a Critical Infrastructure System</p> <p>4. Vidrikova, D. et al. Critical Infrastructure and Integrated Protection. Ostrava, CR. The Association of Fire and Safety Engineering, 2017. 174p. ISBN 978-80-7385-190-3.</p>
Additional material for further reading	5. ..

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).		
25 min	Assignments presentations	2 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	<i>Previous module instructor</i>	
30 min	Lecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal environment of Critical Infrastructure • Explanation of basic terms • Resilience measures of critical entities • Critical entities sectors • Risk assessment process 	Maria Luskova	
5 min	Break			
15	Working on the case study Risk assessment of Zilina bus station – a potential element of critical infrastructure (teacher)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Characteristics of the Žilina bus station, basic data – Basic structure – Current protection of the bus station – Source materials for the identification of the risks of the Zilina bus station: natural and climatic risks, technical and technological risks. 	Maria Luskova	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NstmXyGMJDg

35 min	Working on the case study Risk assessment of Zilina bus station – a potential element of critical infrastructure (students)	<p>Based on the source materials students will carry out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk identification of the bus station with focus on natural risks related to climate change, technical and technological risks. • Risk analysis – determining the size of the risk based on probability and impact. • Risk evaluation - comparison of the level of risk found during the analysis process with the risk criteria, use of the risk matrix. 	Maria Luskova + Michal Titko	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students divided into groups think and discuss about other risks, especially natural risks related to climate change and technical risks, perform their analysis and evaluation. - Used methods: brainstorming,
-- min				
5 min	Presentation of assignment for the next module	Instructions for elaboration assignment related to propose measures for treatment of unacceptable and undesirable risks.	Maria Luskova	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on the identified, analysed and evaluated risks within the case study students will prepare proposal of measures for risk treatment related to unacceptable and undesirable risks.
	Wrap-up			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 8 – Digital transition for safe mobility

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 10 APRIL 3-5PM
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Tibor Petrov
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
HELPER <i>to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, timekeeper</i>	Christina or Yannick
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS <i>if any</i>	City of Zilina – Lubos Slebodnik
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
<p>Knowledge / hard skills: <i>What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understanding of the basic concepts of how digital technologies impact transport safety; • understanding of a basic architecture of ITS systems • overview of digital technologies used in road transport to increase traffic safety with the focus on access restriction/pedestrian zone; • overview of advantages and disadvantages of ITS solutions for vehicle access restriction • overview of the risks associated with the digital solutions in transport – a wider perspective – risk of rebound in the case of Avs, limits of the V2X communication, cybersecurity and privacy considerations
<p>Soft skills: <i>What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teamwork and team communication by brainstorming and idea generation
<p>Attitudes: <i>What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thinking in wider context

<p>Mindset: <i>How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?</i></p>	
<p>3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES</p>	
<p><i>What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?</i></p>	
<p>Preparatory / reading / viewing material to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Map and StreetView photos of Zilina city center 2. Data related to the ITS case study 3. Background info about ITS 4. Intro to ITS 5. ITS explained 6. CAPITAL Webinar on ITS & C-ITS online training courses (3:53-14:13)
<p>Additional material for further reading</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7.

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).	Tibor	
25 min	Assignments presentations	2 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	Instructors from the previous module	
5-min	Group activity	Guessing the road safety statistics: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is the average number of road fatalities in EU per million inhabitants? 2. What was the number of road accidents in EU resulting in injuries or death in 2021? 3. What is the estimated annual socio-economic cost of road transport accidents in EU? 	Tibor	Slido.com poll
10 min	Presentation 1	Introduction of basic traffic safety statistics, causes behind them and the interventions proposed by the EU, digital technologies as a support for safe mobility	Tibor	
10 min	Case study presentation	Presentation by the city of Zilina: case study, city goals, current solution and reasons for its inadequacy, data	city of Zilina - Lubos	
5 min	Break			

10 min	Group activity	Brainstorming about how can regulating vehicle access impact traffic safety in the area (both positive and negative)	Tibor	Common discussion OR Whiteboard
15 min	Presentation 2	Overview of technological solutions used to increase road safety, focus on restricting access of vehicles to pedestrian zone	Tibor	
20 min	Defining the problem	<p>Based on the city's challenge, the idea is to come up with the solutions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify the city challenge – discuss what can be done about it? 2. Research ITS solutions and their pros/cons – group activity 3. Solutions already applied in other cities – group activity 4. Explore data and decide what to include in further discussions <p>Create 4 teams and assign partial problems: Team 1: analysis of technological solutions for restricting vehicle access into a predefined zone including pros and cons analysis – (find solutions applicable to the city of Zilina, think about their pros and cons in terms of price, security, installation difficulty, etc.) Team 2: analysis of the goals defined by the city and definition of access rules to support those goals Team 3: definition of the requirements for the potential technological solution based on the pre-defined access rules Team 4: Proposal of technological solution and estimation of its impact on the defined city goals</p> <p>Outcome: short presentation of key findings</p>	Tibor	Whiteboard – prepare already the background information, e.g. the city goals and what is required from the students
5 min		Presentation of the data		

10 min	Presentation of assignment	<p>Do some research and prepare a presentation of what are the benefits and risks associated with the restricting access in the part of a city in the wider context. Are there synergies with what they already learned up to now? (opportunity to reflect on the course and reinforce the recently acquired knowledge), what are the city needs?</p> <p>Think of the risks and opportunities associated with different ITS solutions.</p> <p>Research, if there are similar measures taken in their home cities, how they are implemented and gauge if, based on what they've seen so far, Zilina could benefit from them as well.</p> <p>Play with the data and try to come up with some interesting insights – USE SOME EXAMPLE QUESTIONS HERE, e.g., “Imagine, you are an urban/transport planner – what would you discuss with the city, which data is important?”</p>		
	Wrap-up			

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Module 9 – Cybersecurity in the smart city

Module organisation: Case study with authentic challenge; groups of 5-6 are created for the whole duration of the course; students are asked to contribute to the case study from each module's perspective; minimum 15 foreign students and up to 15 UNIZA students = 30 students maximum.

1. MODULE DETAILS	
WHEN	WEDNESDAY 17th April 2024 3-5pm
WHERE	Teams: http://bit.ly/incities-course-2024
LECTURERS/INSTRUCTORS	Peter Vestenický, Peter Holečko
HELPER to answer questions in the chat or organise data and tools, <i>timekeeper</i>	Christina Georgouli
INCITIES EXTERNAL PARTNER(S) CONTRIBUTORS if any	
2. KEY LEARNING OUTCOME DESCRIPTION	
<p>Use the SMART strategy and Syntax from the principle 1. Learning outcomes must be Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timed. A very efficient syntax of the outcome is: LEARNER – ACTIVITY – CONTEXT – WHAT AND HOW</p>	
Knowledge / hard skills: What knowledge/facts/information/data will be acquired by the students by your methods?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of what the basic principles of cybersecurity mean and how it applies to smart cities • Practice cybersecurity analysis tools to meet the hacker and administrator techniques
Soft skills: What soft skills will be developed by means of your methods and activities?	Team work, active hearing, critical thinking, creativity
Attitudes: What attitude do you plan to pay attention to? For example, self-awareness, positive thinking, conscious learning, goal setting, mindfulness, etc.	Conscious learning based on presented knowledge, setting the goal of creating a secure information system, mindfulness to SW updates
Mindset: How will you pay your attention to a mental framework that influences how individuals think, feel, and act in various situations?	Students will develop critical and analytical thinking by performing experimental tasks.
3. RECOMMENDED RESOURCES	
What materials, resources and tools will they use? Which platform and its functionalities?	
Preparatory / reading / viewing material to send prior to the course, e.g. video to watch, section of a document or plan, seminal scientific article, dataset etc.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Watch this video https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nPR131wMKEo 2. What was the cost of cybercrime globally in 2023?

	<p>https://cybersecurityventures.com/cyber-crime-to-cost-the-world-8-trillion-annually-in-2023/</p> <p>3. The Evolution of the Digital Predator: Using AI to Evade Security Controls https://sansorg.egnyte.com/dl/QkeeWAI-BdW</p> <p>4. https://threatmap.checkpoint.com</p> <p>5. Watch this video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cczlpiiu42M</p>
<p>Additional material for further reading</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. https://www.cvedetails.com/2. https://overthewire.org/wargames/bandit/3. https://docs.rapid7.com/metasploit/quick-start-guide

4. APPLIED METHODS DESCRIPTION IN THE CASE STUDY

Make a list of activities and the methods applied in them, a breakdown for the 2h module (including breaks and logistics).

How will you activate and motivate the students? How will you make them get engaged actively?

(Write the names of activities planned in your module. They may follow the organization of the case study. Examples: guided discussion/frontal lecture, peer learning/buzz groups; presentations; simulations of real environment; continuing oral and/or written knowledge assessment; feedback)

Duration	Activity	Description / Method	Instructor(s)	Student Involvement / Tools / Expected Outcome
5min	Wait for attendees to log in + start recording	Agreement that the course is recorded so that students joining later can catch up (<i>turn off your camera if you don't want to be recorded; breakout rooms are not recorded by default, unless stated otherwise – these are meant to talk openly</i>).	Christina	
25 min	Assignments presentations	2 group presentations and discussion on assignment from previous module	Previous module instructor	
5 min	Break			
10 min	Small exercise	Brainstorming exercise using Slido or Mentimeter 4 questions in total (2 minutes per question)	Christina Peter H.	How many devices are online these days? What do you consider to be the biggest problems in cybersecurity? How did the increasing number of online mobile devices influence the cybersecurity? How many cybersecurity experts are still missing?
10 min	Basic terms and definitions e.g. cybersecurity	Setting the stage - cybersecurity – definition(s) - assets, vulnerabilities, threats, exploits, risks, countermeasures - techniques and tools	Peter H.	Discussing the examples Understanding the basics of cybersecurity language

10 min (5+5 for questions)	Vulnerabilities: the concept and food for thought	Presentation with ppt slides <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Types of vulnerabilities • Finding vulnerabilities • Penetration testing 	Peter H.	The idea is to inform the students of the bugs and flaws devices might have, how the attackers can exploit them and how to avoid this.
5 min	Break			
5 min		Existing situation/context of Zilina i.e. smart city, communication infrastructure, vehicles, and mobile devices	Peter H.	What vulnerabilities can be present in the technologies used and how can they be exploited
30 min	Group exercise: Nessus penetration testing tool	Introduction to penetration testing using Nessus Penetration testing of a vulnerable Metasploitable Linux server representing a smart city infrastructure server containing critical/sensitive data (identification of vehicles, devices, persons).	Peter H.	Divide the groups and ask each of them to do the following task: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scan the server using Nessus and identify the most critical vulnerabilities. 2. Try to exploit the chosen vulnerabilities to compromise the server 3. Modify or delete a specific database record or a file corresponding to a criminal activity Modify a webpage content to compromise the information provided to the public
10 min	Example for assignment: Hashcat tool	Necessity of using strong passwords	Peter V.	Example of cracking a password (stored in the file <code>/etc/shadow</code> in Linux) using the SW tool Hashcat.
5 min	Presentation of findings	Presentation by 2 groups of their Whiteboard		Presenting the results and suggesting countermeasures to avoid the most critical attacks

5. PRECONDITIONS FOR MODULE COMPLETION

When is the module efficient and how will you measure it? How will you provide students with feedback?

Condition(s) for passing the module <i>common to all modules</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attending is passing2. Presentation of home assignment as a group in one of the online Modules
Module feedback	<i>Link to survey for students to give feedback to each module</i>

Annex XV - Participant Information Sheet with Informed Consent Form

Participant Information Sheet

Sustainable Mobility Innovations BIP course

Thank you for your interest in attending the Sustainable Mobility Innovations BIP course organised by the University of Žilina (UNIZA) in collaboration with the InCITIES project partners. In order to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation and ethical standards, we would like to ask you to read this Participant Information Sheet and return the signed Informed Consent Form.

About InCITIES project

The InCITIES project aims to achieve the transformations of HEIs and their surrounding ecosystem centred around on cities' needs of inclusion, sustainability and resilience. Its specific focus on widening countries (Portugal and Slovakia) will allow to overcome structural, sociocultural, economic, political and institutional barriers. Addressing the European-global challenges of cities, InCITIES has 4 objectives: 1) Map institutional transformation strategies towards research-based sustainable universities including open science and career opportunities. 2) Build a long-term network of participating HEIs and surrounding ecosystems based on integrated knowledge HUBs. 3) Increase scientific, technological and staff capacity by sharing the best pedagogical, research, management and administrative practices in the consortium, and piloting leverages to widening HEIs. 4) Promote digitally driven universities by creating an open and innovative education and training platform in synergy with the project research and innovation agenda on inclusive, sustainable and resilient cities. The 5 methods jointly developed will set the foundation for the consortium role model: 1) Method for a common research map, 2) Capacity building actions based on the Learning by Developing a pedagogical model, 3) Capacity building in talent scout and career opportunity strategy (attractiveness of research careers, including open science incentives), 4) Capacity building on equality, diversity and inclusion, 5) Methods to address enablers and barriers to integration of the InCITIES Alliance. From knowledge cocreation to joint production between European HEIs, surrounding ecosystems and citizens' involvement, integrated actions play a key role in achieving the consortium objectives. Capacity-building actions implemented are a step towards the submission to the European Universities Initiative; it will strengthen the ERA, the EEA, and Europe's approach to cooperation in R&I.

About the course

The course is taking place between the 19th of February and the 26th of April 2024 with 9 weekly online modules and 1 week of on-site seminars.

Audio-visual recording

Online modules will be delivered via Microsoft Teams and all sessions will be recorded, apart from the breakout room discussions. The recordings will be available for those participants who miss the class or for improving the content and quality of the modules. In case this

course will be repeated in the future, the content of the recordings might be used for educational purposes and/or for attracting participants. The audio-visual file will be saved on a secure server at UNIZA.

Video

During the onsite seminar, there will be some video shooting to support the production of a short video intended for distribution on social media. The video will present the overall scope of InCITIES project, the methodologies developed and applied, as well as results and activities implemented throughout the course. A few students will be asked, voluntarily, to provide some insights on their experience from the course, their motivation in attending such a course, and examples of helpful learnings related to Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient cities. The purpose of the video is to provide some evidence to all InCITIES partner organisations that this initiative is important and relevant, focusing on institutional transformation strategies towards research-based sustainable universities to engage viewers on social media. Furthermore, it can provide some motivating video to attract students for the next year(s), in case the course is repeated.

The video is intended for dissemination in the InCITIES project communication channels ([website](#), [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts), and via individual project partner communication platforms.

Photos

During the onsite seminar, there will be some photo shooting, to support the promotion of the course results. The photos are intended for dissemination in the InCITIES project communication channels ([website](#), [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) social media accounts), and via individual project partner communication platforms.

Personal Data

Your name and contact data will only be documented in the participants list administrated by the course organising team, and not accessible to third parties. Any kind of public publications will be fully anonymised. Reports to the European Commission will include your organisation's name and information about your position therein. In case you do not agree, please indicate your demand for full anonymization in the Informed Consent Form attached.

Right to withdraw

You have the right to terminate your participation at any time without any consequences. In addition, you have the right to access your data at any time, to correct it, to delete it, to restrict its processing or to object to it. You can also withdraw from the declaration of consent below at any time.

If you have any questions please contact the course organisers at circular.incities@uniza.sk or Prof Ing. Tatiana Kovacicova at tatiana.kovacicova@uniza.sk.

Informed Consent Form

In signing this consent form, I confirm that (please circle):

I have read the Participant Information Sheet and the nature and purpose of the activity has been explained to me.	YES	NO
I have had the opportunity to ask questions.	YES	NO
I understand the purpose of the dissemination activities (recordings, video, photos) and my involvement in it.	YES	NO
I understand that I may withdraw from the project by means of a written notification to the contact indicated below at any stage and that this will not affect my status now or in the future.	YES	NO
I understand that while information gained during the workshop may be published, I will not be identified and my personal data will remain confidential.	YES	NO
I agree that the organisation I am affiliated with will be named in reports to the European Commission, while organisations' names will be anonymized in all publicly accessible publications unless there is explicit approval.	YES	NO
I understand that the course documentation (recordings, video, photos) will be stored electronically for a maximum period of 3 years after completion of InCITIES project.	YES	NO

Any concerns?

If you have any concerns or complaints about your rights as a participant in this course, please contact the course organisers at circular.incities@uniza.sk or Prof Ing. Tatiana Kovacikova at tatiana.kovacikova@uniza.sk.

Signed

Print name Date

Annex XVI - Full text of email sent to the selected UNIZA pilot course participants to collect accommodation and travel information

Dear Sustainable Mobility Innovations BIP course participants!

To help us organize your accommodation during the onsite week in April and the shuttle bus to Zilina and back, we kindly ask you to provide to us the following information:

1. Do you need accommodation at UNIZA dormitories for the onsite week? (Yes/No)
2. Please, provide exact dates when you request the dormitory accommodation (if applicable).
3. All rooms are shared by 2 people. If you have a preference for a roommate, please indicate his/her name.
4. In the case you are travelling by plane, send us the airport of your arrival and departure as well as the date and time of your flights.

Please, send us the abovementioned information **by Wednesday, 28th of February** at the latest, so we can make the necessary arrangements in advance.

Thank you!

Warmest regards,
The UNIZA InCITIES project team